

Navigating the Evolving EU Neurotechnology Landscape: A Multi-Regulatory Analysis

Master Thesis

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
“Master of Laws” - “LL.M.”

Master Program:
LL.M. Digital Business & Tech Law

Executive Education
MCI – The Entrepreneurial School

Supervisor:
Prof. Dr. Markus Frischhut, LL.M.

Author:
Tania Alejandra Gonzalez Alfaro, MBA
52420161

Date of submission:
09. October 2025

Total Quantity of Words: 19600

Declaration in Lieu of Oath

I hereby declare, under oath, that this master thesis has been my independent work and has not been aided with any prohibited means. I declare, to the best of my knowledge and belief, that all passages taken from published and un-published sources or documents have been reproduced whether as original, slightly altered or in thought, have been declared as such at the corresponding places of the thesis, by citation, where the extent of the original quotes is indicated.

The paper has neither been submitted for evaluation to another examination authority nor has been published in this form or another.

Innsbruck, 09. October, 2025

Tania Alejandra Gonzalez Alfaro

(Signature)

Acknowledgements

Dedicated to my family and friends in both continents, supporting me in this professional and personal journey, as well as my continuous studies along the years.

THANK YOU!

Abstract

This thesis investigates the fragmented and often ambiguous regulatory landscape governing non-medical brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) and brain data wearables in the European Union, addressing the critical gaps that emerge when these devices operate outside of a medical context. By conducting a detailed analysis of key EU regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the AI Act (AIA), the General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR), and the Medical Device Regulation (MDR), this research aims to identify where current frameworks fall short in ensuring consumer privacy and safety. A secondary review of the Radio Equipment Directive (RED), Cyber Resilience Act (CRA), and other relevant standards, further highlights the need for a comprehensive and harmonized approach to address issues of cybersecurity and data integrity. The findings of this research provide a crucial legal and technical framework for regulators, manufacturers, and researchers, offering a path toward harmonized governance that can foster innovation while protecting fundamental rights in the expanding field of consumer neurotechnology.

Keywords: Neurotechnologies, Brain-Computer Interfaces, Wearables, European Regulatory Framework, Legal Neuro Recommendations, Neurosecurity

Gender Disclaimer

For reasons of readability, the simultaneous use of male and female pronouns, as well as diverse language forms, is avoided. All personal pronouns expressly apply equally to all genders.

Table of Contents

List of Figures.....	III
List of Tables.....	IV
List of Abbreviations	V
1. Introduction.....	1
1.1. Motivation.....	4
1.2. Problem Statement and Objectives	5
1.3. Methodology and Structure	6
2. What is Neurotechnology?.....	7
3. Potential Risks and Legal Consequences.....	15
4. Focused Analysis of the Regulatory Landscape	17
4.1. Medical Device Regulation (MDR).....	17
4.1.1. The Regulation Overview	17
4.1.2. Software Coverage.....	22
4.1.3. Are Neurotechnologies covered by the MDR?.....	24
4.1.4. Potential Open Considerations	29
4.2. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).....	32
4.2.1. The Regulation and Our Rights	32
4.2.2. Vulnerable Populations	33
4.2.3. Mental Data, Mental Health and Public Interest.....	37
4.2.4. Moving Forward	42
4.3. Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA).....	45
4.3.1. The Regulation.....	45
4.3.2. Biometrics and Emotional Recognition.....	46
4.3.3. Transparency and Vulnerable Groups.....	49

4.3.4. Data Sharing	50
4.3.5. Future-Proof Resilience	51
4.3.6. Latest Releases.....	56
4.4. General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR).....	59
4.4.1. The Regulation.....	59
4.4.2. Software Observations	64
4.4.3. Further Standards.....	65
5. Potential Recommendations	67
6. Conclusion	72
7. Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted Technologies	74
8. Bibliography	75
9. Annexes	94
9.1. Events, Conferences and Memberships	94
9.2. Supplementary Terminology.....	95
9.3. Hacking the Mind: A Step-by-Step Guide to Building a BCI	96
9.4. Future Educational Modules in this Area	97
9.5. Recommended Related ISO Standards.....	98
9.6. Cultural Bonus	99

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Private Sector Signals	7
Figure 2 - 2024 Neurotech Funding Snapshot.....	8
Figure 3 - Types of Neurotechnologies.....	8
Figure 4 - Neuroimaging Techniques	9
Figure 5 - Neurotechnology Examples	10
Figure 6 - Emotiv MW20	10
Figure 7 - End to End (E2E) Process for body data capture and transmission.....	11
Figure 8 - New Wireless Neuro Earphones – Tracked Mental States. Emotiv.....	14
Figure 9 - Medical Device Classification Comparison.....	18
Figure 10 - Understanding Medical Device Classifications	19
Figure 11 - Overview of the neurotechnological device regulations under the EU MDR	26
Figure 12 - Democracy index: Economist Intelligence Unit 2024	40
Figure 13 - Number of countries experiencing autocratization and democratization since 1900	41
Figure 14 - The Concentric - Circle Hard-Soft Law Continuum for NPI Protection	43
Figure 15 - Between Science-Fact and Science-Fiction: Innovation and Ethics in Neurotechnology.....	49
Figure 16 – Our <i>Personal Command Center</i> landscape of risk.....	53
Figure 17 - Brain Data Security and Neurosecurity	54
Figure 18 - Alterego wearable - Sketch to App Camera Testing	58
Figure 19 - Meta/Ray-Ban New AI Glasses and Meta Neural Band	62
Figure 20 - Recommendations. International Human Rights Protection Gaps in the Age of the Neurotechnology	69

List of Tables

Table 1 - Potential Neurotechnology Risks versus EU Applicable Laws.....	16
Table 2 - Neurotechnology Recommendations.....	71

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
3D	Three dimensional
ADHS	Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act EU
Art.	Article
AR	Augmented Reality
BCI or BCIs	Brain Computer Interfaces
BCI-HID	Brain-Computer Interface - Human Interface Device: protocol
BMI	Brain Machine Interface
CCTV Footage	Closed-Circuit Television Recording (Video Security and Monitoring)
CD	Committee Draft
CDR	Corporate Digital Responsibility Austria
CE Marking	Conformité Européenne Marking (EU)
CISM or CISM's	Certified Information Security Manager
CRA	Cyber Resilience Act
CTRL-Labs	Read as CONTROL-Labs (USA Technology Brand)
DEFCON	Defense Readiness Condition
DMA	Digital Markets Act EU
DNI	Direct Neural Interface
DPAs	Data Processing Agreements
DSA	Digital Services Act EU
DTC	Direct-to-Consumer
E2E	End to End
EAA	European Accessibility Act
EC	European Commission
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
EEGs	Electroencephalograms
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
EMG	Electromyography Diagnostic Procedure
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
et al.	Et aliter
Etc.	Et cetera
EU	European Union
Eudamed	European Database on medical devices
e.g.,	exempli gratia (in Latin). For example (in English)

FDA	Food and Drugs Administration: USA Agency
fMRI	Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging
FOMO	Fear of Missing Out
GB	Gigabits
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation EU
GNM	Global Neuroscience Market
GPSR	General Product Safety Regulation EU
GPT	Generative Pre-training Transformer (AI Type)
HW	Hardware
Ibid.	Ibidem. In the same place
IBM	International Business Machines (USA Technology Brand)
IDS	Intrusion Detection Systems
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE SA	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Standard Association
IoTs	Internet of the Things (Devices with sensors and connectivity)
IP	Intellectual Property
ISACA	Information Systems Audit and Control Association
ISEE	Information Security Engineering Environment
ISMS	Information Security Management System
ISO	International Standards Organization
IVD	In Vitro Diagnostic
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
KPMG	Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler (UK Services Network)
LLM	Large Language Model: AI
MDCG	Medical Device Coordination Group
MDD	Medical Device Directive EU
MDPIA	Mental Data Protection Impact Assessment
MDR	Medical Device Regulation EU
MIND	Management of Individuals' Neural Data – US Act
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MMI	Mind Machine Interface
MS	EU Member States
MW20	Emotiv's wireless neuro earphones model
NDAs	Non-Disclosure Agreements
NIS2	Network and Information Security Directive EU
No	Numero: Number
NPI	Neural Personal Information
NT or NTs	Neurotechnologies
ÖNormen	Austrian Standards
p. or pp.	Page Number or Page Numbers
PDF	Portable Document Format

PLA	Polylactic Acid (Natural Thermoplastic Polyester)
RAPEX	Rapid Alert System for Dangerous Non-Food Products: Safety Gate EU
RED	Radio Equipment Directive EU
RMB	Renminbi (RMB) = Yuan (CNY): Chinese Official Currency
TÜV	Technischer Überwachungsverein: Technical Inspection Association
UAE	United Arab Emirates
UBI	Universal Basic Income
UDI	Unique Device Identifier
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UK or U.K.	United Kingdom
US, USA or U.S.A.	United States of America
USD	United States Dollar
VLOP	Very Large Online Platform
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VR or VR/AR	Virtual Reality / Augmented Reality
“We”	Refers to us as society, professionals, and/or all readers.
WEF	World Economic Forum
WHO	World Health Organization

Other considerations

The following terms have been used indistinctively: NT Data, Brain data, Neurodata, Neuro data, Mental data and Neural data.

1. Introduction

As technology rapidly moves forward, with products like Generative AI, metaverse, face recognition and brain productivity gadgets, smart cities, quantum and biocomputing, we must stop and reflect. Are these new technologies fully covered by the existing regulations? Which risks can they bring to the society and future generations? How can we proactively address them?

This Master Thesis has the intention to investigate these newest neurotechnologies, their possible implications and gaps, their intricate connection with the European Union regulations, as well as to generate public awareness and gather a series of recommendations for them.

This paper focuses on Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) and neuro-wearables. The Council of the European Union has defined BCI as: “[...] an array of neurotechnologies which enable direct communication between the brain and an external device. BCIs detect and interpret the brain’s electrical signals and convert these neural impulses into computer-executable commands, enabling users to interact with computers or control devices purely through mental processes whilst bypassing the need for physical movement.”¹

Over the last decade, “[...] several strategic BCI plans have been launched, such as the U.S. Brain Initiative, the E.U. Human Brain Project, and the China Brain Project.”² According to Wei et al. (2025), “In 2011, the Chinese Ministry of Science and Technology launched the ‘National Twelfth Five-Year Plan for Science and Technology Development, ‘designating brain science as a key research priority in basic sciences. In 2021, the ministry officially initiated the ‘Brain Science and Brain-like Research’ project under the

¹ Council of the European Union, Research Paper, From vision to reality: Promises and risks of Brain-Computer Interfaces 2024, p.4.

² Wei et al., 2025, pp.1-2.

Science and Technology Innovation 2030 major initiative, which covers 59 research fields and directions with a projected national investment exceeding 3.148 billion RMB.”³ China has been exceeding the 100 patents annually, in the last three years.⁴

Besides the typical medical BCI uses, “Neurotechnologies may also become incorporated into common digital technologies such as smart watches or earphones to measure nervous system activity.”⁵ Or even in clothing as the Google’s Jacquard Project, which “transforms fabric into a touch-sensitive surface, allowing users to interact with their devices seamlessly and intuitively through gestures made on their clothes.”⁶ The Google Blog stated, “The first early adopter of the Jacquard platform was Levi’s® [...] across six countries (Australia, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, U.K. and USA) [...] Jacquard Tag—which is smaller than a stick of gum and has a battery life of up to two weeks...with a Camera ability and new Google Assistant [...] with a gesture [...]”.⁷

Although, the Jacquard Project seem to be able to detect touch, and gestures, there are others like “NextMind”, a French company, who developed a similar tag but with the capability of translating brain signals from the visual cortex into digital commands in real time.⁸ While not recommended for infants, epileptic patients, exterior conditions (rain, sweat, etc.) and not for longer than 1 hour without a 15-minute break⁹, seems to be dragging a lot of attention of confidential customers and buyers.

Even if the USA and China have taken the lead in AI and neurotechnologies, Germany, France, among other EU countries keep accelerating their pace in this field, though with an extra focus in the pharmaceutical industry.¹⁰ And due to this reason, the European Commission, UNESCO and other nations are rushing to develop the first set of studies and frameworks that will be applicable to them.

³ Wei et al., 2025, p.4.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Bublitz et al., 2024, p.2.

⁶ R., 2024. (*Author’s Full Last Name not found).

⁷ Poupyrev, 2019.

⁸ STWS, 2024.

⁹ Next Mind, 2022.

¹⁰ UNESCO, Unveiling the Neurotechnology Landscape, 2023.

To mention a few milestones, Chile has approved the first regulation on mental rights, Spain has also made a significant related legal enhancement¹¹, and thanks to the UNESCO awareness initiatives, further recommendations have been provided to multiple regions of the world, specially to the global south. For example, in Costa Rica, a Central American country, the neuro risks were formally presented in 2022, and a neurorights law project was introduced to the Parliament on 2024¹², while not yet approved, it is an attest to the great communication that UNESCO has been doing. Brazil, Mexico and Colombia seem to be making progress on this area as well.¹³ While these efforts are merely starting, much more work remains to be done.

Most recently, on September 24th, 2025, three US Senators introduced a novel bill in the US Congress called “Management of Individuals’ Neural Data Act of 2025” (MIND Act).¹⁴ It addresses topics like mind and behavior manipulation, monetization of neural data, neuromarketing, erosion of personal autonomy, discrimination, surveillance, unauthorized access to the minds by foreign actors and misuses in the areas of employment, healthcare, financial services, housing, education, law enforcement and criminal justice.¹⁵

The “Brussels Effect”¹⁶ (the influence that the EU has had in the world, especially in the regulation’s field) has been predominant, however, in the neurotechnology arena, it has not yet made a bolder move.

¹¹ Chavarriaga et al., 2023, p.9.

¹² Asamblea Legislativa Republica de Costa Rica, n.d.

¹³ UNESCO, Towards A Draft Text of a Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology, 2024, p.42.

¹⁴ U.S. Senate Committee on Commerce, Science, & Transportation, 2025.

¹⁵ Cooley, 2025.

¹⁶ Bradford, 2020.

1.1. Motivation

The last decade has been marked by significant global investments in neurotechnologies. Deloitte's 2023 analysis of the global neuroscience market (GNM) highlights the rapid growth of this novel sector, valuing it at US\$612 billion in 2022, and estimating projections of over US\$721 billion by 2026.¹⁷

Neurotechnologies represent the start of an exciting new technology era, with promising revolutionary applications and human and computing augmented capabilities, but at the same time, it has the power to challenge our societies, ethic, human rights, values, use cases, and much more.

Genser et al. (2022) explained, "Emerging technologies are no longer solely concerns for accessibility, privacy, and discrimination-related reasons. Today, neurotechnology also presents concerns for mental integrity, free will, the development of thought, the protection of due process, and inequality of human enhancement."¹⁸ Therefore, the novelty and disruptive potential of consumer BCIs necessitate a thorough examination of how existing legal frameworks can adapt to regulate them effectively, ensuring innovation, competitiveness, the protection of fundamental rights and vulnerable populations, and the prevention of misuses and cyber-attacks.

This paper aims to proactively contribute to the current legal frameworks, facilitating a clearer understanding for professionals to easily navigate through the complexities that currently surround them, and that we will see more clearly coming in the upcoming years, as the technologies continue to expand, particularly concerning BCIs and Direct-to-Consumer (DTC) neurotechnologies.

Additionally, it is crucial to keep generating awareness about these cutting-edge innovations and identifying the areas that might still need focused attention, from legal professionals and legislators.

¹⁷ Perez et al., 2023.

¹⁸ Genser et al., 2022, p.6.

1.2. Problem Statement and Objectives

The problem statement resides on the following questions: Are these technologies currently covered by European Union legal frameworks? If so, which regulations are currently applicable to them? Are they appropriate?

An analysis of the following key regulations will be developed, the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR), the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA), and the General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR). Main areas of attention will be emphasized.

The following objectives will contribute to answer the questions above:

- Explain what neurotechnologies are, specially BCIs (Brain-Computer Interfaces).
- Assess the current associated legal regulations, mainly the MDR, GDPR, AI Act, GPSR regulations and potential areas of attention.
- Explore the possible legal risks, implications and further observations.
- Gather overall recommendations to those risks, when appropriate.

1.3. Methodology and Structure

This paper was developed with the following qualitative methodologies:

- Exploratory research on brain-related technologies.
- Legal analysis and association of the current regulations that apply to them.
- Further research and an inductive approach will be used to find possible recommendations that could bring value to both, technology and legal areas.

Data collection will be based on numerous legal and academia scientific papers, available online, and the analysis of the MDR, GDPR, AI Act and the GPSR regulations. Although other regulations worldwide might apply, for example FDA Medical Device Regulation (USA),¹⁹ or Data Protection Law (LGPD) in Brazil,²⁰ among many others, this document will only focus on the ones mentioned above, specific for the European Union.

Finally, and when suitable, complementing data of neurotechnology scientific and legal conferences and events will be included. The list is available under the Annex 9.1.

¹⁹ Chavarriaga et al., 2023, p.9.

²⁰ Magee et al., 2024, p.3021.

2. What is Neurotechnology?

“According to UNESCO, during the last decades, neuroscience has been one of the most dynamic areas of research and innovation, with an increasing number of patents (from less than 500 in 2000 to over 12,000 in 2020), scientific publications (reaching 1.2 million in 2021) and investments (the neurotechnology devices market is expected to reach USD 24.2 billion by 2027).”²¹ As shown in Figure 1, the expected growth of only the private sector is 10%.

Private Sector Signals

CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM MARKET IS EXPECTED TO GROW 10% IN THE NEXT 5 YEARS, WITH GROWTH IN BOTH NEURODEGENERATIVE AND MENTAL HEALTH THERAPIES

Figure 1 - Private Sector Signals²²

“Neurotechnology (NT) is an umbrella term which broadly refers to any device or method that can be used to record or modify human neural activity. NTs result from the convergence of scientific innovations in various fields, including neuroscience, computer science, bioengineering, chemistry, medical science, and material science. They include a diverse array of devices and methods which seek “to access, monitor, investigate, assess, manipulate, and/or stimulate the structure and function of the neural

²¹ UNESCO, Preliminary Report on the first draft of the Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology, 2024.

²² Eyre, Private Sector Signals, Slide #12, 2025.

systems of natural persons.” Through their direct connection to the brain, these technologies can interfere with an individual’s mental states and processes.”²³

In Figure 2, the Global Neurotech Summit 2025 reported the investment going to the neurotechnologies during 2024 was US\$2.3 billion, focused on 129 deals, which 72% were for non-implanted deals, US\$571 million were specifically for BCIs, US\$124 million for sleep related technologies and US\$66 million for DTC neurotechnologies.

Figure 2 - 2024 Neurotech Funding Snapshot²⁴

These technologies facilitate the merge of the brain and nervous system functions (Neuroscience) with tools and devices (Engineering). NTs can be categorized according to their main purpose, as below (Figure 3).²⁵

Figure 3 - Types of Neurotechnologies²⁶

²³ Istace et al., 2024, p.2.

²⁴ Eyre, 2024 Neurotech Funding Snapshot, Slide #10, 2025.

²⁵ Istace et al., 2024, p.2.

²⁶ Ibid. (Table: Self-created. Content based on: Istace, et al., 2024, p.2).

These multiple types and styles of NTs use various methodologies and techniques, which will not be covered in this paper. Figure 4 illustrates some of them.

Figure 4 - Neuroimaging Techniques²⁷

Some of the neurotechnologies, for example the Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) also referred to as Mind Machine Interface (MMI), Direct Neural Interface (DNI), Brain Machine Interface (BMI), “create direct pathways for communication between an enhanced or wired brain and external devices. This technology can restore function for those with disabilities, for instance, enabling individuals with spinal cord injuries to control limbs, wheelchairs, or computers with their thoughts.”²⁸, which serves as medical devices, and others in the areas of wellness, gaming, education and employment, for non-medical purposes.

Categorization problems might arise, “For instance, the same wearable neurostimulator for the treatment of insomnia and anxiety is considered a wellness application in some countries (the UK and the EU) but in others (the US) requires approval under the medical device regulation. This blurring of the lines between medical and non-medical devices raises a number of concerns. For example, manufacturers of non-medical NTs may claim that their devices offer medical benefits, or consumers with

²⁷ University of York, Europe Campus, CITY College, 2025.

²⁸ The Centre for Neurotechnology and Law, 2024.

reduced access to medical care may turn to commercial devices to address health issues.”²⁹

Figure 5 - Neurotechnology Examples³⁰

Portable BCIs have many appearances, which will not be covered here. To exemplify some of them, see Figure 5. In Figure 6, the newest in the market, the Emotiv MW20³¹ which claimed to be the world’s first wireless neuro earphones with Hi-Fi Audio.

Figure 6 - Emotiv MW20³²

²⁹ Istace et al., 2024, p.8.

³⁰ University of York, Europe Campus, CITY College, 2025.

³¹ Emotiv, 2025.

³² Ibid.

Their multiple sensors transmit data back to web platforms, applications and provider infrastructures, where they are analyzed with the help of many methodologies and AI/Machine Learning systems, which ultimately opens the scenario to risks in numerous areas of cybersecurity. A simplified view of the process available in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - End to End (E2E) Process for body data capture and transmission

As mentioned by the European Commission, “Personal wearable sensors could become the most powerful individual self-surveillance technology available to citizens. These ubiquitous, networked devices currently offer a breadth of capabilities to sense, digitally enhance and upload data of fine granularity such as body and health physiological functions, images, locations, sounds and motion.”³³

³³ EC, JRC, Wearable Sensors and Digital Platforms in Health, 2015, p.5.

It is essential to clarify some conceptual differences. In Annex 9.2 other relevant terminologies are also available.

- a) Implantable (invasive) devices assist patients with physical disabilities, to enhance their ability to communicate, walk and achieve greater independence. This is accomplished when implanted in the head (intracranially or subcutaneously), manually or even with robotic-assisted methods, as “Neuralink”³⁴. Some of them can get charged as any wireless cell phone charger and can be directly connected and managed by the user’s cell phone application and/or by the provider devices and computers, when onsite (as far as it has been openly informed). They tend to be medical-focused.

“[...] in 2018, the MIT Media Lab used an invasive BCI to transcribe human thoughts into typed messages, reading neural signals from the wearer’s brain – but not writing back to it. [...] In 2019, a group of scientists conducting research in laboratory animals discovered that repeatedly stimulating certain parts of a mouse’s brain could cause the mouse to behave in a predetermined way – such as repeatedly drinking – after the manipulation of its sensory experiences.”³⁵

- b) Non-invasive devices are portable/wearable devices designed to address a range of non-clinical applications, including cognitive enhancement for concentration, focus, and learning, as well as optimizing sleep patterns and overall efficiency. Furthermore, it provides a way to reduce physical risk by enabling the remote operation of hazardous equipment or serving as an exclusive hands-free control system for interactive media like video games. Providers like Emotiv, Microsoft, Meta, Apple, IBM, Fujitsu, Samsung, Intel, Siemens, Sony, Hitachi, and several more³⁶ are marketing it differently, some as achieving peak human performance and as the full symbiosis between humans and machines.³⁷

³⁴ Neuralink, 2025.

³⁵ Genser et al., 2022, p.12.

³⁶ UNESCO, 2023, Unveiling the Neurotechnology Landscape, p.12.

³⁷ Reed, 2024.

To complement, Genser et al. (2022) explain as follows, “Non-invasive BCIs, [...] are typically considered electronic consumer devices and face few regulations for data privacy or accessibility. They include wearable helmets, glasses, diadems, caps, wristbands, and headbands which can read brain activity, and/or peripheral nervous system activity, by touching a person’s head or body (rather than directly touching the brain). Recent examples of their use include sharing images and words between two people in different rooms, which allowed the two to communicate. Non-invasive BCIs also have enabled a person who is quadriplegic to drive a Formula One race car, and a person who is paraplegic to make the first kick of the World Cup using a mind-controlled robotic exoskeleton. CTRL-Labs developed a wristband that may be the first consumer product to use neural activity to translate intentions, gestures, and motions into computer control of movements of a robotic avatar. And Kernel released the Flow helmet in the fall of 2020, which maps brain activity with unprecedented and detailed accuracy.”³⁸

UNESCO believes an additional case from the non-invasive BCIs could be that it is used as lie detectors and highlighted, how the concept of consciousness would change: “Prospects of powerful lie detectors and their potential applications in society became debated. Clinical applications of such tools detected signs of consciousness in comatose patients who were diagnosed as unconscious, leading to an urgent medical and ethical conundrum as the moral status of these patients still needs to be addressed.”³⁹

- c) Mental states: “[...] are typically named in commonsense terms, such as emotions (e.g., fear, disgust, love), cognitions (e.g., retrieving a memory, planning the future, concentrating on a task), perceptions (e.g., face perception, color perception, sound perception), and so on.”⁴⁰ Below the “Emotiv” Mental States dashboard, which gathers the details from the Neuro-earphones.

³⁸ Genser et al., 2022, p.11.

³⁹ UNESCO, 2024. Towards a Draft Text of a Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology, p.4.

⁴⁰ Oosterwijk et al., 2012, p.1.

Figure 8 - New Wireless Neuro Earphones – Tracked Mental States. Emotiv⁴¹

⁴¹ Emotiv, 2025.

3. Potential Risks and Legal Consequences

The table in the next page presents the overall identified risks by its overarching categories. In addition to the clustered risks, a variety of general legal liabilities could arise from the use of direct-to-consumer (DTC) neurotechnologies. Individuals who utilize these NTs to commit criminal offenses may face significant legal repercussions, including sanctions, criminal prosecution, imprisonment and financial penalties. Concurrently, organizations that facilitate or condone such illicit activities could also be held criminally liable. Manufacturers, importers and distributors of these devices could face strict liability claims for damages resulting from defective products or a failure to comply with established contracts, performance metrics and regulatory standards. The potential for these devices to be used for surveillance purposes could also lead to substantial fines and severe legal action. Moreover, any contracts found to involve fraud, coercion, illegal practices, or other immoral activities could be rendered void, potentially impacting the companies, owners, and stakeholders involved, depending on the severity and scale of the events.⁴²

Regarding legal and ethical considerations, the use of neurotechnology is subject to several significant liabilities under regulations such as GDPR, cybersecurity and AI frameworks. Data protection authorities can and will impose substantial fines on organizations that violate these regulations. Courts may order the destruction or modification of devices or data used in an infringement, and liabilities can be claimed in cross-border transactions if data is mismanaged.⁴³

Beyond organizational liability, large language models could face fines and be forced to discard a model if it was trained on sensitive data without proper consent.⁴⁴ In the medical field, a different set of liabilities applies. Medical professionals and psychotherapists may be held accountable for negligent or non-consented use of neurotechnology medical devices, which could lead to the revocation of their licenses and additional fines.⁴⁵

⁴² Bösch, *Vertragsrecht Summer Semester, 2025*.

⁴³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), OJ 2016 L 119.

⁴⁴ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AIA), OJ 2024 L 1689.

⁴⁵ Österreichischer Bundesverband für Psychotherapie, n.d.

Table 1 - Potential Neurotechnology Risks versus EU Applicable Laws

Topic	Neurotechnology Risks	Main Applicable European Regulations
Health and Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct physical or psychological harm (e.g., side effects of brain stimulation, surgical risks of invasive devices). - Unknown long-term effects of consumer neurodevices. - Lack of rigorous regulatory scrutiny for non-medical consumer neurotechnologies with health implications. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Medical Devices Regulation (MDR) (EU) 2017/745 - MDR Implementing Regulations (EU)2022/2346 and (EU) 2022/2347 for Non-Medical Devices. - General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR) and Consumer Protection Regulations - AI Act (AIA) Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 - National Criminal Laws - Soft law: Medical & Psychiatric Associations, Code of Ethics
Mental Privacy, Dignity, Autonomy & Freedom of Thought	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unauthorized access, social engineering, inference of sensitive mental states (thoughts, emotions, intentions). - Cognitive surveillance by institutional actors (e.g., Education and Private Sectors, non-democratic public authorities). - Subliminal manipulation, threat or distortion of behavior affecting free choice and autonomy, including Neuromarketing. - Alteration of self-perception, attention, mood, memory, personality, memories, cognitive abilities and decision-making. - Other Ethical Dilemmas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Regulation (EU) 2016/679 - Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 - AI Act (AIA) Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 - Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union - National Criminal Laws
Data Protection & Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hacking and cybersecurity threats to neural devices and related data storage systems. - Misuse, unauthorized disclosure, or inadequate handling of highly sensitive neural and cognitive biometric data. - Gaps in existing data protection frameworks to specifically address the unique nature of neural data (cognitive-affective). - Neurodata biased algorithms leading to unfair profiling, categorization, or discriminatory outcomes (e.g., sensitive attributes like race, political opinions). - Social marketing overcontrol, data exploitation and monopolization of neurodata, with potential risks of re-identification of pseudonymized data and inappropriate use cases. - Lack of an aligned international governance/regulation. Major contrasting perspectives & focuses (Welfare vs Economic Boom). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Regulation (EU) 2016/679 - Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 - NIS2 Directive (EU) 2022/2555 - National Criminal Laws - AI Act (AIA) Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 - General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR) and Consumer Protection Regulations - European Electronic Communications Code (EECC) Directive (EU) 2018/1972 - Radio Equipment Directive 2014/53/EU
National Security & Dual-Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential military applications or state surveillance, e.g., remote un-manned vehicles, weapons. - Vulnerability of neurotechnology systems and malicious cyber-attacks for espionage or disruption. - Difficulty distinguishing between civilian and military research, leading to proliferation concerns. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 - AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689) - General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR) - Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, other National Security Laws - Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP), Treaty on European Union (TEU)
Innovation, Equitable Access & Social Justice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overly strict or premature regulation, stifling groundbreaking research and development of beneficial medical or assistive NTs. - Unclear legal landscape creating uncertainty for innovators and investors. - Unequal global development and access to beneficial neurotechnologies, exacerbating health and societal disparities. - Potential enhancement of human capabilities and new forms of social stratification. - Lack of inclusivity in design and deployment, potentially marginalizing vulnerable populations. - Social norm alterations, in areas like employment, creativity, education, leisure and social interaction. - Addiction and over dependence of neurotechnologies. - The Council of the EU even included “telepathy”, cross-species connections and digital recording of person life experiences, as some of the long-term applications for it. (Council of the European Union, 2024). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union - UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology (Soft Law) - AI Act (AIA) Regulation (EU) 2024/1689

4. Focused Analysis of the Regulatory Landscape

4.1. Medical Device Regulation (MDR)

4.1.1. *The Regulation Overview*

When analyzing the EU MDR regulation and the further related regulations (Regulation (EU) 2020/561, Regulation (EU) 2022/112, Regulation (EU) 2023/60, Regulation (EU) 2024/1860 and (EU) 2022/2346, (EU) 2022/2347 and (EU) 2023/1194), the first two noticed observations were: a) how complex it has been to implement it fully, in which situations like the COVID19 worldwide pandemic, or the complications from some State Members to comply fast enough with all requirements and workflows, like the notified bodies, clinical investigations, performance studies, the conformity assessments, the tooling, among others, seem to have impacted, and b) how technology keeps progressing so rapidly, that keeps putting pressure to the system on how to regulate them accordingly and in a timely manner.

Diving into the MDR, what is the MDR (Medical Device Regulation)? Bublitz et al. (2024) described it as: “The legal foundation for regulating medical devices in the EU [...] adopted in 2016 and came into effect in 2021. It replaced the Medical Device Directive (MDD) and numerous other EU laws.”⁴⁶

In terms of scope, the MDR addresses mainly medical devices, but it takes non-medical devices under consideration as well, as per Article 1(3): “Devices with both a medical and a non-medical intended purpose shall fulfil cumulatively the requirements applicable [...]”⁴⁷ It applies “[...] to the groups of products without an intended medical purpose that are listed in Annex XVI, taking into account the state of the art, and in particular existing harmonised standards for analogous devices with a medical purpose, based on similar technology. The common specifications for each of the groups of products listed in Annex XVI shall address, at least, application of risk management as set out in Annex I for the group of products in question and, where necessary, clinical

⁴⁶ Bublitz et al., 2024, p.3.

⁴⁷ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR), OJ 2017 L 117, Article 1(3).

evaluation regarding safety.”⁴⁸ Foreseeing the need of incorporating some non-medical intended devices, highlights the importance of respecting the fundamental rights and principles of the Charter, especially human dignity, integrity of the person, personal data protection, freedom of science, art, conducting business and property rights. Its relevance pertains to all devices placed on the market.⁴⁹

The MDR uses a 4-layer classification process (similar to the USA and Canada,⁵⁰ in Figure 9, which will not be covered in this document), these layers are based on the potential risk impact, the device could be involved in, and on the probability of the risk to occur.

Figure 9 - Medical Device Classification Comparison⁵¹

The four risk classes are I, IIa, IIb, and III, being class I the lower risk category and class III the highest risk.⁵² The following image (Figure 10) can easily illustrate it. It is also important to mention that class I has the particularity that is the only class, in which the majority of the cases, that will not be requiring a Notified Body approval and will only be needing a self-assessment; there are exceptions where the Notified Body has to be involved, for example in the case of class I devices with reusability capabilities, measuring features, among others.⁵³

⁴⁸ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR), OJ 2017 L 117, Article 1(2).

⁴⁹ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR), OJ 2017 L 117.

⁵⁰ VEM Medical.

⁵¹ Opoku Adusei, 2015.

⁵² Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR), OJ 2017 L 117.

⁵³ Ibid.

Figure 10 - Understanding Medical Device Classifications⁵⁴

Under the Article 2(1) - Definition of the MDR, highlights the following concepts which are key to understand the regulations and further observations. What are medical devices? “[...] any instrument, apparatus, appliance, software, implant, reagent, material or other article intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for human beings for one or more of the following specific medical purposes: diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment or alleviation of disease, diagnosis; monitoring, treatment, alleviation of, or compensation for, an injury or disability; investigation, replacement or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological or pathological process or state [...]”⁵⁵

⁵⁴ Byrne, 2025.

⁵⁵ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR), OJ 2017 L 117, Article 2(1).

“Intended purpose” comprehends “[...] the use for which a device is intended according to the data supplied by the manufacturer on the label, in the instructions for use or in promotional or sales materials or statements and as specified by the manufacturer in the clinical evaluation.”⁵⁶ This definition is directly interconnected to the concept of “performance” which is defined as the “the ability of a device to achieve its intended purpose as stated by the manufacturer [...]”.⁵⁷

“Informed consent”⁵⁸ has the particularity that must be free and voluntary, in cases of clinical investigations, and in case of minors it should be expressed by their legally designated representative. It's also worth mentioning, that the MDR assigns the responsibility of assigning specific protection measures to the Member States, regarding minors and vulnerable groups, as stated in “Incapacitated subjects, minors, pregnant women and breastfeeding women require specific protection measures. However, it should be left to Member States to determine the legally designated representatives of incapacitated subjects and minors.”⁵⁹

“Clinical investigations” are “any systematic investigation involving one or more human subjects, undertaken to assess the safety or performance of a device”⁶⁰, it is different from “clinical evaluation”, which refers to “a systematic and planned process to continuously generate, collect, analyse and assess the clinical data pertaining to a device in order to verify the safety and performance, including clinical benefits, of the device when used as intended by the manufacturer;”⁶¹ then what is “Clinical data”⁶²? it involves investigations, scientific literature and studies, peer review reports and even information rising from post-market surveillance and post-market clinical follow ups.

Medical devices should also have the capability of being interoperable with other devices from the same provider or even with different ones, including its software. They should also have an ‘Unique Device Identifier’ (‘UDI’),⁶³ standardized and accepted internationally, and registration obligations referred to in Articles 29 and 31, which

⁵⁶ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR), OJ 2017 L 117, Article 2(12).

⁵⁷ Ibid. Article 2(22).

⁵⁸ Ibid. Article 2(55).

⁵⁹ Ibid. Recital 72 and Article 64.

⁶⁰ Ibid. Article 2(45).

⁶¹ Ibid. Article 2(44).

⁶² Ibid. Article 2(48).

⁶³ Ibid. Article 2(15).

facilitates its traceability and post-sale requirements. The creation of the “*Eudamed*” (European Database on medical devices) complements the integration and centralization of the related information.⁶⁴

Depending on their risk categorization they might or not require a “conformity assessment”⁶⁵, which it is the manufacturers evidence that a particular device it is fully compliant to all requirements listed in this Regulation. These conformity assessments are tested, inspected and calibrated by *conformity assessment bodies*, more commonly known as a *notified bodies*. Medical devices can opt for obtaining a ‘*CE marking of conformity*’ or ‘*CE marking*’, this represents not only being aligned with this Regulation, but with other EU applicable legislations.

A device should not be place in the EU market, unless an authorized representative has been designated. Article 51, states, “In cases where the manufacturer has no registered place of business in the Union and has not yet designated an authorised representative, the matter shall be referred to the competent authority of the Member State in which the authorised representative referred to [...] has its registered place of business.”⁶⁶ ‘Authorised representative’ is understood as “any natural or legal person established within the Union who has received and accepted a written mandate from a manufacturer, located outside the Union, to act on the manufacturer's behalf [...]”⁶⁷

Manufacturers of medical devices are responsible for “post-market surveillance,”⁶⁸ contemplating all related activities that collaborate with the collection and review of feedback, lessons learned and information from their devices. Regarding their quality and performance, this applies to products that have been previously placed in the market. It is important to differentiate it from “market surveillance”,⁶⁹ which is exclusively used for measures and activities taken by the competent authorities to make sure all devices comply with the legislation requirements. Expanding on the information that the manufacturer should gather, as part of the post-market surveillance, the MDR recommends clinical evaluations, design and manufacturing details, instructions, safety

⁶⁴ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR), OJ 2017 L 117, Article 33.

⁶⁵ Ibid. Article 2(40).

⁶⁶ Ibid. Article 51(2).

⁶⁷ Ibid. Article 2(32).

⁶⁸ Ibid. Article 2(60).

⁶⁹ Ibid. Article 2(61).

and clinical performance, identification of preventive and corrective needs and actions, improvement opportunities, specially related to usability, performance and safety of the device, technical documentation and trends.

These activities are key to prevent *incidents*, “[...] malfunction or deterioration in the characteristics or performance of a device made available on the market, including use-error due to ergonomic features, as well as any inadequacy in the information supplied by the manufacturer and any undesirable side-effect;”⁷⁰ as well as *device deficiencies* which considers “[...] any inadequacy in the identity, quality, durability, reliability, safety or performance of an investigational device, including malfunction, use errors or inadequacy in information supplied by the manufacturer;”⁷¹ and “serious deteriorations,”⁷² for example a “medical or surgical intervention to prevent life-threatening illness or injury or permanent impairment to a body structure or a body function.”⁷³

In collaboration with the prevention measures mentioned above, they have also recommended a quality management system; a strategy for regulatory compliance, including compliance with conformity assessment procedures, identification of safety and performance requirements, management responsibility; risk management, resource management, including suppliers and sub-contractors; communication, monitoring and reporting processes and strategies, among others. The MDR even describes personal, professional and educational characteristics that the person responsible for the regulatory compliance should have, including a recognized university degree and at least one year of experience in regulatory affairs.⁷⁴

4.1.2. Software Coverage

Hardware devices are covered under the MDR and Software too. Software has the potential to serve as a “medical device”: “It is necessary to clarify that software in its own right, when specifically intended by the manufacturer to be used for one or more of the

⁷⁰ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR), OJ 2017 L 117, Article 2(64).

⁷¹ Ibid. Article 2(59).

⁷² Ibid. Article 2(58)(b) and Annex VIII, Chapter III, point 6.3, rule 11.

⁷³ Ibid. Article 2(58)(b).

⁷⁴ Ibid. Article 5(1)(b).

medical purposes set out in the definition of a medical device, qualifies as a medical device, while software for general purposes, even when used in a healthcare setting, or software intended for life-style and well-being purposes is not a medical device. The qualification of software, either as a device or an accessory, is independent of the software's location or the type of interconnection between the software and a device.”⁷⁵

These devices with electronic programmable systems (software), need to ensure that their design can deliver repeatable and reliable results, with the right amount of performance as it was originally intended. At the same time, they should include a set of minimum requirements, among them, hardware, IT network, IT security measures, risk management, information verification, validation and other procedures that will guarantee its protection against unauthorized access, etc.⁷⁶ Annex VIII, point 6.3. Rule 11 adds: “Software intended to provide information which is used to take decisions with diagnosis or therapeutic purposes is classified as class IIa, except if such decisions have an impact that may cause: death or an irreversible deterioration of a person's state of health, in which case it is in class III; or a serious deterioration of a person's state of health or a surgical intervention, in which case it is classified as class IIb.”⁷⁷

Although the MDR makes a good job describing the classifications, it is also conscious about the potential confusions, disagreements and debates it will bring, therefore, it delegates on the notified bodies and Member States (MS), the “case-by-case” dispute resolution. The MDR also considers the possibility for the Commission to consult expert panels, the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG), the European Medicines Agency (EMA), the European Chemicals Agency and the European Food Safety Authority, as necessary.⁷⁸

⁷⁵ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR), OJ 2017 L 117, Recital 19.

⁷⁶ Ibid. Annex I, Chapter II, point 17.4.

⁷⁷ Ibid. Annex VIII, point 6.3, Rule 11.

⁷⁸ Ibid. Recital 8 and Article 4(2).

4.1.3. Are Neurotechnologies covered by the MDR?

In general terms, they are covered. This is evidenced by the following three statements.

Firstly, the MDR has included them in Annex XVI, as part of the devices which even without an intended medical purpose, are still in scope. It has been literally stated as: “Equipment intended for brain stimulation that apply electrical currents or magnetic or electromagnetic fields that penetrate the cranium to modify neuronal activity in the brain.”⁷⁹

Secondarily, specific MDR cases like:

- a) one exception where a class I device must involve a Notified Body, is the capability for the device to measure, stated also on the MDR Article 52, Conformity assessment procedures, “Manufacturers of class I devices, [...] the involvement of the notified body in those procedures shall be limited: [...] in the case of devices with a measuring function, to the aspects relating to the conformity of the devices with the metrological requirements.”⁸⁰
- b) The “Active Devices” definition, is being considered as “[...] intended for diagnosis and monitoring’ means any active device used, whether alone or in combination with other devices, to supply information for detecting, diagnosing, monitoring or treating physiological conditions, states of health, illnesses or congenital deformities.”⁸¹ The Rule 10 in the same Annex, even states: “Active devices intended for diagnosis and monitoring are classified as class IIa.”⁸² Under the MDR “Definitions”, Software was included as an *active device*, meaning “any device, the operation of which depends on a source of energy other than that generated by the human body for that purpose, [...] Software shall also be deemed to be an active device.”⁸³

⁷⁹ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR), OJ 2017 L 117, Annex XVI, point 6.

⁸⁰ Ibid. Article 52, point 7(b).

⁸¹ Ibid. Annex VIII, Chapter I, point 2.5.

⁸² Ibid. Annex VIII, Chapter III, point 6.2, rule 10.

⁸³ Ibid. Article 2(4).

- c) The MDR also classifies Software in different categories, but the Software used in some NTs, should be class IIa, accordingly to the following statement: “Software intended to monitor physiological processes is classified as class IIa, except if it is intended for monitoring of vital physiological parameters, where the nature of variations of those parameters is such that it could result in immediate danger to the patient, in which case it is classified as class IIb. All other software is classified as class I.”⁸⁴

If we contemplate that NTs are currently measuring brain sensitive data, its waves, impulses, patterns, regardless of the methodology to obtain them, subsequently the notified body should be informed (accordingly to Article 52 - Conformity assessment procedures and Annex VII), and should help re-classifying the device into its appropriate risk level, if not clear already. And if there is still a doubt or a dispute between the manufacturer and the notified body, then shall be referred for a decision to the competent authority of the Member State.⁸⁵

Even if in Figure 11, non-medical neurotechnologies seem to be not regulated under the MDR, it is important to denote that based on the statements above they seem to be subtly included, although not as explicit as in the Implementing Regulations in green.

That is why, the third reason is the creation of the Implementing Regulations (EU) 2022/2346⁸⁶ and (EU) 2022/2347⁸⁷ which are complementary to the MDR regulation. They play a really important role, as they seem to have cleared the previously existing uncertainty around NTs, Bublitz et al. (2024) considered it as “the apparently first binding regulation of non-medical neurotechnologies in the world and may thus serve as a model or a cautionary tale for other jurisdictions.”⁸⁸ This can also be interpreted as an opportunity to keep generating the “*Brussels Effect*”⁸⁹, which over the years, the EU has

⁸⁴ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR), OJ 2017 L 117, Annex VIII, Chapter III, point 6.3, Rule11.

⁸⁵ Ibid. Chapter V, Article 51(2).

⁸⁶ Regulation (EU) 2022/2346, OJ 2022 L 311.

⁸⁷ Regulation (EU) 2022/2347, OJ 2022 L 311.

⁸⁸ Bublitz et al., 2024, p.2.

⁸⁹ Bradford, 2020.

position itself as a major influence and as a *de facto* global standard for the regulatory field.

Diagram I. Overview of neurotechnological device regulation under the EU Medical Device Regulation.

Figure 11 - Overview of the neurotechnological device regulations under the EU MDR⁹⁰

In the (EU) 2022/2347, the Commission has clearly classified NTs the following way: “According to available scientific evidence on equipment intended for brain stimulation that apply electrical currents or magnetic or electromagnetic fields that penetrate the cranium to modify neuronal activity in the brain as referred to in Section 6 of Annex XVI to Regulation (EU) 2017/745, such as those for transcranial magnetic stimulation or transcranial electric stimulation, the use of such products may cause side effects, for example, atypical brain development, abnormal patterns of brain activity, increase metabolic consumption, fatigue, anxiety, irritability, headaches, muscle twitches, tics, seizures, vertigo and skin irritation at the electrode site. While such equipment is not surgically invasive, the electrical currents or magnetic or electromagnetic fields do penetrate the cranium to modify neuronal activity in the brain. Such modifications can

⁹⁰ Bublitz et al., 2024, p.8. (Color lines have been included /modified).

have long-lasting effects, and any unintended effects may be difficult to reverse. Such products should therefore be classified as Class III.”⁹¹

The (EU) 2022/2347 has also stated: “As a result of reclassification under this Regulation, in accordance with Article 52 of Regulation (EU) 2017/745, a notified body is to be involved in the conformity assessment of the products concerned, to assess and confirm that, among the relevant general safety and performance requirements, the product achieves the intended performance and that the risks posed by the product have been eliminated or reduced as far as possible.”⁹²

The (EU) 2022/2346 has also outlined highly relevant topics for non-medical intended neurotechnology devices. To name some, it mentions the requirement for manufacturers to look at the following recommendations:

- a) “Evidence of qualification and competences of personnel, such as education, training, skills and experience, shall be documented.”⁹³ Also considering if the consumers/users are healthcare professionals or not.
- b) “The results of the risk management activities, including the reference to the device, the reference to the persons who carried out the activities and the dates of execution of such activities, shall be recorded. For every identified hazard, the records shall provide traceability to the results of risk analysis, risk evaluation, risk control and evaluation of residual risks.”⁹⁴ Also references on *how* and *who* in the company should perform the activities.⁹⁵
- c) “Throughout the entire lifecycle of a device, the manufacturer shall establish a system to ensure a continuous systematic update of the risk management process in relation to that device.”⁹⁶ Addressing the *when* and *for how long* aspects of the product.

⁹¹ Regulation (EU) 2022/2347, OJ 2022 L 311, Recital 7.

⁹² Regulation (EU) 2022/2347, OJ 2022 L 311, Recital 8.

⁹³ Regulation (EU) 2022/2346, OJ 2022 L 311, Annex I, point 2.3.

⁹⁴ Ibid. Annex I, point 2.4.

⁹⁵ Ibid. Annex I.

⁹⁶ Ibid. Annex I, point 2.6.

- d) “Manufacturers shall consider clinical data as one of the sources of information for the risk analysis and for the estimation of the severity and the probability of occurrence of harms.”⁹⁷

This modifies entirely how non-medical intended devices (in scope) will be evaluated, manufactured, marketed and put into the EU market, incorporating clinical data and investigations into the game. The clinical investigations must be based in post-market surveillance and post-market clinical follow-ups, and will be utilized to confirm the conformity assessments, and safety/performance requirements.⁹⁸

Under the (EU) 2022/2346 Annex VII, it has also been stated that the manufacturers are responsible of putting important labels into their products, with clearer information, specially about recommendations, potential risks and further observations. Some of the listed risks are: “[...] (a) the incorrect placement of electrodes and coils may result in failed performance, enhanced electrical currents in tissue or unintended neural responses; (b) brain stimulation may have very different neural responses and thus unintended effects on different groups of persons. Some groups may be particularly vulnerable: persons who are less than 18 years old, young adults, pregnant women, psychiatric patients, persons with psychological disorders or medical conditions affecting the central nervous system, alcohol addicts, users of addictive substances and other substances that modify a person’s natural perception; [...] (d) excessive, frequent and cumulative long-term use may result in unforeseen neural effects which in some cases might result in structural changes in the brain.”⁹⁹

“The Commission assumes that these devices may cause ‘atypical brain development, abnormal patterns of brain activity, increase metabolic consumption, fatigue, anxiety, irritability, headaches’ and that ‘brain modifications can have long-lasting and hard to reverse effects.’”¹⁰⁰

Additionally, manufacturers are also responsible for applying new safety measures, for example: “a) avoidance of unauthorised access to the device (for example

⁹⁷ Regulation (EU) 2022/2346, OJ 2022 L 311, Annex I, point 4.4.

⁹⁸ Ibid.

⁹⁹ Ibid. Annex VII, point 3.2.

¹⁰⁰ Bublitz et al., 2024, p.11.

by means of key switch or code) and unintended use of the device (for example by means of dual control of energy emission); [...] emergency stop function [...]”¹⁰¹ automatic deactivations in case of different circumstances like overexposure, videos with instructions, appropriate trainings on how to safely use the device, correct functioning measures and even automatic alarms based on energy levels, and when durations of use are above the maximum recommendable ranges.

4.1.4. Potential Open Considerations

Even if the implementing regulations have helped with these non-medical neurotechnologies, there are still potential conflicting topics, that could lead to possible issues and will be covered below.

If the devices with or without a medical purpose, can modify or not the neuronal activity, this seems like a topic that will require exhausting clinical trials, documentation, metrics, research time and proof that a particular device does not have the capability to modify neuronal activity. This could be the cause of long disputes, while the results get to be discovered, leaving the risk still open for its users, especially for existing products prior to these implementing regulations; or even products bought out of the EU. Same situation above with devices that claim to stimulate the brain, how can they determine that these devices are truly stimulating it favorably? How can they investigate and gather enough proof (and risks) in a timely manner?

In the MDR, “Active Devices” are considering monitoring “physiological” conditions. This term is not specified under the MDR definitions, neither in the additional regulations. According to the online Cambridge Dictionary, physiological is: “relating to the way in which the bodies of living things work”¹⁰², if we strictly use this concept, then the questions would be: are our thoughts and emotions part of our bodies, part of our physiological conditions? Or is mainly a result of our psychological processes and therefore, a result of our minds only? This is the “Dualism” question between mind and body, present for centuries in the philosophic and psychology fields.¹⁰³ Bublitz et al.

¹⁰¹ Regulation (EU) 2022/2346, OJ 2022 L 311, Annex VII, point 4.2.

¹⁰² Cambridge University Press & Assessment, 2025.

¹⁰³ Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, 2020.

(2024), also brought it to the table, when they stated the MDR classifying rules are “solely based on the vulnerability of the human body (Recital 58 MDR).”¹⁰⁴ then, where are we leaving the potential risks related to the human mind, emotions and opinions? When will we start to consider them? Annex VII of the (EU) 2022/2346 mentions psychological risks and long-term effects of brain functioning.¹⁰⁵ Nevertheless emotions can be measured, thoughts could be decoded, opinions could get influenced and manipulated even more as they currently are, which could represent the start of societal, fundamental rights and democracy related changes and consequences.

Vulnerable groups: The (EU) 2022/2346 and the (EU) 2022/2347 bring great measures, cover risk management activities and recommendations, it includes clearer instructions and information to the users and concerned parents, but can it be assured they are truly read and that are aware of its consequences? Requirements as alarms and automatic deactivations might eventually help reducing the risks, but is that sufficient? Annex VII also mentions: “[...] unless there is specific evidence for safe use, the following categories of consumers shall be excluded”¹⁰⁶ But how can it be assured that those vulnerable groups avoid getting further jeopardized? How can we make sure providers, distributors and vulnerable groups are following the recommendations proactively? Without falling into overregulating them, it is pertinent to mention that among these vulnerable groups, are our future generations, what do we truly want for them? Is compensation for damages caused by a defective device enough?

Virtual Reality (VR) devices, Artificial Intelligence (AI) glasses with neuronal measurement sensors or other wearable devices with similar sensor capabilities, for example, meditation-performance diadems¹⁰⁷ or even clothing with mood sensors like “Google’s Jacquard Project”¹⁰⁸ or “NextMind”¹⁰⁹, that might monitor, measure, track and bidirectionally communicate with the brain through impulses, or potentially, modify and

¹⁰⁴ Bublitz et al., 2024, p.14.

¹⁰⁵ Regulation (EU) 2022/2346, OJ 2022 L 311, Annex VII, point 3.3(a)(e).

¹⁰⁶ Ibid. Annex VII point 4.1.

¹⁰⁷ Cody Rall MD with Techforpsych, 2023.

¹⁰⁸ R., 2024. *(Author’s Full Last Name not found).

¹⁰⁹ Next Mind, 2022.

decode thoughts and memories.¹¹⁰ Some of these capabilities seem to still be excluded and uncovered under the current scope of the MDR and related regulations.

A similar situation happens with other type of wearables (without neuro sensors) (which will not be covered in detail here), these can “monitor cardiac performance, respiration, activity of the central nervous system”¹¹¹, like smart watches, wristbands, among others; as when their intended purpose is medical, they could classify as Class IIa,¹¹² but when they are not considered medical devices, it could end in the indirect promotion and further expansion of the private and sensitive data repositories, owned by the biggest tech providers worldwide.

Considerable work remains undecided, regarding not only neurotechnologies, but all groundbreaking innovations with human monitoring capabilities. It is clear that complying with all requirements above could imply in higher costs for the companies, harder and longer clinical trials and might also have an impact in the EU competitiveness. An increase on transparency from the marketing campaigns, the proper guidance of the manufacturers regarding these regulations, the appropriate education and awareness of the citizens, especially professionals and students, promoting critical thinking exercises and moral values; a strong market surveillance and the further control of the products entering the Union’s market are a starting point to make a better future for next generations.

¹¹⁰ Council of the European Union, Research Paper, From vision to reality: Promises and risks of Brain-Computer Interfaces, 2024.

¹¹¹ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR), OJ 2017 L 117, Annex VIII, Chapter III, point 6.2, rule 10.

¹¹² Ibid.

4.2. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

4.2.1. *The Regulation and Our Rights*

Moving forward with the REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 or more broadly known as the GDPR, published in April 2016 and coming into effect in May 2018. According to the regulation, its purpose is to contribute on the areas of freedom, security, justice, the well-being of natural persons and the protection of the fundamental rights and freedoms,¹¹³ where “[...] the protection of personal data, freedom of thought, conscience and religion, freedom of expression and information, freedom to conduct a business, the right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial, and cultural, religious and linguistic diversity.”¹¹⁴ are considered as key truths. But how exactly does the GDPR can help on freedom of thought and conscience? Interestingly, it was only mentioned once in the entire regulation, no further explanations, what would have supported the neurotechnologies considerations if it would have been further explained.

Recital 7, mentions that “Natural persons should have control of their own personal data [...]”¹¹⁵ Later in the regulation it explains the data rights included, as for example, the right to be informed about how their data is being processed, the right to access the data a company holds of them,¹¹⁶ the right to rectify inaccurate information,¹¹⁷ the erasure of personal data or right to be forgotten,¹¹⁸ the right to data portability,¹¹⁹ the right to object,¹²⁰ along with the rights of restricting data processing and the possibility to choose if the subject wants or not to be included into automated decision-making tools, including *profiling*.¹²¹

Many authors consider these rights as “insufficient” and claim the need for new fundamental brain rights, “Neurorights”, new regulations and new measures. Like for

¹¹³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), OJ 2016 L 119, Recital 2.

¹¹⁴ Ibid. Recital 4.

¹¹⁵ Ibid. Recital 7.

¹¹⁶ Ibid. Article 15.

¹¹⁷ Ibid. Article 16.

¹¹⁸ Ibid. Article 17.

¹¹⁹ Ibid. Article 20.

¹²⁰ Ibid. Article 21.

¹²¹ Ibid. Article 22.

example, Yuste et al., (2017),¹²² presented five new potential rights, a) the right to mental privacy against unauthorized access, b) the right to personal identity, preventing modifications to a person's sense of self, c) the right to free will, to make sure people could continue making their own decisions without manipulation, d) the right to fair access, to avoid inequality of use and access to the NTs, and e) the protection from algorithmic biases, to make sure neurodata is not used to discriminate against individuals.

GDPR comprehends “Any processing of personal data in the context of the activities of an establishment of a controller or a processor in the Union [...] regardless of whether the processing itself takes place within the Union.”¹²³ It also includes processing activities related to “goods or services irrespective of whether connected to a payment.”¹²⁴ Moreover, “The processing of personal data [...] should also be subject to this Regulation [...] related to the monitoring of the behaviour of such data subjects in so far as their behaviour takes place within the Union.”¹²⁵ For example tracking people via internet or profiling methods, like documenting, analyzing and/or predicting preferences, behaviors and attitudes of natural persons. These criteria would apply to neurotechnologies, as most of them have the capability to track, monitor and create large profiling sets of behaviors, attitudes, emotions and mental states, besides mental structures, deficiencies, among others. A reason why Istace et al. (2024), also recognized its current significance and expansion, “As the use of NTs becomes increasingly widespread, so does the availability of data generated by them. [...] Partly because of this, the neuroscience has transitioned from a predominantly closed science model (marked by limited data sharing) to a predominantly open science model, resulting in a dramatic increase in publicly available neurodata.”¹²⁶

4.2.2. Vulnerable Populations

Extracted from Recital 71 and then later expanded in Article 22, “[...] Such processing includes ‘profiling’ that consists of any form of automated processing of personal data

¹²² Yuste et al., 2017, pp. 159-163.

¹²³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), OJ 2016 L 119, Recital 22 and Article 3(1).

¹²⁴ Ibid. Recital 23 and Article 3(2)(a).

¹²⁵ Ibid. Recital 24 and Article 3(2)(b).

¹²⁶ Istace et al., 2024, p.9.

evaluating the personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict aspects concerning the data subject's performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences or interests, reliability or behaviour, location or movements, where it produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her. [...] Such measure should not concern a child. [...] Automated decision-making and profiling based on special categories of personal data should be allowed only under specific conditions.”¹²⁷ Additionally, Recital 58 mentions “Given that children merit specific protection, any information and communication, where processing is addressed to a child, should be in such a clear and plain language that the child can easily understand.”¹²⁸

Some of the DTC NTs are exclusively directed to children, promising learning or cognition enhancement, concentration, virtual reality, AI capabilities, gaming, and so on. Where are the neurodata guardrails here? Predictions based on health neurodata, behavioral data, emotions and preferences, with the help of gaming or NT user profiles around the world, are and might continue to be captured. Would these historical generated trends be later used to influence their behavioral patterns (e.g. marketing or politically)? Is consent enough? How is it even verified that children are older than 16 years (or 13 years, if the MS state designated this way)?¹²⁹ Most of these DTC NT technologies are advertised in English, and even if available in other languages, children might, conscious or unconsciously, ignore all Data Protection statements and click straight to the game or final NT use.

Consent should be freely given and informed, in which “Silence, pre-ticked boxes or inactivity should not therefore constitute consent. Consent should cover all processing activities carried out for the same purpose or purposes. When the processing has multiple purposes, consent should be given for all of them. If the data subject's consent is to be given following a request by electronic means, the request must be clear, concise and not unnecessarily disruptive to the use of the service for which it is provided.”¹³⁰ But, how is NT consent informed, collected and saved? Is it written or verbal? Is it truly clear? Are

¹²⁷ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), OJ 2016 L 119, Recital 71 and Article 22.

¹²⁸ Ibid. Recital 58.

¹²⁹ Ibid. Article 8(1).

¹³⁰ Ibid. Recital 32 and Article 7.

they openly revealing how is their data used? Are they explaining clearly if there are any consequences? If someone wants to remove their consent, is there a process? Which? Can they exercise their GDPR rights (remove, delete data)? If it is embedded in an AI Model, is it truly removable? As Ienca et al. (2022) mentioned “[...] research has shown that that the collection and processing of mental data from consumer neurotechnology and digital phenotyping applications often occurs under weak consent regimes.”¹³¹

Companies like Emotiv, have mentioned they are securing all data in their private infrastructure, and they have stated in their website they are compliant with the GDPR.¹³² This is important to mention as most of these NT companies haven’t included it in their websites or it is still too vague, and as most of them are not subject to an additional payment subscription or online service, may cause a lower interest of users to inform themselves on its data guidelines.

Having said that, users might not even recognize that their data is being processed, or some might not have taken it seriously, as they follow their “logic” or the human social/psychological behaviors of “peer group pressure”, discovered by Salomon Asch in 1951,¹³³ or the “herd mentality”, a social behavior initially confirmed by Wilfred Trotter¹³⁴ in 1916, in which people follow instinctual drives that guide societies; or due to the known marketing “Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) Strategy”¹³⁵, where anxiety arises from the belief that others are having rewarding experiences from which one is absent or could miss it if he/she doesn’t do it too. In these three human behaviors, people tend and try to be “accepted”, to be part of a group, without truly caring much about their data. Translated into the NT space, it represents a social pressure to buy the device, to ignore the data privacy statements, or to rush into an uninformed consent, especially in younger groups, or when associated to a limited availability of the products, exclusive games or marketing promotions and benefits, that could amplify the user’s self-esteem, image, self-worth, in both virtual and physical worlds.

¹³¹ Ienca et al., 2022, p.12.

¹³² Emotiv, 2025.

¹³³ Asch, 1951.

¹³⁴ Trotter, 1916.

¹³⁵ McGinnis, 2004.

A fourth reason could be influenced by the “reciprocity principle” (R. Cialdini, 1984)¹³⁶ in which people, patients or NT testers could allow to provide their consent to their data without limits or further details, as a reciprocity appreciation gesture, in exchange for the games, technologies, benefits or medical improvements they think they are receiving instead. Due to these human characteristics, it was significantly easy to influence people’s decisions, in the past, and with NTs, it will be unmistakable facilitated even bordering the legal frontiers and ethical fundamentals.

Wei et al. (2025) complemented my concern with the following statement, “[...] NPI collected by BCIs is dynamic and subject to continuous updates overtime. The informed consent rules only offer necessary information at specific points, overlooking the continuous evolution of NPI. Once initial consent is given, BCI providers may discover NPI’s novel uses and alter their information processing methods, creating unforeseen privacy risks.”¹³⁷

DTC NTs, as part of a device manufacture industrial process, are subject to a Lot Number, a Serial Number, a Product Number, a License number, an IP address (if connected to the internet), all being unique identifiers¹³⁸ that could identify the person using it, including children. Even when anonymized and secured, this data collection, could form extensive profiling sets, metrics, and dashboards (performance, preferences, interests, health, location, behavior, movements, etc.) that could be subject of potential hacking breaches. We depend on the provider guidelines, values, processes and readiness to secure it, and equality on governments to use it wisely and accordingly to the fundamental rights.

In criminal investigations, NTs are also being considered, in China, as Wei et al. (2025) mentioned: “‘Brain fingerprinting’ techniques are already utilized to identify lies in suspects,”¹³⁹ or in the USA, where Farahany, in her “Incriminating Thoughts”¹⁴⁰ article, explains a set of potential scenarios, as “self-incrimination” and how NTs’ fate could potentially develop. In the EU, can non-medical or medical neurodata, during criminal

¹³⁶ Cialdini, 1984, Chapter 2, p.23.

¹³⁷ Wei et al., 2025, p.12.

¹³⁸ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), OJ 2016 L 119, Recital 30.

¹³⁹ Wei et al., 2025, p.13.

¹⁴⁰ Farahany, Incriminating Thoughts, 2012.

inquiries, be used? Will they be used? The GDPR grants the “[...] possibility for Member States under specific conditions to restrict by law certain obligations and rights when such a restriction constitutes a necessary and proportionate measure in a democratic society to safeguard specific important interests including public security and the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security.”¹⁴¹ Will there be specific NT guidelines and guardrails? The Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council, known as Law Enforcement Directive (will not be covered here), doesn’t seem to contain anything NT-related yet either.

4.2.3. Mental Data, Mental Health and Public Interest

GDPR separates personal data, from special categories of personal data. Personal data being a person's name, email address, IP address, location data, or even a cookie ID,¹⁴² and special categories like sensitive data, which have the capability of revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, genetic data, biometric data for unique identification, health data and data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation, which require a more strict set of processing conditions.¹⁴³ The GDPR concepts of genetic data and biometric data do not consider, nor define “mental data” specifically. And “data concerning health” includes “[...] personal data related to the physical or mental health of a natural person, including the provision of health care services, which reveal information about his or her health status;”¹⁴⁴ but where do we leave non-medical mental data? “[...] Neurodata thus provides a unique window into an individual that can unveil sensitive characteristics such as future health, sexual orientation, intentions and decision making. It is considered by many to be the “ultimate resort of informational privacy”, because it both “includes unexecuted behaviour, inner speech or other non-externalized action” and can be collected without the meaningful control of the data subject.”¹⁴⁵

¹⁴¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), OJ 2016 L 119, Recital 19 and Article 23(1).

¹⁴² Ibid. Article 4(1) and Article 4(15).

¹⁴³ Ibid. Article 9.

¹⁴⁴ Ibid. Article 4(15).

¹⁴⁵ Istace et al., 2024, p.9.

Recital 35, states “Personal data concerning health should include all data pertaining to the health status of a data subject which reveal information relating to the past, current or future physical or mental health status of the data subject. [...] a number, symbol or particular assigned to a natural person to uniquely identify the natural person for health purposes; information derived from the testing or examination of a body part or bodily substance, including from genetic data and biological samples; and any information on, for example, a disease, disability, disease risk, medical history, clinical treatment or the physiological or biomedical state of the data subject independent of its source [...].”¹⁴⁶ If the neurodata is processed under a non-medical purpose and/or tagged under an inoffensive category, like gaming, wellness and focus, if “[...] consumer BCIs are unlikely to be considered sensitive data, unless those emotions can either be used even to infer the mental health status of the individual (eg digital biomarkers of neuropsychiatric disorder) or to reveal information about religious beliefs, political opinions, and sex life or sexual orientation.”¹⁴⁷ How can the EU and Member States enforce that this sensitive data gets to be covered properly under this regulation, even if anonymized?

As Ienca (2022) explained, the GDPR has a significant gap in its protection of *mental data*, as its list of "sensitive data" in Article 9(1) is too narrow.¹⁴⁸ It includes categories like health, sexuality and political opinions, but does not explicitly cover all mental states. For example, emotions, moods, or desires would not be subject to the protections of Article 9, unless a direct or even indirect link could be proven to one of the listed sensitive categories.¹⁴⁹ This lack of comprehensive coverage leaves a wide range of mental data vulnerable to processing without the same high level of consent and justification that is required for traditional sensitive data.

According to the GDPR preamble, Recitals 53 and 54, public health data could be gathered by public management institutions, even without the data subject’s consent, when it is related to public interest in public health, health security or monitoring and it declares, Member States should introduce further limitations regarding genetic data,

¹⁴⁶ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), OJ 2016 L 119, Recital 35.

¹⁴⁷ Ienca et al, 2022, p.10.

¹⁴⁸ Ibid. p.14.

¹⁴⁹ Ibid. p.11.

biometric data or health data. The GDPR also indicates, as guidance for “public health”, the Regulation (EC) No 1338/2008, which in its’ Annex 1, states “The harmonised and common data set to be provided shall cover the following list of subjects: - health status, including health perceptions, physical and mental functioning, limitations and disability [...]”¹⁵⁰ important to mention it also considers children information, when necessary. GDPR’s Article 89 further specifies it should only be used for the written specific purposes (which will not be further expanded here).

If we remember and combine the current three worldwide risks: a) the WHO, reported mental health (depression and anxiety), as one of the main public health concerns;¹⁵¹ b) the WEF is actively promoting neurodata and AI to be used in the best interest of patients, including workplace use cases;¹⁵² c) the WEF predictions on the “Future of Jobs”,¹⁵³ with the risk of a vast unemployment wave (projections estimate 39% key skills to change by 2030),¹⁵⁴ due to the technology evolution and the continual increase of AI in all industries. This intricate chain of occurrences could result in a potential intensification of brain related disorders, leading individuals into potential suicidal thoughts and actions.

Psychologically, it has been proved by multiple researchers, from Viktor Frankl¹⁵⁵ to Victor Strecher,¹⁵⁶ that human beings need a life purpose; large populations depending only on a potential universal salary (UBI – Universal Basic Income) will not be homogeneously effective, nor achievable in the world, nor even within Europe. Other types of employment might not be feasible in a short-term, as massive upskilling initiatives would be urgently required. If forecasts are right and it gets to advance before 2030, there will not be enough time for societies to prepare.

Depending on how existing worldwide topics, in politics, technologies, economics, demographics, health crises develop, there might be a probability that neurodata could be considered as a source of “public data”, and its “public interest” could

¹⁵⁰ Regulation (EC) No 1338/2008, OJ 2008 L 354, Annex 1(d).

¹⁵¹ World Health Organization, 2022.

¹⁵² World Economic Forum, 4 imperatives for improving mental health care in 2025, 2025.

¹⁵³ World Economic Forum, The Future of Jobs Report 2025, 2025.

¹⁵⁴ World Economic Forum, Jobs and the Future of Work Future of Jobs Report 2025, 2025.

¹⁵⁵ Frankl, 2006.

¹⁵⁶ Strecher, 2016.

borderline the limits of the Fundamental Human Rights. As of today, there are no legal considerations to prevent some types of neurodata from turning into “health data of public interest”; Regulation (EC) No 1338/2008,¹⁵⁷ Annex 1, reinforces the track of mental functioning, limitations and disabilities for statistical purposes. Without the aim to make it sound disastrous nor encouraging overregulation, this situation has the capability of transmuting into a legal risk, a risk to democracy, liberty, individualism, freedom of thought, human integrity, human autonomy, diversity, among many rights, especially due to the hypothetical threat of evolving into hyper-surveillance and even, into a well-intended persecution.

In Recital 56, the GDPR covers electoral data, granting political opinions to be processed and compiled, using “public interest” as a motive too. If we consider the frightening decrease in the democracy indexes around the world (Figure 12), with negative numbers in all continents, especially in North America (one of the high influencing world powers); we might be at the door of the next democracy crisis, or we might be in a (so far, small) “reverse democracy wave”,¹⁵⁸ with the current battles for technology related minerals, the aggressive computational and technology power race and the recent increase of geopolitical tensions and realignment of forces.

Democracy index Economist Intelligence Unit					
Country or region ↓	↑↓ 2006	↑↓ 2024	2006-2024	↑↓ Absolute Change	↑↓ Relative Change
Africa	4.11	3.92		-0.19	-5%
Asia	4.38	4.06		-0.32	-7%
Europe	7.75	7.41		-0.34	-4%
North America	6.57	5.64		-0.92	-14%
Oceania	7.58	7.46		-0.12	-2%
South America	6.52	6.01		-0.51	-8%

Figure 12 - Democracy index: Economist Intelligence Unit 2024 ¹⁵⁹

¹⁵⁷ Regulation (EC) No 1338/2008, OJ 2008 L 354, Annex I(d).

¹⁵⁸ Huntington, 1991.

¹⁵⁹ Our World in Data, 2025. (Color lines have been included /modified).

And while this paper focuses on the legal context, bringing the quick reference of Samuel P. Huntington's, "The Third Wave: Democratization in the Late Twentieth Century"¹⁶⁰, written in 1991, will serve to support my previous statement. He recognized three major democracy waves in history, and he explained how the democratization is a cyclical process, followed by reverse waves. Unfortunately, these reverse waves cause effects similar as snowballs and have the potential to influence many other countries, especially when major influencing countries serve as reverse role models. Aspects, we, as citizens and legal professionals, have the responsibility to be conscious about and prevent further consequences. Below a graphical visualization of the democratic waves' trend (Figure 13).

Figure 13 - Number of countries experiencing autocratization and democratization since 1900¹⁶¹

These scenarios serve as underlying causes for the critical need to safeguard neurodata, with specific legal guidelines, appropriate democratic and human-right related protections and potential new classifications of how neurodata types could be fragmented, in a way that could leave specific cluster(s) of neurodata, out of the potential scope and inclusion of public data, research and even statistics. Like for example, a category that comprehends "cognitive-affective"¹⁶² neurodata, specifically understood as thoughts,

¹⁶⁰ Huntington, 1991.

¹⁶¹ Boese et al., 2021. (Color lines have been included /modified).

¹⁶² UNESCO, First Draft Of A Recommendation On The Ethics Of Neurotechnology, 2024, p.7.

memories, beliefs, opinions, perceptions, attitudes, emotions, moods, desires and mental states.

4.2.4. Moving Forward

On Recital 26, “[...] This Regulation does not therefore concern the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes”¹⁶³ leaving the gap open for NT, in research or Beta Testing status, to process personal and sensitive data. Later, Recital 157 delegates the designation of appropriate conditions and safeguards to the Member States. Will consent, encryption, network and data security risk, data minimization and anonymization be enough for NTs? How easy will be unauthorized reversal of pseudonymization and cyber threats in NTs, in the post-quantum era? Which has been predicted to burst prior to 2030, specially with the most recent breakthrough from companies like Amazon, Google, IBM, and Microsoft.¹⁶⁴ Will neurodata be included in Data Spaces? Which restrictions will they have? Are monetary, legal implications,¹⁶⁵ awareness-raising activities (specially for parents and data protection officers),¹⁶⁶ the transparency principle, legitimate purposes, storage period limitations, compliance and mitigation plans, reporting breaches (in less than 72 hours to the authorities),¹⁶⁷ certifications,¹⁶⁸ supervisory authorities¹⁶⁹ and data impact assessments¹⁷⁰ enough for NTs? How critical can the neurodata be? If manipulation and discrimination in mass scale could be a risk, if democracy could be at risk, shouldn’t we have a special category of fines and penalties for each category of neurodata (under the risk and proportionally principle)? Do we need a new governmental NT supervisory authority?

As Wei et al. (2025) mentioned, it is critically important that there are soft and hard laws supporting the human rights, at a worldwide level. They proposed “[...] the establishment of a concentric-circle hard–soft law continuum to support a hybrid

¹⁶³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), OJ 2016 L 119, Recital 26.

¹⁶⁴ Soller, 2025.

¹⁶⁵ Ibid. Articles 82-84.

¹⁶⁶ Ibid. Article 37-39.

¹⁶⁷ Ibid. Article 33.

¹⁶⁸ Ibid. Article 42.

¹⁶⁹ Ibid. Article 51 and Article 59.

¹⁷⁰ Ibid. Article 35.

governance model for NPI, rooted in fundamental human rights principles.”¹⁷¹ See Figure 14.

Neural personal information and its legal protection • 15

Figure 14 - The Concentric - Circle Hard-Soft Law Continuum for NPI Protection ¹⁷²

This multi-layered approach to regulate BCIs and their Neural Personal Information (NPI) could address the limitations of traditional hard law. By using soft law¹⁷³ as industry standards and ethics committees, could allow flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and adaptability to rapidly evolving technologies. NPI could be classified into a hierarchical system (highly identifiable, sensitive and general)¹⁷⁴ each level having different rules for consent and storage. They also recommended risk warning mechanisms, policies, rules of conduct, industry standards, reviews, certification systems and for governments to incentivize companies to adopt these self-regulatory measures, for instance by offering tax breaks to encourage the establishment of ethics committees and adherence to these standards.¹⁷⁵ Ienca et al. (2022) also suggested “Mental Data Protection Impact Assessment’(MDPIA)”¹⁷⁶ which could be of help, but are these recommendations still sufficient?

¹⁷¹ Wei et al., 2025, p.1.

¹⁷² Ibid. p.15.

¹⁷³ Ibid. p.15.

¹⁷⁴ Ibid. p.16.

¹⁷⁵ Ibid. p.18.

¹⁷⁶ Ienca et al., 2022, p.19.

With the increase of AI in all industries, we must contemplate that some data privacy responsibilities will rely on the Large Language Model (LLM) user and some of the GDPR rights might not even be feasible today. Novelli et al. (2024)¹⁷⁷ explained the complex data privacy challenges posed by LLMs under GDPR.

- a) The user-provided data, where a user's prompt might contain personal information about a third party. While the user is the initial controller, the LLM operator becomes the sole controller for any subsequent processing, like memorization or data leakage, making them responsible for compliance under the GDPR's Article 5(2).
- b) The "right to erasure"¹⁷⁸ and the potential for model inversion and data leakage, where personal data can be reconstructed from the model itself, raising the possibility of the LLM being considered personal data, which would give individuals the right to demand the deletion of the entire model. They also mentioned a potential solution presented by OpenAI, a web crawler with an opt-out feature, which could help with compliance for both copyright and GDPR's right to object to data processing.¹⁷⁹
- c) The hallucinations and the incapability of the LLM operators to correct it, there are several cases like the Noyb case¹⁸⁰, where they filed multiple complaints against OpenAI, and as of September 2025, no final decision has been made. The outcome is highly anticipated, as it could set a major precedent for how GDPR applies to generative AI and how AI operators will be held accountable for the data they process and the information they produce.

In essence, amplified AI neurodata is a topic our legal frameworks are not equipped to manage, and new ways and safeguards should be established.

¹⁷⁷ Novelli et al., 2024.

¹⁷⁸ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), OJ 2016 L 119, Article 17.

¹⁷⁹ Ibid. Article 21.

¹⁸⁰ Noyb, 2024.

4.3. Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA)

4.3.1. *The Regulation*

Diving into the Regulation (EU) 2024/1689¹⁸¹, it aims to establish a uniform legal framework for AI systems within the EU's internal market, promoting a human-centric and trustworthy approach. It's designed to foster innovation and free movement of AI-based goods and services while ensuring a high level of protection for health, safety and fundamental rights, including democracy and the rule of law. By preventing the fragmentation of the internal market from differing national rules, the regulation seeks to create legal certainty for AI developers and users. Additionally, it includes specific provisions for the protection of personal data (e.g., AI remote biometric identification/categorization restrictions).

The Regulation defines AI as “[...] a fast evolving family of technologies that contributes to a wide array of economic, environmental and societal benefits across the entire spectrum of industries and social activities. By improving prediction, optimising operations and resource allocation, and personalising digital solutions available for individuals and organisations, the use of AI can provide key competitive advantages to undertakings and support socially and environmentally beneficial outcomes, for example in healthcare, agriculture, food safety, education and training, media, sports, culture, infrastructure management, energy, transport and logistics, public services, security, justice, resource and energy efficiency, environmental monitoring, the conservation and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems and climate change mitigation and adaptation.”¹⁸²

It also grasps into the potential risks to public interests and fundamental rights, including physical and psychological to societal and economic damages. Its human-centric characteristic and its alignment to the Union's values and rights, addresses and highlights the need to protect them, along with democracy, the rule of law and the environment.¹⁸³ It also encompasses seven non-binding ethical principles, 1) human

¹⁸¹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AIA), OJ 2024 L 1689.

¹⁸² Ibid. Recital 4.

¹⁸³ Ibid. Recital 5-8, Article 1, Art. 7(3).

agency, dignity, autonomy and oversight; 2) technical robustness and safety; 3) privacy and data governance; 4) transparency, traceability and explainability; 5) diversity, non-discrimination, equality and fairness; 6) societal and environmental well-being and 7) accountability, including democracy.¹⁸⁴

This Regulation uses a risk-based approach tailored to the intensity and scope of the risks that AI systems can generate.¹⁸⁵ AI-enabled manipulative techniques, subliminal components and important adverse impacts on physical, psychological health or financial interests are prohibited.¹⁸⁶ The Regulation also refers to the possibility of using NTs for forbidden matters as “[...] for example, by machine-brain interfaces or virtual reality as they allow for a higher degree of control of what stimuli are presented to persons, insofar as they may materially distort their behaviour in a significantly harmful manner.”¹⁸⁷

Given the digital nature of the systems, this regulation applies to all AI systems, regardless of their location, their readiness/commercial status, or their market location, as the EU data could be at risk of being part of them. Among the exceptions found, stand a) public authorities of third countries and international organizations, when acting in areas of law enforcement and judicial cooperation with the respect to the protection of fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals;¹⁸⁸ (b) military, defense or national security purposes;¹⁸⁹ c) systems with scientific research and development purpose (prior to be placed on the market).¹⁹⁰

4.3.2. Biometrics and Emotional Recognition

Terminology-wise, it considers the same definition of “Biometrics” as the GDPR, “‘biometric data’ means personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, such as facial

¹⁸⁴ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AIA), OJ 2024 L 1689, Recital 27.

¹⁸⁵ Ibid. Recital 26.

¹⁸⁶ Ibid. Recital 29 and Article 5.

¹⁸⁷ Ibid. Recital 29.

¹⁸⁸ Ibid. Recital 22 and Article 2(4).

¹⁸⁹ Ibid. Recital 24 and Article 2(3).

¹⁹⁰ Ibid. Recital 25 and Article 2(8).

images or dactyloscopic data”¹⁹¹ excluding mental data and brain biometrics, but incorporating “[...] authentication, identification or categorisation of natural persons and for the recognition of emotions of natural persons.”¹⁹² As biometrics exclusive use should be associated only to the authentication purposes, it dismisses these human characteristics from the Regulation, regardless of their consent: “[...] human features such as the face, eye movement, body shape, voice, prosody, gait, posture, heart rate, blood pressure, odour [...] irrespective of whether the individual has given its consent or not.”¹⁹³

Biometrics, even if categorized, they should not be commercialized, nor used for real-time systems,¹⁹⁴ or they will be subject of both regulations (AI Act and GDPR). “Biometric categorisation systems [...] to deduce or infer an individuals’ political opinions, trade union membership, religious or philosophical beliefs, race, sex life or sexual orientation should be prohibited.”¹⁹⁵ Same as for AI Systems for social scoring,¹⁹⁶ expanding facial recognition databases through the untargeted scraping of facial images from the internet or CCTV footage,¹⁹⁷ detecting the emotional state of individuals in situations related to the workplace and education.¹⁹⁸ No biometric 24 hours real-time authentication use cases are allowed, if any, the market surveillance authority and the national data protection authority should be notified of each use. Exceptions will be reviewed.¹⁹⁹

Any other biometric or emotion recognition AI system that is not used for authentication, cybersecurity or any of the restricted exceptions will be considered “high-risk” or prohibited, if not medical-related.²⁰⁰ This is equality applicable for emotion recognition systems, with the “[...] purpose of identifying or inferring emotions or intentions of natural persons on the basis of their biometric data.”²⁰¹ Exclusions are “pain” and “fatigue” to prevent accidents in professional pilots or drivers.²⁰²

¹⁹¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), OJ 2016 L 119, Article 3(34).

¹⁹² Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AIA), OJ 2024 L 1689, Recital 14.

¹⁹³ Ibid. Recital 15.

¹⁹⁴ Ibid. Recitals 17, 32, 33, Article 5.

¹⁹⁵ Ibid. Recital 30 and Article 5(1)(g).

¹⁹⁶ Ibid. Recital 31, Article 5(c), Article 6(2) and Annex 3.

¹⁹⁷ Ibid. Recital 43, Article 5(e).

¹⁹⁸ Ibid. Recital 44, Article 5(f) and Article 26(7).

¹⁹⁹ Ibid. Article 5.

²⁰⁰ Ibid. Recital 54, Article 5, Article 6(2) and Annex 3(1)(c).

²⁰¹ Ibid. Recital 18, Article 5, Article 6(2), Annex 3(1)(c).

²⁰² Ibid. Recital 18.

Recital 63 incorporates emotional states as personal data, and clarifies that should not be considered legal, "The fact that an AI system is classified as a high-risk AI system under this Regulation should not be interpreted as indicating that the use of the system is lawful under other acts of Union law or under national law compatible with Union law, such as on the protection of personal data, on the use of polygraphs and similar tools or other systems to detect the emotional state of natural persons."²⁰³ Recital 59 mentions AI systems used for law enforcement, predicting who might commit a crime or be a crime victim, assessing evidence, or evaluating a person's risk of re-offending are considered as high-risk, likewise polygraphs. This represents another restriction to the potential improper use of NTs, making sure that processing these data is also under the GDPR statutes. The challenges might be how to accurately map who is using it with these purposes, and how to effectively educate the global population on it.

"For all other purposes, emotional recognition is permitted but considered "high risk" (Annex III 1[c]). This applies to AI neuroimaging methods that analyze emotional reactions to stimuli such as BCIs or closed-loop neuromodulation devices for affective disorders but also recreational consumer devices and possibly the entire field of neuromarketing (which likely falls outside the scope of exempted "scientific research"),²⁰⁴ complemented Bublitz et al. (2024).

Conversely, Ienca et al. (2022) remarked a more optimistic perspective regarding governance, "[...] *emotion AI* (also known as *affective computing*) has emerged with the aim of studying and developing systems that are capable to detect, interpret, process, and simulate human affects and emotions. [...] These inherent features of mental data raise meaningful ethical and legal implications. These implications are being currently addressed at several levels of governance such as technical and biosecurity standards, ethical guidelines and analogous soft law approaches, consumer protection regulation, and international human rights law."²⁰⁵ Most countries are not yet giving the importance it truly requires, and as Istace et al. (2022) mentioned, is not only limited to emotions, but many other mental processes as illustrated in Figure 15. Meaning, there are many other categories potentially ignored.

²⁰³ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AIA), OJ 2024 L 1689, Recital 63.

²⁰⁴ Bublitz et al., 2024, p.3014.

²⁰⁵ Ienca et al., 2022, pp.3-6.

“Data on the structure and functioning of the brain generated by neuroimaging technologies (also known as ‘neurodata’) facilitates a detailed analysis of brain activity patterns. When processed by sophisticated artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms, researchers can use this neurodata to correlate patterns of brain activity with imagined language, emotions, visual images or movements.”¹¹ (p.2) [...] “Using sophisticated decoding algorithms, studies have shown that it is possible to extract information on individuals’ mental processes and states, including visual perception,¹¹ memories,¹² semantic knowledge,¹³ emotions,¹⁴ dreams,¹⁵ inner speech¹⁶ and intentions.¹⁷ The process, however, is technically complex. Decoding visual perception, for example, requires that study participants’ have their brain activity measured via fMRI while watching videos.”¹¹ (p.2)

Figure 15 - Between Science-Fact and Science-Fiction: Innovation and Ethics in Neurotechnology²⁰⁶

In summary, NTs connected to AI systems using biometrics (brain biometrics implied) should not be used to categorize profiles, nor used for commercial, nor educational, nor workplace, nor for non-authentication purposes, nor for 24 hours real time monitoring, nor for manipulative or subliminal techniques, nor with adverse impacts on physical, psychological health or financial interests, nor for polygraph (lie detector) purposes, although it fails to define “brain data” specifically. Besides that, it might allow military, national security and scientific research use cases, plus other potential reported and analyzed exceptions, that even if considered as high-risk, can leave other opened scenarios like neuromarketing, other data categories and training brain-data AI models, creating regional brain patterns and be used for brain predictions, that if accessed by unauthorized persons might be used negatively.

4.3.3. Transparency and Vulnerable Groups

AI systems that interact with people or generate content, regardless of their risk level, may present a specific risk of impersonation or deception. Therefore, their use should be subject to specific transparency obligations, e.g., notifying the users that they are interacting with an AI, which may be waived only if the AI system's nature is already obvious to a reasonably well-informed, observant, and cautious person. In fulfilling this requirement, the system's intended interaction with vulnerable groups, such as those with disabilities or of a certain age, must be considered. Furthermore, individuals must be notified when an AI system processes their biometric data to identify or infer emotions,

²⁰⁶ Istace et al., 2024. (Modified by the Author. Content based on Istace et al., p.2.)

intentions, or other personal attributes. All such notifications should be provided in accessible formats for persons with disabilities.²⁰⁷

The protection of the rights and safety of the vulnerable populations, as children, women, people with disabilities, certain age, racial, ethnic and sexual orientation groups is crucial,²⁰⁸ as the AI systems might have the capacity to forecast their different spaces during their entire course of life, leading to personal consequences. If the systems are related to essential public assistance benefits and services from public authorities namely healthcare services, social security benefits, social services, banking or insurance, will also be classified as high-risk, due to the latent risks and impacts.²⁰⁹

Currently, most of the NT users are vulnerable populations, people with disabilities (physical and mental), children, women, or even highly susceptible individuals who are easily swayed by cutting-edge technologies. Is consent enough in these cases? Is notifying them that they are interacting with an AI sufficient?

4.3.4. Data Sharing

Recital 68 also touches the “data spaces” which is crucial for sharing data between businesses and governments in the public interest, and for creating a trustworthy, accountable, and non-discriminatory environment for it. It is mentioned that this data is essential for training, validating, and testing AI systems. As an example, the Regulation named the European Health Data Space, which allows secure, privacy-preserving and transparent access to health data for training AI algorithms. This should be understood as under encryption, anonymized and with no access to the raw data conditions.²¹⁰ But should this be allowed for neurodata? Will neurodata be considered medical²¹¹ or public data?²¹² Even if it is non-medical data? Who will have access to it? and who presently does?

²⁰⁷ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AIA), OJ 2024 L 1689, Recital 132.

²⁰⁸ Ibid. Recitals 54- 57, Article 5(b)(g).

²⁰⁹ Ibid. Recital 58 and Recital 96.

²¹⁰ Ibid. Recital 68, Article 10.

²¹¹ Ibid. Recital 68.

²¹² Ibid. Recital 70.

The AI Act covers copyrights and requires their authorization in order to use it for development and training of new models,²¹³ preventing its data mining and allowing “opt out” options to its creators. Recently, Denmark gave to its citizens copyrights of their faces, voice and body.²¹⁴ Shouldn’t we do the same with certain neural data?

Certain brain data should be considered as copyright of its holder/producer, no neurodata mining should arise, nor be used to train any AI models, nor use for private or company benefits, monetization, as it also involves fundamental rights, sensitive data and can translate itself into discrimination scenarios, it should have an explicit purpose, consent, and still would be at the border of transgressing fundamental rights. Thoughts should be copyrighted with no “opt out” options. Self-replicating data, unauthorized copies²¹⁵ nor neurodata transfers should be allowed.

4.3.5. Future-Proof Resilience

Radio Equipment interconnected with AI are considered high-risk,²¹⁶ and if take a closer look into which devices it refers to, the Radio Equipment Directive (RED: Directive 2014/53/EU),²¹⁷ named the following non-exhaustive applicable categories: Smart phones, Tablets, Smart devices, Network devices using Bluetooth, Wireless Access Systems, Radio Local Area Network or Ultra-Wideband Technology (comprising mobile and satellite services), including wearables, robots, drones and even autonomous vehicles; Medical Devices for imaging, monitoring, assistive listening devices, or active implants (for humans and animal uses).²¹⁸ The list doesn’t seem to include explicitly NTs, nor passive implants, nor non-medical listening devices, nor smart glasses, nonetheless as most of them have mobile and other type of connectivity, they should fall into both, the AI Act and the RED. Important to remind the readers that as it is a Directive, each EU Member State might have implemented it with slight variations.

²¹³ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AIA), OJ 2024 L 1689, Recitals 104-107, Article 25(5), Article 53(1)(c).

²¹⁴ Bryant, 2025.

²¹⁵ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AIA), OJ 2024 L 1689, Recital 110.

²¹⁶ Ibid. Recital 50 and Annex I (6).

²¹⁷ Directive 2014/53/EU (RED), OJ 2024 153 L.

²¹⁸ EC, Publication in accordance with Article 1(3) of Commission Decision 2000/299/EC.

Briefly explained, the RED compels these devices to meet essential requirements for health and safety, electromagnetic compatibility (EMC), and efficient use of the radio spectrum, it also includes technical features for the protection of privacy, personal data and against fraud. Manufacturers, importers and distributors have strict obligations, as conducting a conformity assessment, maintaining technical documentation, and affixing the CE mark to demonstrate that their products comply with the directive's rules before being placed on the market. More recently and with the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) it complemented its related hardware and software cybersecurity and environmental considerations. RED Annex 1.1 excludes “(c) equipment constructed by individual radio amateurs for experimental and scientific purposes related to amateur radio.”²¹⁹ Interestingly, there are online manuals on how to build your own NT for approximately US\$1000, which could leave a potential regulatory gap if presented as experimental or if commercialized. (See Annex 9.3).

Given the fact that NTs could turn into the next cell phone, our *personal command center* and might replace keyboards and computer mouses/mice (See Figure 16), should NTs with AI connectivity have access to your bank account information, to your health information, to your thoughts, to your family information, to your most sacred data? In a deep fake or deceptive cybersecurity scenario, which multi-authentication would be applicable to NTs? If your brain structure, oscillations or brain password²²⁰ turn into a typical authentication biometric? Or even with the current dactyl biometrics, a social engineering attack targeting individuals with BCIs, could soon, represent a profound vulnerability, with amplified access to the brain data, especially in the case of vulnerable populations. Biometrics combined with a person’s conscious or unconscious mental landscape, would serve as a catastrophic mixture for a financial and reputational breach. We must recognize that most people are technologically *naïve*, awareness trainings are not enough; healthy tech conscious people have given their email, router, platform passwords, including online banking passwords for much less effort.²²¹ What would be the next security border that can comprehend the complexity and severity of the NTs?

²¹⁹ Directive 2014/53/EU (RED), OJ 2024 153 L, Annex 1(1)(c).

²²⁰ Stanford Report, 2025.

²²¹ CrowdStrike, 2023.

Figure 16 – Our *Personal Command Center* landscape of risk

The AI Act consistently reinforces the necessity for high-risk systems to meet an appropriate level of accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity, throughout their lifecycle,²²² as well as, keeping detailed levels of technical documentation, change management logs, risk mitigation, performance metrics, and even fail-safe plans, in case of needed to safety interrupt its' operation.²²³

“Article 15(5) indicates [...] The technical solutions to address AI specific vulnerabilities shall include, where appropriate, measures to prevent, detect, respond to, resolve and control for attacks trying to manipulate the training data set (data poisoning), or pre-trained components used in training (model poisoning), inputs designed to cause the AI model to make a mistake (adversarial examples or model evasion), confidentiality attacks or model flaws.” Article 42(2) also states “High-risk AI systems that have been certified or for which a statement of conformity has been issued under a cybersecurity scheme pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2019/881” (CRA)²²⁴ should comply with Cybersecurity requirements in Article 15 of the AI Act.

²²² Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AIA), OJ 2024 L 1689, Recitals 74-77, Article 13(3)(b)(ii), Article 15.

²²³ Ibid. Recitals 75 and Article 15(4).

²²⁴ Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 (CRA), OJ 2024 L 2847.

Recital 138 addresses a “future-proof” resilience, but how can we attain future-proof for NTs with AI capabilities? Can NTs (with or without AI capabilities) be hacked? For more than a decade²²⁵, pacemakers, insulin pumps, among other medical devices have been hacked.²²⁶ Sponsored NT hackathons and trainings on bio and BCI penetration testing, for students and ethical hackers have been promoted for almost a decade too, on the annual DEFCON Biohacking Village²²⁷, Black HAT Trainings²²⁸ and Imperial College Neurotech Society Hackathons²²⁹, to mention a few. This could indicate large numbers of people (ethical and non-ethical) currently skilled to hack them. Cybersecurity for NTs and post-quantum tech are two topics that will require special legal and technological requirements, as the current ones will not be sufficient. Is ENISA and the rest of the cybersecurity teams in the World ready for this?

Ienca mentioned it back in 2015, and still “Neurosecurity”²³⁰ is considered an emerging technology by ISACA²³¹, and other major technology-framework referents. In their webpage, Er. Kritika, a cybersecurity researcher, published a paper, which summarizes the complexities and the potential proposals around them.²³² Before it is covered, Neurosecurity definition must be presented. Ruiz-Vanoye et al. (2024) made a great differentiation between “Brain Data Security” and “Neurosecurity” (Figure 17):

“Neurosecurity encompasses a broader range of protection measures, including physical and ethical aspects. This concept refers to the comprehensive protection of the brain and its functions against external threats, ensuring the physical security of implanted devices, protection against electromagnetic interference, and the integrity of mental processes. In contrast, brain data security focuses exclusively on the security of neural data, emphasising the protection of brain-generated information through methods such as encryption, authentication, and anonymisation. While neurosecurity addresses the holistic protection of the brain as a whole, brain data security specialises in safeguarding the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of brain data.” (p.21)

Figure 17 - Brain Data Security and Neurosecurity²³³

²²⁵ DEFCON, 2017.

²²⁶ Akitra, 2024.

²²⁷ DEFCON, 2017.

²²⁸ Black Hat - CyberArk, 2021.

²²⁹ ICL Neurotech Society, 2025.

²³⁰ Ienca, 2015.

²³¹ ISACA, 2025.

²³² Kritika, 2025.

²³³ Ruiz-Vanoye et al., 2024. (Modified by the Author. Content based on Ruiz-Vanoye et al., p.21).

Kritika's text outlines some cybersecurity challenges, embracing the risk of thought injection, where a malicious command could be disguised as a genuine neural instruction, and consciousness leakage, a potential quantum phenomenon that could inadvertently broadcast private thoughts. The brain's neuroplasticity could also lead to "security drift," causing a system to misinterpret a user's evolving thought patterns. Furthermore, new attack vectors are emerging, such as "neuro-linguistic hacking," which embeds malicious commands in everyday language, and the potential exploitation of the temporal lobe to manipulate or extract memories. Finally, the cognitive encryption paradox raises questions about privacy, as the very act of using *a thought as a key* could make it vulnerable.²³⁴

To address these critical issues, it advocates for the urgent establishment of an International Neuro-Rights Convention, a global agreement to protect rights such as mental privacy and neurological self-determination. In addition, it proposes the creation of a Global Neuro-Digital Regulatory Body to set international security standards and mediate disputes. Also emphasizes the need for increased funding for interdisciplinary research initiatives to better understand this complex field, as well as the importance of public education campaigns to raise awareness about both the benefits and risks of neurotechnology. Lastly, it stresses the need for adaptive regulatory frameworks that can evolve with the technology, rather than relying on traditional static approaches.²³⁵

Ruiz-Vanoye et al. (2024) also made a series of fundamental recommendations for securing our brain and the brain data, they propose a multi-faceted approach. They highlighted five main methods: Data Anonymization, Blockchain, Access Control, Data Encryption, and Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS). Each of these methods addresses a different aspect of the security challenge. Besides, also recommended several future-focused ideas that merge with these existing methods to enhance Mental Privacy and Neuro-Rights. These concepts include Brain Firewalls, and specialized Advanced Encryption for Brain Data that uses unique neural patterns as biometric encryption keys. The development of Neuro-Consent Interfaces would empower individuals to have precise control over who accesses their neural data, while Cognitive Liberty Guardians (autonomous AI systems) would monitor and protect individuals' Neuro-rights.

²³⁴ Kritika, 2025.

²³⁵ Ibid.

Moreover, the document suggests physical protections like electromagnetic shielding and Integrated Security Implants that can detect tampering and self-deactivate.²³⁶

According to The Cost of a Data Breach Report 2025, the global average cost of a data breach is US\$4.4 million, 97% due to lacked AI governance policies and access controls. Phishing (social engineering) was the most frequent attack vector, accounting for 16% of all data breaches. Healthcare and financial services industries were also identified as the most expensive targets for data breaches.²³⁷ These, plus the fact that are, so far, an estimate of more than 14.000 online unsecured medical devices²³⁸, makes NTs perfect areas for hackers to attack. Will regular post-market monitoring,²³⁹ human oversight²⁴⁰ and fundamental rights impact assessments²⁴¹ be sufficient for NTs?²⁴²

Or if we based it on the CRA, would the following requirements be enough for NTs? risk and conformity assessments, mitigating vulnerabilities, password-managers, access management, encryption, VPNs, data minimization, opt-out mechanisms, regular testing, updates and patching, audits, monitoring and documentation?²⁴³ BCIs are considered class I by the CRA, meaning, a lower risk digital product, only subject to self-assess their conformity.

4.3.6. Latest Releases

Earlier this year, Apple released their BCI-HID protocol²⁴⁴, which introduces a novel significant privacy-by-design architecture for brain-computer interfaces, it does not collect, nor processes personal data, only commands (“scroll” or “click”). This protocol facilitates interoperability of NT users with their phones, tablets or laptops without physically moving. This has the potential to massify NTs in the next months, converting

²³⁶ Ruiz-Vanoye et al., 2024.

²³⁷ IBM and Ponemon Institute, 2025.

²³⁸ Censys, 2024.

²³⁹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AIA), OJ 2024 L 1689, Article 72.

²⁴⁰ Ibid. Article 14.

²⁴¹ Ibid. 2024, Article 27.

²⁴² Ibid. 2024.

²⁴³ Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 (CRA), OJ 2024 L 2847.

²⁴⁴ Farahany, BCI-HID, 2025.

Apple and Android into the first NT “gatekeepers”. Will the Digital Market Act (DMA) (Regulation (EU) 2022/1925)²⁴⁵ apply to protocols too? Protocols are not explicitly mentioned under the categories of “core platform services” but have the potential to transform into future massive online services.

Recital 118-120 of the AI Act refers to the Digital Services Act (DSA) Regulation (EU) 2022/2065.²⁴⁶ As NTs with VR AI glasses from Meta continue to expand, will they be the first NTs’ VLOP (Very Large Online Platform)? Or Apple? Neuralink? OpenAI? Microsoft? What kind of augmented influence will they comprise? Which additional measures should be taken (legally and technologically)? Is the DSA prepared for this? Should the DSA consider other ranges of users for NT AI platforms? Will the Directive (EU) 2019/882,²⁴⁷ (also mentioned in the AI Act) commonly known as the European Accessibility Act (EAA) serve as the perfect justification to promote and expand the use of DTC NTs?

The Regulation gaps can be further elucidated by considering one of the newest releases, “Alterego”²⁴⁸ (See Figure 18), a non-invasive wearable device (a former MIT Project) which claims to be the first near-telepathic interface. Its public release was made on September 9, 2025. According to the creators, thoughts are not being read, only the *speaking intentions signals* from the peripheral nervous system, captured from multiple bones in the head. The AI interprets the signals and uses them to communicate with electronic devices and other Alterego users. It also has camera and multi-language translations capabilities, as additional features, it can convert physical drawings into digital assets or applications, only by “thinking” it and silently commanding it, no words, no writing.²⁴⁹

More open questions are left behind... Will this be considered as a new type of data in the GDPR? Will neuromuscular data be considered as health data? As per its AI capabilities, it is considered as a high-risk AI but will be considered as a biometric or emotion recognition device? Will this new data category be used for identity theft?

²⁴⁵ Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 (DMA), OJ 2022 L 265.

²⁴⁶ Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 (DSA), OJ 2022 L 277.

²⁴⁷ Directive (EU) 2019/882 (EAA), OJ 2019 L 151.

²⁴⁸ Day, 2025.

²⁴⁹ Alterego, 2025.

Espionage, blackmail, or surveillance? This is only one of the first NT releases from many more soon to be communicated; we are entering a new technological era. Which international organization is proactively monitoring them? Will the regulation frameworks follow these accelerated technologies, accordingly?

Figure 18 - Alterego wearable - Sketch to App Camera Testing²⁵⁰

²⁵⁰ Ibid. (Screenshot taken by their product release video in their website).

4.4. General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR)

4.4.1. *The Regulation*

The Regulation (EU) 2023/988's main purpose is “[...] to ensure the health and safety of consumers and the functioning of the internal market as regards products intended for consumers.”²⁵¹ And “[...] ensuring coherence with the market surveillance legislative framework for products falling within the scope of Union harmonisation legislation [...]”²⁵² and avoid overlapping provisions. It entered into force on December 13th, 2024.

The previous one, Directive 2001/95/EC laid “down the requirement that consumer products must be safe and that Member States’ market surveillance authorities must take action against dangerous products [...]”²⁵³ and has been now reinforced with guidelines for online platforms and new technologies.

The GPSR comprehensively addresses product safety within the consumer market, extending its scope to include products initially designed for professional use that later enter the consumer domain, as well as second-hand, repaired, reconditioned, or recycled products²⁵⁴ re-entering the commercial supply chain, unless explicitly presented for repair or as historical collectibles.²⁵⁵ It also includes distance selling, including online sales,²⁵⁶ when targeted at consumers within the European Union, with assessment factors like geographical dispatch, language, payment methods, and domain names.²⁵⁷ The core principle mandates economic operators to place only safe products on the market, primarily achieved through product design and features that account for intended and foreseeable use, with remaining risks mitigated by safeguards like warnings and instructions.²⁵⁸

²⁵¹ Regulation (EU) 2023/988 (GPSR), OJ 2023 L 135, Recital 4.

²⁵² Ibid. Recital 3.

²⁵³ Ibid. Recital 1.

²⁵⁴ Ibid. Recital 16.

²⁵⁵ Ibid. Recital 16 and 18.

²⁵⁶ Ibid. Recital 20-21 and Article 19.

²⁵⁷ Ibid. Recital 21.

²⁵⁸ Ibid. Recital 22, Article 6(1)(d) and Article 35(1).

The product safety assessment is holistic, considering physical, mechanical, and chemical characteristics,²⁵⁹ presentation, and the specific needs and risks for vulnerable consumers, such as children, older persons, and individuals with disabilities. This includes environmental risks impacting health and safety, and health risks from digitally connected products, particularly mental health risks for vulnerable groups, emphasizing the need for safety, security, and privacy by design for children's products.²⁶⁰ The assessment also considers the accessibility of necessary safety information and the product's safety throughout its entire lifespan,²⁶¹ including risks posed by items that connect to or influence other products.²⁶²

In Recital 29 and Article 6(e), a risk differentiation by gender was made, which highlights the requirements to achieve gender-balance, representative and inclusive standards that can avoid discrepancies and gender safety gaps. This is important to mention, as there are NTs claiming they can solve moods and menstrual cramps²⁶³ and other devices with pregnancy uses²⁶⁴, which should be carefully assessed, as it could impact not only vulnerable consumers, but could represent potential health risks of future generations.

Regarding terminology: “The World Health Organisation defines ‘health’ as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity.”²⁶⁵ A product is considered *safe* if, under normal use, presents only minimal and acceptable risks consistent with a high level of consumer health and safety.²⁶⁶ Although “acceptable risks” is a wide-ranging term, even if considers the probability and severity of a harm. On the other hand, a "serious risk" is only considered in terms of the need of a rapid intervention by market surveillance authorities, even if the harm is not immediate. Which in the case of NTs, could be hard to determine if current acceptable risks, with time and use could turn into irreversible health issues, like brain development impairments, including impacts on neuroplasticity.

²⁵⁹ Regulation (EU) 2023/988 (GPSR), OJ 2023 L 135, Recital 23.

²⁶⁰ Ibid. Recital 23 and Article 6(1)(e).

²⁶¹ Ibid. Recital 23.

²⁶² Ibid. Recital 24 and Article 6(1)(b)(g).

²⁶³ Lomas, 2024.

²⁶⁴ King et al., 2022.

²⁶⁵ Regulation (EU) 2023/988 (GPSR), OJ 2023 L 135, Recital 19.

²⁶⁶ Ibid. Article 3(2).

Another relevant term is “Market surveillance” which refers to the activities and measures carried out by a designated “market surveillance authority” to ensure that products comply with the regulation's requirements. These authorities are responsible for organizing and executing these activities within their Member State.²⁶⁷

Over the entire regulation, manufacturers, importers, distributors, all the supply and distribution chains are held accountable with numerous actions, even at the international cooperation level,²⁶⁸ making sure that each of them take the appropriate measures (identifying risks, detailing product descriptions, safety assessments, risk mitigation measures, investigating complaints and accidents) to ensure that they only made available products, which are safe and in conformity with this Regulation,²⁶⁹ and providing detailed safety information and instructions available in digital form, such as QR or data matrix codes. This technical documentation should be based on internal risk analysis and proportionate to the complexity of the product and the possible risks.²⁷⁰ This documentation shall be at the disposal of the market surveillance authorities for a period of ten years after the product has been placed on the market and make that documentation available to those authorities upon request.²⁷¹ Appointing a legal representative in the Union is also required.²⁷²

Marketing-responsible techniques are also subject of the regulation, especially in products presenting serious risks,²⁷³ although it wasn't covered extensively, which could represent an improvement point for further amendments. And as stated by Steindl, “The Amazon Alexa Fund invests in AI-powered neural interfaces to unlock speech/smart home controls and to develop new adaptive interfaces for assisted reality technology. Bill Gates' and Jeff Bezos' private investment firms are putting money into a company called Synchron, developing a minimally invasive endovascular brain implant. Meta is working on a neural interface via an EMG (electromyography) wristband to interact with AR or VR devices. Elon Musk continues to promote Neuralink, which has been approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for human trials. The Google Spin-off

²⁶⁷ Regulation (EU) 2023/988 (GPSR), OJ 2023 L 135, Article 3(24).

²⁶⁸ Ibid. Article 40.

²⁶⁹ Ibid. Recital 36, Article 7 and Article 9.

²⁷⁰ Ibid. Article 9(2) and Article 9 (3).

²⁷¹ Ibid. Article 9(3), Article 11(6), Article 15(4).

²⁷² Ibid. Recital 39 and Article 10.

²⁷³ Ibid. Recital 37, Recital 69 and Article 28(1).

Nextsense is exploring earbuds to perform EEGs through the ear in order to collect brain signals. The collected brain signals could be used for identification, to monitor epilepsy and predict seizures, for interaction with one's digital devices, or to keep people fit and healthy by learning how they sleep and how they walk. Apple has increased their number of neuro scientific researchers to study health neurotechnology and filed a patent for EEG-integrated AirPods.”²⁷⁴ Not only the NT field is significantly increasing, but its marketing responsibility as well, these new products and services, with online and neural capabilities, promise interconnecting humans to technology, and augmenting human capabilities with the help of BCIs, implants and even cell alteration therapies. To sum to Steindl's cite above, Neuralink's clinical trials in Canada and the UAE have been started, and in Great Britain have been previously launched,²⁷⁵ Meta released their new AI glasses collection (available in Europe starting on 2026) with Ray-Ban (Figure 19) and Oakley,²⁷⁶ and Open AI's new venture with Merge Labs, is “exploring the idea of using gene therapy to modify brain cells that would communicate with an implanted ultrasound device that could then “detect and modulate activity” in those genetically modified cells”²⁷⁷ under a new field called *sonogenetics*,²⁷⁸ making the race to the brain or as Farahany calls it, “Battle for your brain”²⁷⁹ more obvious and intense.

Figure 19 - Meta/Ray-Ban New AI Glasses and Meta Neural Band ²⁸⁰

²⁷⁴ Steindl, 2024.

²⁷⁵ Sinha, 2025.

²⁷⁶ Meta, 2025.

²⁷⁷ Farahany, The Tech Titans Are Coming for Your Brain, 2025.

²⁷⁸ Swetlitz, 2025.

²⁷⁹ Farahany, The Battle for Your Brain, 2024.

²⁸⁰ Meta, 2025. (Screenshot taken by their product release video in their website).

Consumers are encouraged to register products to receive safety warnings and recall information.²⁸¹ Recall notices must be clear, transparent and accurately describe risks, avoiding language that minimizes consumer perception of danger, and should provide accessible means for further information, like a toll-free telephone number or other interactive instrument.²⁸² In the event of a dangerous product recall, consumers should follow recall instructions but retain their right to seek remedies from the seller for non-conformity.²⁸³ Economic operators initiating a recall must offer consumers at least two options from repair, replacement, or an adequate refund, unless impossible or disproportionate, with repairs only permissible if the product's safety can be guaranteed post-repair.²⁸⁴ The Union also aims to cooperate and exchange product safety information with third-country regulatory authorities and international organizations, ensuring confidentiality and personal data protection, solely for consumer health and safety.²⁸⁵ Finally, penalties for economic operators and online marketplace providers who place dangerous products on the market must be effective, proportionate, and dissuasive, reflecting the infringement's nature, potential economic advantage, and the severity of consumer harm.²⁸⁶

Concerning online marketplace providers, they are not responsible for verifying the completeness or accuracy of information, as traceability rests with the trader, but they are obligated to cooperate with market surveillance authorities on product safety issues, including recalls and accident reporting,²⁸⁷ through the RAPEX system (now Safety Gate), which allows providers, platforms, authorities and the Commission to exchange information on dangerous products, inform consumers, transmit information to relevant national authorities, and serve as a centralized source.²⁸⁸

From voluntary commitments, such as the Product Safety Pledge,²⁸⁹ to mandatory due diligence obligations,²⁹⁰ online marketplaces are required to implement a robust and

²⁸¹ Regulation (EU) 2023/988 (GPSR), OJ 2023 L 135, Recital 86 and Article 35(3).

²⁸² Ibid. Recital 87 and Article 36.

²⁸³ Ibid. Recitals 88-89, Article 33(4), Article 37.

²⁸⁴ Ibid. Recital 91 and Article 37.

²⁸⁵ Ibid. Recital 95 and Article 40.

²⁸⁶ Ibid. Recitals 97-98 and Articles 40-42.

²⁸⁷ Ibid. Recital 68.

²⁸⁸ Ibid. Recital 68, Articles 25-27.

²⁸⁹ Ibid. Recital 48.

²⁹⁰ Ibid. Recital 49 and Article 22.

proactive approach to product safety, leveraging technology for the automated identification of dangerous products through improved alert systems like the Safety Gate Portal.²⁹¹ A designated single point of contact for regulatory authorities and for consumers it is also required. Their internal mechanisms must also align with existing obligations under Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 (DSA) to streamline communication, inform customers, authorities and ensure consumer protection.²⁹²

The Consumer Safety Network further enhances cooperation and coordination among the product safety authorities of the Member States on safety enforcement and market surveillance,²⁹³ with regular joint activities, including inspections of products acquired, online or offline, exchange of expertise, best practices and education.

4.4.2. Software Observations

Considering NTs, the GSPR, mentions in Recital 25, new technologies with new risks in consumers' health and safety, as hacking, should have software updates, and should be subject to new risk assessments. Recital 26 and Article 6(1)(g) also reinforce the need to take appropriate cybersecurity features, to protect the product from external influences, including malicious third parties; and for products with advanced functionalities, the assessment must also evaluate the evolving, learning and predictive nature of the product itself, thereby addressing the safety implications of a product that can change and adapt over time.²⁹⁴ Although, the GSPR overlooked two important topics, 1) the Software related products, as it was limitedly mentioned, only regarding the software update obligation mentioned above,²⁹⁵ and on Article 15, where upon request the economic operators shall identify and communicate traceability information of the software embedded in the product, applicable for a period of 6 years after the product release; but most of the software these days, is not even *embedded*, instead, they are hosted online, e.g., Cloud-storage based and with AI capabilities. 2) Mental health related risks and damages, in Recitals 19 and 23, these will be hard to identify and to be claimed,

²⁹¹ Regulation (EU) 2023/988 (GPSR), OJ 2023 L 135, Article 34.

²⁹² Ibid. Recital 50 and Article 22.

²⁹³ Ibid. Recital 76 and Article 30.

²⁹⁴ Ibid. Article 6(h).

²⁹⁵ Ibid. Recital 25 and Article 37(3).

especially if they materialize as gradual damages, therefore, potential risky NTs will be also hard to recall. “Mental health” is not detailly described in the regulation, and there are no references to software controls, video games, VR/AR devices, smart glasses, smart clothing, wearables, IoTs, emotions and biometric sensors or its associated applications, neither addresses learning impairment consequences, nor brain health limitations upon using a “serious risk” product, nor ethical nor moral concepts for them. Will these risks be included in their labels, instructions, technical documents and warnings? Will that be assessed? Is that enough to guarantee mental health, especially in vulnerable populations?

4.4.3. Further Standards

As Steindl mentions in her article, “[...] the GPSR is a safety net for all products not covered by other EU legislation and ensures protection against unsafe products.”²⁹⁶ But she also recognizes that: “All BCIs falling outside sector-specific product safety law are subject to horizontal product safety legislation. [...] As a general legislation, the GPSR does not address specific products or technologies. The GPSR does therefore not encompass any provisions specifically tailored to BCIs.”²⁹⁷ Consequently, all non-medical related-BCIs and smart-wearables are not directly covered, and as Steindl underlines it too, “The concerted efforts to improve general product safety legislation in the area of cybersecurity is highly relevant for consumer BCIs.”²⁹⁸

On the other hand, it will be worth looking at the ISEE 11073 - IEEE Standard for Health Informatics²⁹⁹ and also the ISO/IEC CD 8663³⁰⁰, that as mentioned by Gulotta, “Although it may seem too early to standardize BCIs, private standardization bodies are already working on this issue. The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Standard Association (IEEE SA) is set to release four standards on human augmentation: those on taxonomy and definitions, privacy and security, identity, and the methodologies and processes for ethical considerations. The development of ‘foundational standards’ related to BCIs was undertaken in 2022 by the Joint Technical Committee for information

²⁹⁶ Steindl, 2024, p.7.

²⁹⁷ Ibid. p.8.

²⁹⁸ Ibid. p.7.

²⁹⁹ IEEE, 2023.

³⁰⁰ ISO, 2025.

technology, a consensus-based and voluntary international standards group established by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC).”³⁰¹, seem to be the first to release international standards for human augmentation. The ISO/IEC CD 8663 specifically for Information technology and Brain-computer interfaces, which as of today, it has not yet been released, only a draft preview and the technical report,³⁰² seem to be developing favorably, including topics as data security, invasive versus non invasive, EEG processing methods, signal acquisition, and use cases as a) Smart Environments, b) Medical and Health, c) Learning, education and training, d) Gaming, e) Security and Authentication. Hoping they include cybersecurity-specifics on it as well, similar to the ones covered in the previous section. Other recommended ISO Standards are listed in Annex 9.5.

³⁰¹ Gulotta, 2024, p.243.

³⁰² ISO, 2025.

5. Potential Recommendations

Over the chapters of this paper various recommendations of my own and other authors have been presented and compiled in the consolidated Table 2. Additional general ideas on educational curriculums, have also been included in the Annex 9.4.

In 2017, the proposal of developing new *neurorights* was advised by Ienca in Europe, and Yuste in the United States, seeking to expand human rights to protect the mind from the risks posed by neurotechnologies. This idea, championed by the Neurorights Foundation, has inspired legislative efforts, most notably in Chile. The Chilean constitutional amendment protects mental privacy and free will, and an additional bill aims to regulate neurotechnologies as medical devices while classifying neural data as a human organ to prohibit its sale. However, the move to preserve *neurorights* is not universally accepted, with critics arguing that existing legal frameworks already offer sufficient protection.³⁰³ Or might dilute the significance and impact of the current fundamental rights, as mentioned by Bublitz.³⁰⁴

Spain recently adopted a softer approach to governing neurotechnology through its new Digital Rights Charter. This charter is not a legally binding regulation but rather a guiding framework for future actions by Spanish authorities. It articulates a reference framework to guarantee citizens' rights in the new digital age, specifically mentioning neurotechnology and neurorights as a focus area. This proactive approach, which prioritizes guidance over strict legislation, is similar to one issued by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for early regulatory efforts. Both examples demonstrate a preference for anticipatory governance that can evolve with the technology, instead of potentially restrictive laws.³⁰⁵

As Chavarriaga et al. (2023) mentioned, while many neurotechnologies are still in their early stages, they have the potential to significantly change human interaction and may even redefine what it means to be human. This necessitates a global conversation to establish ethical standards and usage limits. A study on this topic offers five

³⁰³ Chavarriaga et al., 2023, p.8.

³⁰⁴ Bublitz, 2022.

³⁰⁵ Chavarriaga et al., 2023, p.9.

recommendations for a governance system to ensure neurotechnologies benefit humanity: first, create tools to monitor neurotechnology trends and their impacts; second, develop new, integrated governance approaches for this diverse field; third, involve a global, multilateral, and multi-stakeholder process to establish a widely accepted framework; fourth, coordinate neurotechnology governance with discussions on other converging technologies like AI and data privacy; and fifth, increase public awareness about the present and future impacts of these technologies.³⁰⁶

This research cannot be concluded without mentioning the UNESCO's First Draft of a Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology, finally released August 2024. "[...] These broad consultations [...] contribute to ensuring that the elaboration of the draft text of a recommendation is inclusive, multicultural, pluralistic and multi-stakeholder shaped."³⁰⁷ More than 800 participants from more than 100 countries were involved in the consultation process, with more than 7000 comments which demonstrated high worldwide interest.³⁰⁸ "[...] based on the outcome of intergovernmental discussions and negotiations in 2025, the final recommendation will be agreed upon by representatives of UNESCO's Member States and submitted for adoption at its General Conference."³⁰⁹

The recommendations were grounded in values such as respect for human rights, fundamental freedoms, human dignity, promoting human health and well-being, ensuring diversity, inclusivity, non-discrimination, fairness, sustainability and global solidarity. They emphasized ethical principles as beneficence, self-determination, mental privacy, protection of neural data, trustworthiness, and global justice.³¹⁰

Further suggestions embrace topics as, a) establishing incentives for responsible innovation, conducting thorough impact assessments, and ensuring equitable global access to neurotechnologies; b) the protection of fundamental rights including freedom of thought, mental privacy, autonomy, and self-determination, alongside the ethical and

³⁰⁶ Chavarriaga et al., 2023, p.10.

³⁰⁷ UNESCO, Towards a Draft Text of a Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology, 2024, p.7.

³⁰⁸ UNESCO, Preliminary Report on the first draft of the Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology, 2024, p.3.

³⁰⁹ UNESCO, Towards a Draft Text of a Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology, 2024, p.7.

³¹⁰ UNESCO, First Draft of a Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology, 2024, pp.8-12.

secure management of neural and cognitive biometric data; c) legal updates to the existing privacy laws to explicitly cover neural data, mandate explicit opt-in consent for sensitive data processing, and adhere to principles of data minimization and purpose limitation; d) robust security measures like "ethics by design" and others already contemplated by the CRA; e) transparency, public literacy, and inclusive engagement to foster informed decision-making and prevent misinformation; f) establishing oversight mechanisms for long-term impact evaluation and special protections for vulnerable populations, including user-friendly hardware-based controls for selective feature disabling; g) for educational and workplace uses, the prohibition of "neuroprofiling" and other misuses, like for example, neuromarketing, manipulation, behavioral modification, establishing measures around them, regardless of if they have medical or non-medical related purposes.³¹¹ Figure 20 also presents general recommendations by promoting panels of experts, neurorights, raising awareness, treaties, procedures and guiding principles.

PROPOSED PATH FORWARD FOR THE UNITED NATIONS TO ADVANCE NEURORIGHTS IN THE AGE OF NEUROTECHNOLOGY

Figure 20 - Recommendations. International Human Rights Protection Gaps in the Age of the Neurotechnology³¹²

³¹¹ UNESCO, First Draft of a Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology, 2024.

³¹² Genser et al., 2022, p.6.

Multiple recommendations have been reviewed, now it is time to observe how countries and regions continue to advance towards the neurotechnologies, as well as in the political, social, economic and legal fields, and associated technology developments and protections. International collaboration will be key for a successful governance and an effective legislation.

Table 2 - Neurotechnology Recommendations

Topic	Regulation Recommendations	Other related Recommendations
MDR Regulation (EU) 2017/745	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Include non-medical intended Software and non-physiological processes (Mental, brain, psychological, other Cognitive-affective neurodata, etc.) - Clearly indicate non-medical intended Brain devices that track neuronal activity, not only "modify neuronal activity". - A special detailed informed consent to be considered. Invasive vs Wearable, and as per different types of neurodata. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manufacturers of neuro-technologies must thoroughly understand and comply with the MDR's requirements, as mentioned by the Implementing regulations, as a Class III. A proactive notification to the current EU registered companies would be crucial.
MDR Implementing Regulations: (EU) 2022/2346, (EU) 2022/2347	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incorporate non-medical intended Software, wearables and other NT devices. - Categorize other NT risks, e.g., Decoding thoughts into text or BCI Bi-directional communications. Include a similar statement as in the AIA, regarding manipulation, subliminal components and further type of misuses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providers should have the obligation to clearly differentiate between purposes, e.g., enhancement vs therapeutic purposes. Marketing-wise, technical documentation and user instructions.
GDPR Regulation (EU) 2016/679	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthen current Human Rights and/or potential inclusion of Neurorights (Mental privacy, personal identity, free will, fair access and protection from algorithmic biases). (Yuste et al, 2017) - Inclusion of Neurodata: management and sharing specifics, per types of data (Health Data vs Mental States vs Thoughts). - Encompass non-medical mental data and amplified Neurodata in AI models. - Incorporate Cognitive-affective neurodata guidelines (thoughts, memories, beliefs, opinions, perceptions, attitudes, emotions, moods, desires & mental states). - Explicit and special informed consent for the brain data, metadata and other outputs. - Opt-out option for neuro data and/or potentially granting copyrights to some categories of neuro data. Financial Penalties. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mental Data Protection Impact Assessments / MDPIA (Ienca et al, 2022) - Combine a set of soft law with hard law, with different levels of rules for each. Risk warning mechanisms, policies, rules of conduct, industry standards, reviews, certification systems and for governments to incentivize companies to adopt these self-regulatory measures, for instance by offering tax breaks to encourage the establishment of ethics committees and adherence to these standards. (Wei et al, 2025) - Neuro-Consent Interfaces (Ruiz-Vanoye et al, 2024)
AI Act Regulation (EU) 2024/1689	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Openly address neuro data and AI models trained with it. - Special neurodata guardrails for Data Spaces. - Specific Neuromarketing boundaries and guidelines. - Opt-out option for neuro data and/or potentially granting copyrights to some categories of neuro data. Financial Penalties. - Address post-quantum cybersecurity challenges. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incorporate current NT cybersecurity protections requirements and measures. (Kritika (2025), Ruiz-Vanoye et al (2024), Cognitive Security Institute, etc.) - International Neuro-Rights Convention, Global Neuro-Digital Regulatory Body, interdisciplinary research initiatives, public education campaigns & adaptive regulatory frameworks. (Kritika, 2025)
GPSR Regulation (EU) 2023/988	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Delineate the "acceptable risks" definition for NTs. - "Mental health" should be detailly described. - A special reference to software controls, regarding metaverse, video games, VR/AR devices, smart-clothing, wearables, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reference to the Radio Equipment Directive. - Reevaluation of the National Telecommunication Acts.
Other Regulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DMA → BCI-HID Protocols might turn into the new BCI gatekeepers → DMA Regulation to be reviewed by policymakers. - DSA → VR AI Glasses might turn into the first BCI VLOP → DSA Regulation to be reviewed by policymakers. - CRA → Address NT specific Cybersecurity Measures and Post-quantum cybersecurity requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manufacturers should consider NIS2, ISO 27001 certification, implementation and having a responsible for Information Security Management System (ISMS). - Corporate CISM to incorporate political, economic, social, etc. risk factors, to their business risk management plans.
Creation of an EU or International Neuro Law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness, governance and compliance trainings. - Conformité Européenne (CE) mark for NTs. - A Neurodata supervisory authority. - Internal or external boards to assess the ethical implications of neurotechnology development and deployment. - Transparent guidelines for neuromarketing plays. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create a High-Level Panel on Neurotechnology, Neurorights, and Neuroethics (Genser et al, 2022) - ISO Standards on BCI and Human Augmentation to be highly recommended for manufacturers and providers.
UNESCO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - First Draft of a Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology (Soft-law) as a general guidance for NTs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highly recommended for the USA to remain part of UNESCO.

6. Conclusion

It is no longer a matter of science fiction to consider the potential opportunities and consequences that these cutting-edge technologies will bring, and the ‘Digital Darwinism’³¹³ will keep causing considerable distress to the EU competitiveness. Recommendations as “removing regulatory hurdles”³¹⁴ and finding the “right balance between caution and innovation”³¹⁵ were recently envisioned in the 2025 “Draghi report”³¹⁶ nonetheless, we cannot forget these actions must be carefully analyzed before executing them, as rapid technology changes have the potential to test the boundaries of EU ethics, law and have major repercussions in the legal systems globally.

Neurotechnologies are rapidly becoming realities. And we must inquire ourselves can consent be truly informed when the technology itself has the potential to alter cognitive processes? How can we mitigate their negative impact or uses? What is the best course of action?

Quantum technologies, Artificial Intelligence, Neurotechnologies and Biocomputing will coexist and complement each other soon, it is highly probable we will see hybrid systems combining their strengths on different approaches. Nevertheless, it is imperative that an international legal framework gets developed, that could have the possibility to balance innovation while protecting of fundamental rights and ethical principles.

We, as professionals and as a global society, have a gigantic responsibility with our future generations, and we need our current legal systems to adapt and address the unique challenges these emerging fields will bring. Technology is moving faster and faster; regulations and legal frameworks need to be proactively executed.

³¹³ Solis, 2025.

³¹⁴ Draghi, 2024, p.3.

³¹⁵ Ibid. p.3.

³¹⁶ Publications Office of the European Union, The Draghi report on EU competitiveness, 2025.

In conclusion, the responsible development and use of neurotechnologies require a multi-faceted approach that integrates legal, ethical, and technological safeguards. By fostering collaboration between researchers, policymakers, and the public, we can ensure that these transformative technologies are used for the benefit of humanity, while safeguarding fundamental rights.

Now the question will stay with you readers: what would you do next to prepare and improve these changes in the social and legal fields for future generations? And as Draghi mentioned, “The European Union exists to ensure that Europe’s fundamental values are always upheld: democracy, freedom, peace, equity and prosperity in a sustainable environment. If Europe cannot any longer deliver these values for its people, it will have lost its reason for being.”³¹⁷ Therefore, are we making everything possible to make it ethically, correct?... We should and we can!!

This work ends with a bonus reflection, an regional cultural classic collaboration thanks to our 96-year-old *Oma* (Grandma), the song named "*Die Gedanken sind frei*" ("Thoughts are free"), considered an “Anthem of Resistance” since the 13th Century and broadly known as a song since 1842, once the melody was included by Hoffmann von Fallersleben.³¹⁸ This song represents and supports the freedom of thought, freedom of political or ideological beliefs and should serve as a peaceful non-political reminder, to keep supporting our freedom of thought, but this time from the technological and legal perspectives.

...*Die Gedanken sind frei*... und sie sollten frei bleiben!!

...The Thoughts are free... and they should remain free!!

Lyrics available in Annex 9.6.

³¹⁷ Draghi, 2024, p.2.

³¹⁸ Hoffmann von Fallersleben.

7. Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted Technologies

During the ideation of this workpaper the author used “Google NotebookLM” to summarize 256 scientific research papers (which were previously available online in Google Scholar), in PDF, all listed in the Bibliography (Section: Initial Survey of Literature), with the purpose of efficiently streamlining the access and selection of the ones that were going to be taken in consideration for the Master Thesis (Literature research only). The majority of the papers were excluded as their relevance, for this thesis, was not as appropriate, but were still included in the bibliography, as a form of repository for the initial exploration. Both sections have been explicitly distinguished.

During the initial steps of the conceptualization of the Master Thesis Topic, Google Gemini was consulted for general “ideas” regarding risks and a possible introduction but were immediately discarded due to the inclusion of irrelevant, unrealistic and too futurist scenarios. Segment summarization was also contemplated (merely for the recommendations section) but later discarded or highly modified (90%) by the author, as it focused on other areas irrelevant for that particular chapter.

Figure 7 and Figure 16 were created with the help of Gemini. Gemini facilitated the graphics / icons only. Wording was manually added by the author. Content source: author’s general knowledge.

Gemini also helped with the ISO table creation on Annex 9.5, once I gave the ISO Standards List.

All citations were included appropriately, all information included is merely a result of valid and trustworthy research papers, sources and the author’s own thoughts. The author carefully reviewed and corroborated all sources and citations to make sure no errors happened during the elaboration of this research paper.

8. Bibliography

- Akitra. (2024, May 21). *From Fingerprints To Thoughts: The Future Of Neurosecurity*. Retrieved August 2025, from Akitra: <https://akitra.com/from-fingerprints-to-thoughts-the-future-of-neurosecurity/>
- Alterege. (2025, September 09). Home. Retrieved September 2025, from Alterego: <https://www.alterege.io/>
- Asamblea Legislativa Republica de Costa Rica. (n.d.). *Consulta de Proyectos de Ley*. Retrieved July, from Asamblea Legislativa Republica de Costa Rica: https://www.asamblea.go.cr/Centro_de_informacion/Consultas_SIL/SitePages/ConsultaProyectos.aspx
- Asch, S. E. (1951). *Effects of group pressure upon the modification and distortion of judgments*. Retrieved July 2025, from Carnegie Press: <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1952-00803-001>
- Black Hat - CyberArk. (2021). *Deconstructing Supply Chain Attacks and Infiltrating a Biohacker's Mind*. Retrieved August 2025, from Black Hat: <https://www.blackhat.com/sponsor-posts/07022021-deconstructing-supply-chain-attacks-and-infiltrating-a-biohackers-mind.html>
- Boese, V. A. (2021, May). *Waves of autocratization and democratization: a rejoinder*. Retrieved August 2025, from Research Gate: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Number-of-countries-experiencing-autocratization-and-democratization-since-1900_fig1_351635550
- Bösch, F. (2025, March). *Technology Sharing & Transfer: Vertragsrecht – ein allgemeiner Überblick*. MCI Innsbruck.
- Bradford, A. (2020, March). *The Brussels Effect: How the European Union Rules the World*. Retrieved November 2024, from Columbia Law School. Faculty Books. 232.: <https://scholarship.law.columbia.edu/books/232>
- Bryant, M. (2025, June 27). *Denmark to tackle deepfakes by giving people copyright to their own features*. Retrieved August 2025, from The Guardian: <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2025/jun/27/deepfakes-denmark-copyright-law-artificial-intelligence>
- Bublitz, M.-G. e. (2024, September 25). *Implications of the novel EU AI Act for neurotechnologies Neuron, Volume 112, Issue 18, 3013 - 301*. Retrieved April 2025, from Cell Press: [https://www.cell.com/neuron/abstract/S0896-6273\(24\)00607-X?returnURL=https%3A%2F%2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com%2Fretrieve%2Fpii%2FS089662732400607X%3Fshowall%3Dtrue](https://www.cell.com/neuron/abstract/S0896-6273(24)00607-X?returnURL=https%3A%2F%2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com%2Fretrieve%2Fpii%2FS089662732400607X%3Fshowall%3Dtrue)
- Bublitz J-C. (2013) *My Mind is Mine!?* *Cognitive Liberty as a Legal Concept*. In: Hildt E, Franke AG, eds. *Cognitive Enhancement. An Interdisciplinary Perspective*. Dordrecht: Springer; p. 233–64.
- Bublitz, C. (2022, April 01). *Novel Neurorights: From Nonsense to Substance*. Retrieved September 2025, from Research Gate: Neuroethics: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12152-022-09481-3>
- Bublitz, C. &. (2024, September 25). *The new regulation of non-medical neurotechnologies in the European Union: Overview and reflection*. Retrieved April 2025, from Oxford Journal of Law and the Biosciences: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lxae021>

- Byrne, J. (2025, April 11). Understanding Medical Device Classifications: MD, IVD, AIMD, or SaMD? Retrieved May 2025, from Cognidox: <https://www.cognidox.com/blog/what-is-a-medical-device-ivd-samd>
- Cambridge University Press & Assessment. (2025). *Cambridge Dictionary*. Retrieved May 2025, from Physiological: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/physiological>
- Censys. (2024, October 10). *14,000 medical devices are online, unsecured and vulnerable*. Retrieved August 2025, from CyberScoop: <https://cyberscoop.com/medical-devices-online-health-censys/>
- Chavarriga, Ricardo J.-M. R. (2023, April). *STRATEGIC SECURITY ANALYSIS, NEUROTECHNOLOGIES: THE NEW FRONTIER FOR INTERNATIONAL GOVERNANCE*. Retrieved August 2025, from Geneva Centre for Security Policy: <https://www.gcsp.ch/sites/default/files/2024-12/ssa-2023-issue29.pdf>
- Cialdini, R. B. (1984). *Influence: The Psychology of Persuasion*. Harper Business.
- Class Central. (n.d.). Class Central: Courses, BSidesLV. Retrieved September 2025, from Neurosecurity - Where Infosec Meets Brain-Machine Interface Course: <https://www.classcentral.com/classroom/youtube-bg-neurosecurity-where-infosec-meets-brain-machine-interface-ben-d-sawyer-matt-canham-152100>
- Cody Rall MD with Techforpsych. (2023, October 28). *Best Brain Devices for 2024*. Retrieved May 2025, from YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fLtSL_z_pEE
- Cognitive Security Institute. (2025). Home. Retrieved September 2025, from Cognitive Security Institute: <https://www.cognitivesecurity.institute/join>
- Cooley (2025). News: The MIND Act: Balancing Innovation and Privacy in Neurotechnology, retrieved on October 4th, 2025 from <https://www.cooley.com/news/insight/2025/2025-09-25-the-mind-act-balancing-innovation-and-privacy-in-neurotechnology>
- Council of the European Union. (2024, September). *Council of the European Union*. Retrieved March 2025, from RESEARCH PAPER: From vision to reality. Promises and risks of Brain-Computer Interfaces: https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/fh4fw3fn/art_braincomputerinterfaces_2024_web.pdf?utm_
- CrowdStrike. (2023, November 07). *10 Types of Social Engineering Attacks and how to prevent them*. Retrieved September 2025, from CrowdStrike: <https://www.crowdstrike.com/en-us/cybersecurity-101/social-engineering/types-of-social-engineering-attacks/>
- Day, J. (2025). Fluid Interfaces. Project Alterego. Retrieved September 2025, from MIT Media Lab. Research: <https://www.media.mit.edu/projects/alterego/overview/>
- DEFCON. (2017, July 28). *Biohacking Village*. Retrieved August 2025, from DEFCON: <https://www.defconbiohackingvillage.org/>
- Draghi, Mario. (2024, September 17). *Address by Mr. Draghi – Presentation of the report on the Future of European competitiveness*. Retrieved September 2025, from European Parliament: https://commission.europa.eu/topics/eu-competitiveness/draghi-report_en#paragraph_47059

- EMOTIV. (2025). *EPOC X - 14 Channel Wireless EEG Headset*. Retrieved from EMOTIV:
https://www.emotiv.com/products/epoc-x?srsltid=AfmBOoqUih_SIH6dBx4nr9Fp275z2MVH4fp4WCUkDDy2_kXBg4zo12AV
- Emotiv. (2025). *Home*. Retrieved December 2024, from Emotiv:
https://www.emotiv.com/?srsltid=AfmBOorlVY1d3xL7s8MakZerFGF6K5yMvtf1MWr_qaxhq--0LA_w5W_F
- European Commission. (2015). *Joint Research Centre. Institute for the Protection and the Security of the Citizen., Wearable Sensors and Digital Platforms in Health: Empowering Citizens through Trusted and Trustworthy ICT Technology: TRUDI Deliverable 3.1. (Publications Office 2015)*. Retrieved April 2025, from <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2788/788525>
- European Commission. (n.d.). *Publication in accordance with Article 1(3) of Commission Decision 2000/299/EC*. Retrieved August 2025, from European Commission - Radio Equipment Directive (RED): <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/circabc-ewpp/d/d/workspace/SpacesStore/6bb8f9e4-6246-42e0-9e11-b5f39babf92d/download>
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Regulation (EC) No 1338/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council on Community statistics on public health and health and safety at work, OJ 2008 L 354*. Retrieved August 2025, from Official Journal of the EU - EUR-LEX: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008R1338>
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Directive 2014/53/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on the harmonisation of the laws of the Member States relating to the making available on the market of radio equipment and repealing Directive 1999/5/EC, OJ 2014 L 153*. Retrieved August 2025, from Official Journal of the EU - EUR-Lex: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014L0053>
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC 119 (General Data Protection Regulation), OJ 2016 L 119.* Retrieved July 2025, from EUR-Lex: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj/eng>
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Directive (EU) 2019/882 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the accessibility requirements for products and services, OJ 2019 L 151*. Retrieved September 2025, from Official Journal of the EU - EUR-LEX: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32019L0882>
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (Medical Device Regulation), OJ 2017 L 117*. Retrieved April 2025, from Official Journal of the EU - EUR-LEX: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32017R0745>
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/2346 laying down common specifications for the groups of products without an intended medical purpose*

- listed in Annex XVI to Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council on medical devices, OJ 2022 L 311. Retrieved May 2025, from Official Journal of the EU - EUR-Lex: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2022/2346/oj/eng*
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/2347 laying down rules for the application of Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards reclassification of groups of certain active products without an intended medical purpose, OJ 2022 L 311. Retrieved May 2025, from Official Journal of the EU - EUR-Lex: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2022/2347/oj/eng*
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector and amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act), OJ 2022 L 265. Retrieved September 2025, from Official Journal of the EU - EUR-LEX: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32022R1925>*
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council on a Single Market For Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act) OJ 2022 L 277. Retrieved September 2025, from Official Journal of the EU - EUR-LEX: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32022R2065>*
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Summaries of EU Legislation: Statistics on public health / health and safety at work. Retrieved August 2025, from Official Journal of the EU - EUR-LEX: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=OJ:L:2008:354:FULL>*
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Regulation (EU) 2023/988 of the European Parliament and of the Council on general product safety, amending Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 of the European Parliament and the Council, and repealing Directive 2001/95/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Directive 87/357/EEC, OJ 2023 L 135. Retrieved May 2025, from Official Journal of the EU - EUR-LEX: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32023R0988>*
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act), OJ 2024 L 1689, Retrieved July 2025, from Official Journal of the EU - EUR-Lex: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng>*
- European Parliament and of the Council. *Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 of the European Parliament and of the Council on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013 and (EU) 2019/1020 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Cyber Resilience Act), OJ 2024 L 2847. Retrieved August 2025, from Official Journal of the EU - EUR-Lex: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R2847>*

- Eyre, H. (2025, March 28). 2024 Neurotech Funding Snapshot, Slide #10. Retrieved 28 March, from Global Neurotech Summit: <https://lu.ma/8ed37s4c?tk=GZxE3R>
- Eyre, Harris (March 28th, 2025). Rice University's Baker Institute. Closing Remarks for the Global Neurotech Summit. Stepping onto the Balcony: Neurotech in the context of the Brain Economy.
- Eyre, H. (2025, March 28). Neurotechnology is Vital to the Brain Economy, Slide #9. Retrieved March 2025, from Global Neurotech Summit: <https://lu.ma/8ed37s4c?tk=GZxE3R>
- Eyre, H. (2025, March 28). Private Sector Signals, Slide #12. Retrieved March 2025, from Global Neurotech Summit: <https://lu.ma/8ed37s4c?tk=GZxE3R>
- Farahany, N. (2012). *Incriminating Thoughts*. Retrieved September 2025, from 64 Stanford Law Review 351-408: https://scholarship.law.duke.edu/faculty_scholarship/2651/
- Farahany, N. (2024). *The Battle for Your Brain: Defending the Right to Think Freely in the Age of Neurotechnology*. St. Martin's Press.
- Farahany, N. (2025, August 12). *Apple's Neural Platform Play: What BCI-HID Actually Is—and Why It Could Quietly Standardize Neurotech*. Retrieved August 2025, from Thinking Freely with Nita Farahany: https://nitafarahany.substack.com/p/apples-neural-platform-play-what?r=1183hr&utm_campaign=post&utm_medium=web&triedRedirect=true
- Farahany, N. (2025, August 20). *The Tech Titans Are Coming for Your Brain: And why the White House might let them*. Retrieved August 2025, from Stay Tuned: https://staytuned.substack.com/p/the-tech-titans-are-coming-for-your?utm_source=substack&utm_campaign=post_embed&utm_medium=email
- Frankl, V. (2006). *Man's Search For Meaning: The classic tribute to hope from the Holocaust (Originally published in 1946 as Ein Psycholog erlebt das Konzentrationslager; first English translation 1959)*. Boston, MA: Beacon Press.
- Genser, J. S. (2022, May 22). *International Human Rights Protection Gaps in the Age of Neurotechnology*. Retrieved July 2025, from Neurorights Foundation: <https://ntc.columbia.edu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/NeurorightsFoundationPUBLICAnalysis5.6.22.pdf>
- GPA. (2025, January 1). *Austrian collective agreement in the field of automatic data processing and information technology services*. Retrieved August 2025, from GPA Meine Gewerkschaft: <https://www.gpa.at/kollektivvertrag/information-und-consulting/it>
- Gulotta, C. (2024, March 27). *Direct-to-Consumer Neurotechnologies under the Framework of WTO Agreements*. Retrieved July 2025, from BioLaw Journal – Rivista di BioDiritto, n. 1/2024: <https://boa.unimib.it/retrieve/d78f5dfb-7e9e-455e-87cd-c6d9b04596cf/Gulotta-2024-Biolaw%20J-VoR.pdf>
- Hoffmann von Fallersleben. (n.d.). *Die Gedanken sind frei*. Retrieved April 2025, from Gedichte7: <https://www.gedichte7.de/die-gedanken-sind-frei.html>
- Huntington, S. P. (1991). *The third wave: Democratization in the Late Twentieth Century*. Oklahoma: Norman and London: University of Oklahoma Press.
- IBM & Ponemon Institute. (2025, July). *Cost of a Data Breach Report*. Retrieved August 2025, from IBM: <https://www.ibm.com/reports/data->

[breach?utm_medium=Email&utm_source=Newsletter&utm_content=CAAWW&utm_term=15MSC&utm_campaign=314591&utm_id=NW-Think2508011ENCTA1&mkt_tok=Mjk4LVJTRS02NTAAAAGcBLN3viYekigbvG0hq1f5JdH-68BP0Qz36YWqRWwlN7TnXLKC9Td4qTZo5J_tcywcKA](https://www.ics.ac.uk/news/2025/01/25/london-neurotech-hackathon)

- ICL Neurotech Society. (2025, January 2025). *London neurotech Hackathon (January 2025)*. Retrieved August, from ICL Neurotech Society: <https://iclneurotech.co.uk/hackathon>
- IEEE. (2023, September 22). *IEEE Standard for Health Informatics - Device Interoperability - Part 10701: Point-of-Care Medical Device Communication - Metric Provisioning by Participants in a Service-Oriented Device Connectivity (SDC) System*. (IEEE, Producer, & IEEE) Retrieved August 2025, from IEEE Std 11073-10701-2022: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10258019>
- Ienca, M. e. (2022, April 25). *Mental data protection and the GDPR*. Retrieved July 2025, from Journal of Law and the Biosciences: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jlb/ljac006>
- Ienca, M. (2015, January 01). *Neuroprivacy, neurosecurity and brain-hacking: Emerging issues in neural engineering*. Retrieved August 2025, from Bioethica Forum: DOI:10.24894/BF.2015.08015
- ISACA. (2025). *ISACA About us*. Retrieved August 2025, from ISACA Home: <https://www.isaca.org/about-us>
- ISO. (2025, May). *ISO/IEC TR 27599:2025(en) Information technology — Brain-computer interfaces — Use cases*. Retrieved August 2025, from ISO.org: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#iso:std:iso-iec:tr:27599:ed-1:v1:en>
- ISO. (n.d.). *Online Browsing Platform (OBP)*. Retrieved September 2025, from ISO: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#home>
- ISO (International Organization for Standardization). (2016). *ISO 13485 Medical Devices*. Retrieved March 2025, from ISO.org: <https://www.iso.org/iso-13485-medical-devices.html>
- Istace, T. M. (2024, May). *RESEARCH BRIEF BETWEEN SCIENCE-FACT AND SCIENCE-FICTION: INNOVATION AND ETHICS IN NEUROTECHNOLOGY*. Retrieved July 2025, from Geneva University - Faculty of Law: <https://www.geneva-academy.ch/joomlatools-files/docman-files/Between%20Science-Fact%20and%20Science-Fiction%20Innovation%20and%20Ethics%20in%20Neurotechnology.pdf>
- King Caroline, P. T.-R.-Z. (2022, September 29). *Safety of deep brain stimulation in pregnancy: A comprehensive review*. Retrieved August 2025, from Frontiers in Human Neuroscience: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2022.997552>
- Kritika, E. (2025, March 01). *Guarding the Mind's Frontier: The Unprecedented Challenge of Neurosecurity Governance*. Retrieved August 2025, from ISACA Journal: https://www.isacajournal-digital.org/isacajournal/2025_volume_2/MobilePagedArticle.action?articleId=2045383#articleId2045383
- Lomas, N. (2024, February 21). *Samphire Neuroscience is building a brain stimulating wearable for period pain*. Retrieved August 2025, from Tech Crunch: <https://techcrunch.com/2024/02/21/samphire-neuroscience/#:~:text=U,for%20period%20pain%20and%20PMS>

- Magee, P. I. (2024, September 25). *Beyond neural data: Cognitive biometrics and mental privacy*. Retrieved July 2025, from Neuron - Cell Press: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2024.09.004>
- McGinnis, P. J. (2004). *Social Theory at HBS: 'Fear of Missing Out' Is a New Disease*. Retrieved July 2025, from The Harbus, Harvard Business School newspaper: <https://www.harbus.org/post/social-theory-at-hbs-mcginnis-two-fos-1>
- Meta. (2025, September 17). *Meta Ray-Ban Display: AI Glasses With an EMG Wristband*. Retrieved September 2025, from Meta: <https://about.fb.com/news/2025/09/meta-ray-ban-display-ai-glasses-emg-wristband/>
- Mind Garden AI. (n.d.). *From Science Fiction to Reality*. Retrieved September 2025, from Mind Garden AI: <https://mindgardenai.com/blog/2024-09-11-lets-build-a-bci/>
- Neuralink. (2025). *Home*. Retrieved December, from Neuralink: <https://neuralink.com/>
- NeurotechEU Online Campus. (2025). *Home*. Retrieved September 2025, from NeurotechEU Online Campus: <https://nteucampus.org/>
- Next Mind. (2022). *Next Mind*. Retrieved April 2025, from Github Repository: <https://github.com/Snapchat/NextMind/blob/main/legal/regulatory.md>
- Novelli, C. F. (2024, November). *Generative AI in EU law: Liability, privacy, intellectual property, and cybersecurity*. Retrieved July 2025, from Science Direct: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2024.106066>.
- Noyb. (2024, April 29). *ChatGPT provides false information about people, and OpenAI can't correct it*. Retrieved August 2025, from <https://noyb.eu/en/chatgpt-provides-false-information-about-people-and-openai-cant-correct-it>
- Nuno Perez, A. e. (2023, February 14). *Sizing the brain: Segmentation and growth factors of the global neuroscience market*. Retrieved May 2025, from Deloitte Insights: <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/insights/industry/health-care/global-neuroscience-market-investment-report.html>
- Oosterwijk S, L. K. (2012, June 5). *States of mind: Emotions, body feelings, and thoughts share distributed neural networks*. Retrieved July 2025, from National Library of Medicine: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3453527/>
- Opoku Adusei, G. O. (2015, October 19). *Medical Device Classification: Consult the Guidance and if in Doubt Ask the Authorities*. Retrieved May 2025, from LinkedIn.com: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/medical-device-classification-consult-guidance-doubt-gabriel/>
- Our World in Data. (2025). *Democracy index – Economist Intelligence Unit*. Retrieved August 2025, from Economist Intelligence Unit (2006-2024): https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/democracy-index-eiu?tab=table&time=earliest..2024&country=OWID_OCE~OWID_EUR~OWID_SAM~OWID_NAM~OWID_ASI~OWID_AFR&tableFilter=continents
- Österreichischer Bundesverband für Psychotherapie. (n.d.). *Psychotherapiegesetz*. Retrieved March 2025, from ÖBVP: <https://www.psychotherapie.at/psychotherapeutinnen/rechtliches/psychotherapiegesetz>
- Patrick Magee, e. a. (2024, September 25). *Beyond neural data: Cognitive biometrics and mental privacy*. Retrieved July 2025, from Neuron - Cell Press: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2024.09.004>

- Poupyrev, I. (2019, October 3). *A smarter wardrobe with Jacquard by Google*. Retrieved April 2025, from Google Blogs: <https://blog.google/products/atap/smarter-wardrobe-jacquard-google/>
- Publications Office of the European Union. (2025, September 16). *The Draghi report on EU competitiveness*. Retrieved September 2025, from European Commission: https://commission.europa.eu/topics/eu-competitiveness/draghi-report_en
- Pycroft L, Boccard SG, Owen SLF, Stein JF, Fitzgerald JJ, Green AL, Aziz TZ. Brainjacking: Implant Security Issues in Invasive Neuromodulation. *World Neurosurg*. 2016; 92:454–62. DOI:10.1016/j.wneu.2016.05.010
- R., Briana. (2024, September 7). *Exploring Google Jacquard: Where Fashion Meets Technology*. Retrieved April 2025, from Medium: <https://medium.com/@cyber-news/exploring-google-jacquard-where-fashion-meets-technology-f235645b8ef8>
- Reed, J. (2024, February 04). *Neuralink: Can Musk's brain technology change the world?* Retrieved from BBC: <https://www.bbc.com/news/health-68169082>
- Ruiz-Vanoye, J. A.-P.-G.-P.-C.-P.-A.-F.-M. (2024, December). *Brain Data Security and Neurosecurity: Technological advances, Ethical dilemmas, and Philosophical perspectives*. Retrieved August 2025, from International Journal of Combinatorial Optimization Problems and Informatics: <https://doi.org/10.61467/2007.1558.2024.v15i5.555>
- Sinha, S. (2025, August 1). *Neuralink leap: Elon Musk's brain chip to be tested on paralyzed patients in UK*. Retrieved August 2025, from Interesting Engineering: <https://interestingengineering.com/innovation/neuralinks-first-clinical-study-in-britain>
- Solis, B. (2025, March 10). *Mindshift or Die! How to Stay Ahead in the Age of AI and Disruption*. Retrieved September 2025, from [www.briansolis.com](https://briansolis.com/tag/digital-darwinism/): <https://briansolis.com/tag/digital-darwinism/>
- Soller, H. (2025, June 23). *The Year of Quantum: From concept to reality in 2025*. Retrieved August 2025, from McKinsey.com: <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/mckinsey-digital/our-insights/the-year-of-quantum-from-concept-to-reality-in-2025>
- Somers, F. (2022, June 10). *BCIs, Big Tech & Even Bigger Data: Why does the emergence of neurotechnologies in the consumer domain threaten the European human rights framework? And how these threats should be mitigated*. Retrieved April 2025, from Research Gate: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/381769982_BCIs_Big_Tech_and_Even_Bigger_Data_Why_does_the_emergence_of_neurotechnologies_in_the_consumer_domain_threaten_the_European_human_rights_framework_And_how_these_threats_should_be_mitigated?enrichId=rgreq-
- Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. (2020, September 11). *Dualism*. Retrieved May 2025, from <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/dualism/#MinBod>
- Stanford Report. (2025, August 14). *Scientists develop interface that 'reads' thoughts from speech-impaired patients*. Retrieved from Stanford Report: <https://news.stanford.edu/stories/2025/08/study-inner-speech-decoding-device-patients-paralysis>
- Steindl, E. (2024, February 10). *Consumer neuro devices within EU product safety law: Are we prepared for big tech ante portas?* . Retrieved May 2025, from Computer Law & Security Review: The International Journal of Technology Law and Practice :

- <https://pdf.sciencedirectassets.com/271884/1-s2.0-S0267364923X00053/1-s2.0-S0267364924000128/main.pdf?X-Amz-Security-Token=IQoJb3JpZ2luX2VjEFcaCXVzLWVhc3QtMSJGMEQCIFXy6HZ7zEpdrdRr3ONN8MDg1st7jz4jnGgMrkRaOzMUaIA1jBek02Xfq8RZgLZzX2BCbOHSPxVwK6fG%2FTMhcSNtzS>
- Strecher, V. J. (2016). *Life on Purpose: How Living for What Matters Most Changes Everything*. HarperOne.
- STWS. (2024). *NextMind: Brain-sensing wearable for real-time device control*. Retrieved April 2025, from STWS: <https://stws.co/directory-annual/listing/nextmind/>
- Swetlitz, I. (2025, August 15). *Sam Altman's Brain Chip Venture Is Mulling Gene Therapy Approach*. Retrieved August 2025, from Bloomberg: <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2025-08-15/sam-altman-brain-chip-venture-is-mulling-gene-therapy-approach?accessToken=eyJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IkpXVCJ9.eyJzb3VyY2UiOiJlTlR5Y3JpYmVvR2lmdGVkQXJ0aWNsZSIsImhhdCI6MTc1NTI3Nm0NCwiZXhwIjoxNzU1ODgyMTQ0>
- The Centre for Neurotechnology and Law. (2024). *What is Neurotechnology?* Retrieved February 2025, from: <https://www.neurotechlaw.com/resources>
- The Centre for Neurotechnology and Law. (2025, February). *Home*. Retrieved from The Centre for Neurotechnology and Law: <https://www.neurotechlaw.com/>
- The Neurorights Foundation Newsletter. (2025, September). *Home*. Retrieved September 2025, from The Neurorights Foundation Newsletter: <https://neurorightsfoundation.org/news>
- The Neurorights Foundation. *News*. (2025, July). Retrieved from The Neurorights Foundation: <https://neurorightsfoundation.org/news>
- Trotter, W. (1916). *Instincts of the Herd in Peace and War*. Retrieved July 2025, from Gutenberg: <https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/53453>
- UNESCO. (2024, August 27). *FIRST DRAFT OF A RECOMMENDATION ON THE ETHICS OF NEUROTECHNOLOGY (REVISED VERSION)*. Retrieved July 2025, from UNESCO: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000391074>
- UNESCO. (2024, September 23). *Preliminary Report on the first draft of the Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology*. Retrieved July 2025, from UNESCO: <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/preliminary-report-first-draft-recommendation-ethics-neurotechnology>
- UNESCO (2021) Report of the International Bioethics Committee on the Ethical Issues of Neurotechnology. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000383559>
- UNESCO. (2024, April 17). *TOWARDS A DRAFT TEXT OF A RECOMMENDATION ON THE ETHICS OF NEUROTECHNOLOGY*. Retrieved July 2025, from UNESCO: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000389438>
- UNESCO. (2023). *UNESCO*. Retrieved March 2025, from Unveiling the Neurotechnology Landscape. Scientific Advancements Innovations and Major Trends: <https://doi.org/10.54678/OCBM4164>
- University of Nottingham. (2025, June 26). *Scientists win award for portable brain imaging breakthrough*. Retrieved from University of Nottingham:

<https://www.nottingham.ac.uk/news/scientists-win-award-for-portable-brain-imaging-breakthrough>

University of York, Europe Campus, CITY College. (2025, May 19-23). Neuroimaging Techniques.

Retrieved May 2025, from 2025. Neuroscience Week 2025 Hybrid Event (Online & In-Person):

<https://york-ac->

[uk.zoom.us/j/97064735526?tk=I1e2OjJYbLiAS2AgOp5SxYClATm3zOCv0ijfBLbN0Xs.DQc](https://york-ac-uk.zoom.us/j/97064735526?tk=I1e2OjJYbLiAS2AgOp5SxYClATm3zOCv0ijfBLbN0Xs.DQc)

[AAAAWmYJTJhYxOTFHZHB4clE1S2pzN3RtZEdaWm93AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA](https://york-ac-uk.zoom.us/j/97064735526?tk=I1e2OjJYbLiAS2AgOp5SxYClATm3zOCv0ijfBLbN0Xs.DQc)

[AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA](https://york-ac-uk.zoom.us/j/97064735526?tk=I1e2OjJYbLiAS2AgOp5SxYClATm3zOCv0ijfBLbN0Xs.DQc)

U.S. Senate Committee on Commerce, Science, & Transportation (2025), Press Release: Sens. Cantwell,

Schumer, Markey Introduce Legislation to Shield Americans' Brain Data From Exploitation,

accessed on October 4th, 2025 at [https://www.commerce.senate.gov/2025/9/sens-cantwell-](https://www.commerce.senate.gov/2025/9/sens-cantwell-schumer-markey-introduce-legislation-to-shield-americans-brain-data-from-exploitation)

[schumer-markey-introduce-legislation-to-shield-americans-brain-data-from-exploitation](https://www.commerce.senate.gov/2025/9/sens-cantwell-schumer-markey-introduce-legislation-to-shield-americans-brain-data-from-exploitation)

VEM Medical. (n.d.). *Guide to Medical Device Classification*. Retrieved May 2025, from VEM Medical:

<https://vem-medical.com/medical-device-classification/>

Wei, B. C. (2025). *Neural Personal Information and Its Legal Protection Evidence from China*. Retrieved

April 2025, from Oxford Journal of Law and the Biosciences: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lsaf006>

World Economic Forum. (2025, January 13). *4 imperatives for improving mental health care in 2025:*

Leveraging AI and technological advancements. Retrieved August 2025, from Wellbeing and

Mental Health: [https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/01/4-imperatives-for-improving-mental-](https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/01/4-imperatives-for-improving-mental-health-care-in-2025/)

[health-care-in-2025/](https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/01/4-imperatives-for-improving-mental-health-care-in-2025/)

World Economic Forum. (2025, January 8). *Jobs and the Future of Work Future of Jobs Report 2025: The*

jobs of the future – and the skills you need to get them / Skills workers need to thrive. Retrieved

August 2025, from World Economic Forum: [https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/01/future-](https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/01/future-of-jobs-report-2025-jobs-of-the-future-and-the-skills-you-need-to-get-them/#:~:text=Roundin%20out%20the%20top%2010,evolving%20demands%2C%20the%20re)

[of-jobs-report-2025-jobs-of-the-future-and-the-skills-you-need-to-get-](https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/01/future-of-jobs-report-2025-jobs-of-the-future-and-the-skills-you-need-to-get-them/#:~:text=Roundin%20out%20the%20top%2010,evolving%20demands%2C%20the%20re)

[them/#:~:text=Roundin%20out%20the%20top%2010,evolving%20demands%2C%20the%20re-](https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/01/future-of-jobs-report-2025-jobs-of-the-future-and-the-skills-you-need-to-get-them/#:~:text=Roundin%20out%20the%20top%2010,evolving%20demands%2C%20the%20re)

[port%20says.](https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/01/future-of-jobs-report-2025-jobs-of-the-future-and-the-skills-you-need-to-get-them/#:~:text=Roundin%20out%20the%20top%2010,evolving%20demands%2C%20the%20re)

World Economic Forum. (2025, January 7). *The Future of Jobs Report 2025*. Retrieved from World

Economic Forum: <https://www.weforum.org/publications/the-future-of-jobs-report-2025/>

World Health Organization. (2022, June 16). *World mental health report: Transforming mental health for*

all - executive summary. Retrieved August 2025, from WHO.int:

<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240050860>

Yuste, R. G. (2017). *Four ethical priorities for neurotechnologies and AI*. Retrieved August 2025, from

Nature: <https://doi.org/10.1038/551159a>

Zada, Z. e. (2024, September 25). *A shared model-based linguistic space for transmitting our thoughts*

from brain to brain in natural conversations. Retrieved July 2025, from Neuron - Cell Press

Volume 112, Issue 18, 3211 - 3222.e5: <https://www.cell.com/neuron/fulltext/S0896->

[6273\(24\)00460-](https://www.cell.com/neuron/fulltext/S0896-6273(24)00460-4?returnURL=https%3A%2F%2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com%2Fretrieve%2Fpii%2FS0896627324004604%3Fshowall%3Dtrue)

[4?returnURL=https%3A%2F%2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com%2Fretrieve%2Fpii%2FS089662732](https://www.cell.com/neuron/fulltext/S0896-6273(24)00460-4?returnURL=https%3A%2F%2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com%2Fretrieve%2Fpii%2FS0896627324004604%3Fshowall%3Dtrue)

[4004604%3Fshowall%3Dtrue](https://www.cell.com/neuron/fulltext/S0896-6273(24)00460-4?returnURL=https%3A%2F%2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com%2Fretrieve%2Fpii%2FS0896627324004604%3Fshowall%3Dtrue)

Initial Survey of Literature:

- Ababkova, M. Y., Pokrovskaya, N. N., & Trostinskaya, I. R. (2018). Neuro-technologies for knowledge transfer and experience communication. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences*.
- Adomaitis, L., & Grinbaum, A. (2024). Neurotechnologies, ethics, and the limits of free will. *Integrative Psychological and Behavioral Science*, 58(3), 894-907.
- Baroni, M. J. L. (2024). Fourth Generation Human Rights in View of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. *Philosophies*, 9(2), 39.
- Beck, C., Chantre, L., Jacobson, M., Whitty, E., Kumar, A. D. U., Polizzotto, L., & Chavarriaga, S. D. R. (2023). Developing a Web-Based Neurotechnology Standards Dashboard.
- Berger, S., & Rossi, F. AI and Neurotechnology: Learning from AI Ethics to Address an Expanded Ethics Landscape The merging of machine, body, and psyche is on the horizon due to the technological advancements enabled by neuroscience and AI.
- Berger, S., & Rossi, F. (2021, August). The Future of AI Ethics and the Role of Neurotechnology. In *Workshop on Adverse Impacts and Collateral Effects of Artificial Intelligence Technologies*. CEUR-WS.
- Bhidayasiri, R. (2024). The grand challenge at the frontiers of neurotechnology and its emerging clinical applications. *Frontiers in Neurology*, 15, 1314477.
- Bibri, S. E. (2023). The metaverse as a virtual model of platform urbanism: its converging AIoT, XRReality, neurotech, and nanobiotech and their applications, challenges, and risks. *Smart Cities*, 6(3), 1345-1384.
- Blitz, M. J., & Barfield, W. (2023). Memory enhancement and brain-computer Interface devices: technological possibilities and constitutional challenges. In *Policy, identity, and Neurotechnology: The Neuroethics of brain-computer interfaces* (pp. 207-231). Springer International Publishing.
- Bothoff, S. B. (2022). *Mental Privacy in the Age of Neurotechnology* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Bowman, D. M., Garden, H., Stroud, C., & Winickoff, D. E. (2018). The neurotechnology and society interface: Responsible innovation in an international context. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 5(1), 1-12.
- Brandt-Rauf, P. W., & Ayaz, H. (2024). Occupational Health and Neuroergonomics: The Future of Wearable Neurotechnologies at the Workplace. *Journal of occupational and environmental medicine*, 66(6), 456-460.
- Brindley, T., & Giordano, D. J. (2014). international standards for intellectual property protection of neuroscience and neurotechnology: neuroethical legal and social (NELS) considerations in light of globalization. *Stanf. J. Law Sci. Policy SJLSP*, 7, 33.
- Cabrera, L., & Carter-Johnson, J. (2020). Emergent Neurotechnologies and Challenges to Responsibility Frameworks. *Akron L. Rev.*, 54, 1.

- Chavarriga, R., Rickli, J. M., & Mantellassi, F. (2023). Neurotechnologies: the new frontier for international governance.
- Coin, A., & Dubljević, V. (2023). An Introduction to Policy, Identity, and Neurotechnology: The Neuroethics of Brain–Computer Interfaces. In *Policy, Identity, and Neurotechnology: The Neuroethics of Brain–Computer Interfaces* (pp. 1-7). Springer International Publishing.
- Colnago, C. D. O. S., & Shiner, B. (2021). A Distinct Right to Freedom of Thought in South America: The Jurisprudence of the Inter-American Court of Human Rights, Neurotechnology and the Application of Bioethics Principles. *European Journal of Comparative Law and Governance*, 8(2-3), 245-270.
- Confortini, C. (2025). Emotions recognition systems and data economy. In *Human Vulnerability in Interaction with AI in European Private Law*. Springer.
- Cornejo-Plaza, M. I., Cippitani, R., & Pasquino, V. (2024). Chilean Supreme Court ruling on the protection of brain activity: neurorights, personal data protection, and neurodata. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, 1330439.
- Council of Europa. (2024). *Human Rights and Biomedicine*, Bioethics, retrieved on November 28th, 2024, from <https://www.coe.int/en/web/bioethics>
- Council of Europa. (2024). *Human Rights and Biomedicine, Emerging technologies*, retrieved on November 28th, 2024, from [https://www.coe.int/en/web/bioethics/emerging-technologies#%2211067078%22:\[0\]](https://www.coe.int/en/web/bioethics/emerging-technologies#%2211067078%22:[0])
- Council of Europa. (2024). *Human Rights and Biomedicine, Neurotechnologies* , retrieved on November 28th, 2024, from <https://www.coe.int/en/web/bioethics/assessing-the-relevance-and-sufficiency-of-the-existing-human-rights-framework-to-address-the-issues-raised-by-the-applications-of-neurotechnologies>
- Dei Lincei, A. N. (2024). Brain-Computer interfaces: Opportunities and Challenges. Toward A Reasoned Use of Neurotechnologies.
- Discretionary, T. (2020). Emergent Neurotechnologies and Challenges To Responsibility Frameworks. *Akron Law Review*, 54(1).
- Drew, L. (2019). The ethics of brain-computer interfaces. *Nature*, 571(7766), S19-S19.
- Eaton, S. E. (2024). Future-proofing integrity in the age of artificial intelligence and neurotechnology: prioritizing human rights, dignity, and equity. *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 20(1), 21.
- Erden, Y. J., & Brey, P. (2023). Neurotechnology and ethics guidelines for human enhancement: The case of the hippocampal cognitive prosthesis. *Artificial organs*, 47(8), 1235-1241.
- European Commission (2024), Commission takes action to boost biotechnology and biomanufacturing in the EU, retrieved on March 27th, 2025, from https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space_en
- European Commission (2024), European Health Data Space (EHDS) retrieved on December 22, 2024, from https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space_en
- European Commission. New Regulations, retrieved on March 9th, 2025, from https://health.ec.europa.eu/medical-devices-sector/new-regulations_en

- European Union. EUR-Lex. Verordnung (EU) 2017/745 des Europäischen Parlaments und des Rates vom 5. April 2017 über Medizinprodukte, zur Änderung der Richtlinie 2001/83/EG, der Verordnung (EG) Nr. 178/2002 und der Verordnung (EG) Nr. 1223/2009 und zur Aufhebung der Richtlinien 90/385/EWG und 93/42/EWG des Rates (Text von Bedeutung für den EWR.), retrieved on March 9th, 2025 from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/de/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32017R0745>
- Europäische Verbraucherzentrum (2024). Your EU rights regarding legal guarantee and warranty, retrieved on March 9th, 2025 from <https://europakonsument.at/en/your-eu-rights-regarding-legal-guarantee-and-warranty/68355>
- Faltus, T., Freise, J., Fluck, C., & Zillmann, H. (2023). Ethics and regulation of neuronal optogenetics in the European Union. *Pflügers Archiv-European Journal of Physiology*, 475(12), 1505-1517.
- Fauzan, N. (2015). Neurotechnology for Special Needs Children. *European Journal of Social Science Education and Research*, 2(3), 134-147.
- Federal Chancellor Republic of Austria. *Bioethics Commission*, retrieved on November 28th, 2024, from <https://www.bundeskanzleramt.gv.at/en/topics/bioethics-commission.html>
- Federal Ministry Republic of Austria (2021). Telecommunications Act 2021, retrieved on March 10th, 2025, from <https://www.bundeskanzleramt.gv.at/en/topics/bioethics-commission.html>
- Field, R. I. (2023). The data we leave behind: Limits of legal protections for neurotechnology and genomic data. *Drexel L. Rev.*, 15, 769.
- Filipova, I. A. (2021). Artificial intelligence and neurotechnologies: In need for constitutional and legal regulation. *Lex Russica*, 74(9), 119-130.
- Filipova, I. A. (2022). Neurotechnologies in law and law enforcement: past, present and future. *Pravoprimerenie= Law Enforcement Review*, 6(2), 32-49.
- Fonseca, D. M. D. B. (2023). Brain-Computer Interfaces and The Decoding Of Thoughts As Personal Data Of The Mind.
- Frahm, N., Doezema, T., & Pfoth, S. (2022). Fixing technology with society: The coproduction of democratic deficits and responsible innovation at the OECD and the European Commission. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 47(1), 174-216.
- Frahm, N. M. (2022). Soft Constitutions: Co-Producing Neuro-Innovation and Society in the US, EU, and OECD (Doctoral dissertation, Technische Universität München).
- Fukushi, T. (2024). East Asian perspective of responsible research and innovation in neurotechnology. *IBRO Neuroscience Reports*, 16, 582-597.
- Gardner, J., & Williams, C. (2015). Responsible research and innovation: A manifesto for empirical ethics?. *Clinical ethics*, 10(1-2), 5-12.
- Gatt, L., Caggiano, I. A., Gaeta, M. C., & Mollo, A. A. (2022, October). BCI devices and their legal compliance: A prototype tool for its evaluation and measurement. In 2022 IEEE International Conference on Metrology for Extended Reality, Artificial Intelligence and Neural Engineering (MetroXRINE) (pp. 551-556). IEEE.
- Genser, J., Damianos, S., & Yuste, R. (2024). Safeguarding Brain Data: Assessing the Privacy Practices of Consumer Neurotechnology Companies.

- Ghezzi, D. (2023). Engineering materials for neurotechnology. *Advanced Engineering Materials*, 25(9), 2201412.
- Giordano, J. (2015). Conditions for consent to the use of neurotechnology: a preparatory neuroethical approach to risk assessment and reduction. *AJOB Neuroscience*, 6(4), 12-14.
- Goering, S., & Yuste, R. (2016). On the necessity of ethical guidelines for novel neurotechnologies. *Cell*, 167(4), 882-885.
- Guerrero, F. (2024). Neurorights: A New Legal and Ethical Frontier. *Multidisciplinary & Health Education Journal*, 6(1), 979-991.
- Gulotta, C. (2024). The Challenges of Neuroenhancement: Comparative Legal Perspectives from US, EU, and Japan. *Direct-to-Consumer Neurotechnologies for Cognitive Enhancement in the European Union: The Legal Framework*.
- Gunnarsdottir, K., Chadwick, R., Hughes, J., Lewis, J. T., O'Connor, A., & Stephens, N. (2012). Cesagen response to Nuffield Council on bioethics consultation on novel neurotechnologies: intervening in the brain.
- Helbing, D., & Ienca, M. (2022). Why converging technologies need international regulation. Available at SSRN 4183791.
- Higgins, N., Gardner, J., & Carter, A. (2022). Recognizing a plurality of industry perspectives in the responsible innovation of neurotechnologies. *AJOB neuroscience*, 13(1), 70-72.
- Hurley, M. E., Sonig, A., Herrington, J., Storch, E. A., Lázaro-Muñoz, G., Blumenthal-Barby, J., & Kostick-Quenet, K. (2024). Ethical considerations for integrating multimodal computer perception and neurotechnology. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 18, 1332451.
- Ienca, M., & Scheibner, J. (2020). What is neurohacking? Defining the conceptual, ethical and legal boundaries. In *Developments in Neuroethics and Bioethics* (Vol. 3, pp. 203-231). Academic Press.
- Ienca, M., Jotterand, F., & Elger, B. S. (2018). From healthcare to warfare and reverse: How should we regulate dual-use neurotechnology?. *Neuron*, 97(2), 269-274.
- Ienca, M., Fins, J. J., Jox, R. J., Jotterand, F., Voienky, S., Andorno, R., ... & Kellmeyer, P. (2022). Towards a governance framework for brain data. *Neuroethics*, 15(2), 20.
- Ienca, M., & Andorno, R. (2017). Towards new human rights in the age of neuroscience and neurotechnology. *Life sciences, society and policy*, 13, 1-27.
- Ienca, M. Why Converging Technologies Need International Regulation.
- Inglese, S., & Lavazza, A. (2021). What should we do with people who cannot or do not want to be protected from neurotechnological threats?. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 15, 703092.
- International Bioethics Committee. (2022). Ethical issues of neurotechnology.
- International Journal of Business and Social Science (2013). Applications and Issues in the Fields of Nanotechnology, Information Technology, Neurotechnology, and Biotechnology, retrieved on March 17th, 2025 from <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=2409424222e2821119a306ee0674e095e24cabd1>
- Intersoft Consulting. Artificial Intelligence Act, retrieved on March 9th, 2025, from <https://ai-act-law.eu/>

- Intersoft Consulting. General Data Protection Regulation, retrieved on March 9th, 2025, from <https://gdpr-info.eu/>
- Islind, A. S., Yucesoy, C. A., & Aras, N. The European University of Brain and Technology.
- Istace, T. (2024). Human rights law: an incomplete but flexible framework to protect the human mind against neurotechnological intrusions. *Law, Innovation and Technology*, 16(1), 309-340.
- Istace, T. (2022). Neurorights: The debate about new legal safeguards to protect the mind. *Issues L. & Med.*, 37, 95.
- Istace, T. (2023). Protecting the mental realm: What does human rights law bring to the table?. *Netherlands Quarterly of Human Rights*, 41(4), 214-234.
- Jotterand, F., & Ienca, M. (Eds.). (2021). *Artificial Intelligence in Brain and Mental Health: Philosophical, Ethical & Policy Issues*.
- Jusline, retrieved on March 9th, 2025 from <https://www.jusline.at/>
- Kendiukhov, I. What Prevents Neurotech From Going Big?.
- Khan, S., Cole, D., & Ekbia, H. (2024). Autonomy and Free Thought in Brain-Computer Interactions: Review of Legal Precedent for Precautionary Regulation of Consumer Products. *UC L. Sci. & Tech. J.*, 15, 95.
- Khan, S. O. (2024). *Institutional Analysis of Consumer Neurotechnology Regulation: Mediating Third-Party Autonomy* (Doctoral dissertation, Indiana University).
- Kop, Mauritz, et al. (December 6, 2024) *A Brief Quantum Medicine Policy Guide*, retrieved on December 22th, 2024, from Harvard Law <https://blog.petrieflom.law.harvard.edu/2024/12/06/a-brief-quantum-medicine-policy-guide/>
- Kop, Mauritz, et al. (December 5, 2024) *How Quantum Technologies May Be Integrated Into Healthcare, What Regulators Should Consider*, retrieved on December 22th, 2024, from Stanford Law School <https://law.stanford.edu/publications/how-quantum-technologies-may-be-integrated-into-healthcare-what-regulators-should-consider/>
- Kop, Mauritz, et al. (April 4, 2024) *EU and US Regulatory Challenges Facing AI Health Care Innovator Firms*, retrieved on December 22th, 2024, from Harvard Law <https://blog.petrieflom.law.harvard.edu/2024/04/04/eu-and-us-regulatory-challenges-facing-ai-health-care-innovator-firms/>
- Kosal, M., & Putney, J. (2023). Neurotechnology and international security: Predicting commercial and military adoption of brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) in the United States and China. *Politics and the Life Sciences*, 42(1), 81-103.
- Larrivee, D., French, J., Antonietti, A., McKinney, Z., Prins, N. W., Soldado-Magraner, J., ... & Cabrera, L. Y. (2024). Examining funders' roles in responsible research and innovation of medical neurotechnology. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 11(1), 2381758.
- Latini, S., & Crepax, T. (2020). To the edge of data protection: How brain information can push the boundaries of sensitivity.
- Laurie, G. (2014). *Novel Neurotechnologies: Intervening on the Brain*.
- Levin, D. (2023). Are You out of Your Mind? Neurotechnologies and The Making of Disembodied Agency. *Berkeley Tech. LJ*, 38, 231.

- Lighthart, S. (2022). Coercive brain-reading in criminal justice: An analysis of European human rights law.
- Lighthart, S., Douglas, T., Bublitz, C., Kooijmans, T., & Meynen, G. (2021). Forensic brain-reading and mental privacy in European Human Rights Law: Foundations and challenges. *Neuroethics*, 14, 191-203.
- Lighthart, S., Ienca, M., Meynen, G., Molnar-Gabor, F., Andorno, R., Bublitz, C., ... & Kellmeyer, P. (2023). Minding rights: Mapping ethical and legal foundations of 'neurorights'. *Cambridge quarterly of healthcare ethics*, 32(4), 461-481.
- Lighthart, S., Douglas, T., Bublitz, C., & Meynen, G. (2019). The Future of Neuroethics and the Relevance of the Law. *AJOB neuroscience*, 10(3), 120-121.
- Liv, N., & Greenbaum, D. (2024). Integrating Mental Privacy within Data Protection Laws: Addressing the Complexities of Neurotechnology and the Interdependence of Human Rights. *AJOB neuroscience*, 15(2), 151-153.
- Lopez, R. (2013). Applications and issues in the fields of nanotechnology, information technology, neurotechnology, and biotechnology. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4(8).
- Lynch, Z. (2006). Neuropolicy (2005 2035): Converging Technologies Enable Neurotechnology, Creating New Ethical Dilemmas. In *Managing nano-bio-info-cogno innovations* (pp. 173-191). Springer Netherlands.
- Mathieson, K., Denison, T., & Winkworth-Smith, C. (2021). A transformative roadmap for neurotechnology in the UK. KTN Innovation Networks. Available from: A transformative roadmap for neurotechnology in the UK-Innovate UK KTN (ktn-uk.org)[accessed June 2022].
- Mathieson, K., Denison, T., & Winkworth-Smith, C. (2020). Towards a UK neurotechnology strategy. KTN Innovation Networks. Available from: Towards a UK Neurotechnology Strategy-KTN Publishes New Report-Innovate UK KTN (ktn-uk.org)[accessed June 2022].
- Meynen, G., Van de Pol, N., Tesink, V., & Lighthart, S. (2023). Neurotechnology to reduce recidivism: Ethical and legal challenges. *Handbook of Clinical Neurology*, 197, 265-276.
- Midha, S., Wilson, M. L., & Sharples, S. (2022, June). Ethical concerns and perceptions of consumer neurotechnology from lived experiences of mental workload tracking. In *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency* (pp. 564-573).
- Miscia, M. (2021). *Neurotechnologies and self-discovery: on the relevance of article 8 of the ECHR to "neuro-inclusivity"*.
- Muhl, E., & Andorno, R. (2023). Neurosurveillance in the workplace: do employers have the right to monitor employees' minds?. *Frontiers in Human Dynamics*, 5, 1245619.
- Muñoz, J. M., Marinaro, J. Á., Iglesias, J. A., Sánchez, M., Monti, N., Colombara, C., & Girardi, G. (2024). Effects of the first successful lawsuit against a consumer neurotechnology company for violating brain data privacy. *Nature Biotechnology*, 1-2.
- Muñoz, J. M., & Marinaro, J. Á. (2023). Neurorights as reconceptualized human rights. *Frontiers in Political Science*, 5, 1322922.
- Nag, S., & Thakor, N. V. (2016). Implantable neurotechnologies: electrical stimulation and applications. *Medical & biological engineering & computing*, 54, 63-76.

- Nakazawa, E., Fukushi, T., Tachibana, K., Uehara, R., Arie, F., Akter, N., ... & Sadato, N. (2022). The way forward for neuroethics in Japan: a review of five topics surrounding present challenges. *Neuroscience Research*, 183, 7-16.
- National Library of Medicine (2019). PubMed Central. Cognitive computational neuroscience, retrieved on March 17th, 2025 from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6706072/>
- National Library of Medicine (2020). PubMed Central. Is the European Data Protection Regulation sufficient to deal with emerging data concerns relating to neurotechnology?, retrieved on March 10th, 2025 from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34386243/>
- National Library of Medicine (2023). PubMed Central. Brain-computer interface: trend, challenges, and threats, retrieved on March 16th, 2025 from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10403483/>
- National Library of Medicine (2024). PubMed Central. Several inaccurate or erroneous conceptions and misleading propaganda about brain-computer interfaces, retrieved on March 16th, 2025 from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11004276/pdf/fnhum-18-1391550.pdf>
- Nawrot, O., Szudejko, P., & Vachev, V. (2024). The interior castle of conscience vs. new human rights in the age of neuroscience and neurotechnology. *The International Journal of Human Rights*, 28(2), 177-196.
- Neuwirth, R. J. (2022). The EU artificial intelligence act: regulating subliminal AI systems.
- Okechukwu, A. S. (2024). Neuro-Rights as A New Frontier of Human Rights: A Case Of Recognition And Protection. Alex-Ekwueme Federal University Faculty of Law Ll. B Projects.
- on Neuroscience, F., Disorders, N. S., & National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2018, July). Workshop Agenda. In *Neuroforensics: Exploring the Legal Implications of Emerging Neurotechnologies: Proceedings of a Workshop*. National Academies Press (US).
- O'Shaughnessy, M. R., Johnson, W. G., Tournas, L. N., Rozell, C. J., & Rommelfanger, K. S. (2023). Neuroethics guidance documents: principles, analysis, and implementation strategies. *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, 10(2), lsad025.
- PALAZZANI, L. (2024). *Neuroscientific Research, Neurotechnologies and Minors: Ethical Aspects*. *Neuroethics and Cultural Diversity*, 287-303.
- Panasenko, S. V. (2019). Role and importance of neurotechnologies in development of Russian Economy. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences*.
- Petrovici, M. A. (2023). The coming decade of digital brain research-A vision for neuroscience at the intersection of technology and computing.
- Pillay, T. (2024). Rethinking the right to freedom of thought: on drug policy, neurotechnology, and the case for cognitive liberty. *The International Journal of Human Rights*, 1-27.
- Piovesan, F., & Morales Antoniazzi, M. (2024). DIGITICCAL. Human Rights and New Technologies: The Contribution of the Inter-American System. *Human Rights and New Technologies: The Contribution of the Inter-American System*.
- Pokrovskaja, N., Margulyan, Y., Lvin, Y., & Bulatetskaia, A. (2020, September). Neuro-technologies and fuzzy logic for intellectual capital evaluation in education and business. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 940, No. 1, p. 012090). IOP Publishing.

- RADU, R. (2024). Neurotechnologies and the future of internet governance. European University Institute.
- Rainey, S., Bublitz, J. C., Maslen, H., & Thornton, H. (2019). Data as a cross-cutting dimension of ethical importance in direct-to-consumer neurotechnologies. *AJOB neuroscience*, 10(4), 180-182.
- Rainey, S., Martin, S., Christen, A., Mégevand, P., & Fourneter, E. (2020). Brain recording, mind-reading, and neurotechnology: ethical issues from consumer devices to brain-based speech decoding. *Science and engineering ethics*, 26, 2295-2311.
- Rainey, S., & Dalese, P. (2024). An alternative focus on data in the neurorights discussion—Lessons from Brazil [version 2; peer review].
- Rechtsinformationssystem des Bundes (2025). Bundesrecht konsolidiert: Gesamte Rechtsvorschrift für Allgemeines bürgerliches Gesetzbuch, retrieved on March 9th, 2025 from <https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10001622>
- Rickli, J. M., & Ienca, M. (2021). The security and military implications of neurotechnology and artificial intelligence. *Clinical Neurotechnology Meets Artificial Intelligence: Philosophical, Ethical, Legal and Social Implications*, 197-214.
- Robinson, J. T., Rommelfanger, K. S., Anikeeva, P. O., Etienne, A., French, J., Gelinis, J., ... & Picard, R. (2022). Building a culture of responsible neurotech: Neuroethics as socio-technical challenges. *Neuron*, 110(13), 2057-2062.
- Ross Dawson. 7 leading Brain-Computer Interface Companies and their current and prospective products, retrieved on March 10th, 2025 from <https://rossdawson.com/futurist/companies-creating-future/leading-brain-computer-interface-companies-bci/>
- San José, D. G. (2024). Artificial Intelligence and Neurorights: Lessons Learned for Regulation. *The Discourse of Biorights: European Perspectives*, 109, 117.
- Schulz, D., Lillo-Navarro, C., Slors, M., Hrabčzy, A., & Reuter, M. (2024). Understanding societal challenges: a NeurotechEU perspective. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 18, 1330470.
- Shein, E. (2022). Neurotechnology and the law. *Communications of the ACM*, 65(8), 16-18.
- Sirodova, T. A. (2020). Methodological aspects of regulation of neuroresearch and neurotechnologies in neuroethics.
- Steneck, N. H. Remarks to the Presidential Commission for the Study of Bioethical Issues in relation to professional ethics and research integrity issues raised by the Brain Research through Advancing Innovative Neurotechnologies (BRAIN) Initiative and other recent advances in neuroscience.
- Stevens, I., & Gilbert, F. (2022). International regulatory standards for the qualitative measurement of deep brain stimulation in clinical research. *Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics*, 17(3), 228-241.
- Stieglitz, T. (2021). Why Neurotechnologies? about the purposes, opportunities and limitations of neurotechnologies in clinical applications. *Neuroethics*, 14(1), 5-16.
- Stocchi, F. (2022). The role of law in regulating neurosciences: discrimination and inequality as major concerns.
- Stocchi, F. (2023). The need for a serious interdisciplinary approach to forensic neurotechnologies. A case study from an Italian court.

- Struić, G. (2023). The Regulation of Neurorights in National Legislation: What Should be Kept in Mind?. *British Journal of Philosophy, Sociology and History*, 3(2), 01-08.
- ter Gunne, R. M. P., Schellekens, M. I. M. H., & Röttiger-Wirtz, S. Finding the flaws in copyright when confronted with neuro-technologies and brain data.
- Terris, C. (2024). Moving beyond context: Reassessing privacy rights in the neurotechnology era. *AJOB neuroscience*, 15(2), 144-146.
- Ugwuoke, V. (2023). Neurotechnology and the Law; Privacy and Security Concerns. *Privacy and Security Concerns* (March 23, 2023).
- Ulnicane, I. (2020). Governance of Dual Use Research in the EU: The Case of Neuroscience. In *Emerging Security Technologies and EU Governance*. Taylor & Francis.
- Universität Wien (2024). Institut für Ethik und Recht in der Medizin, retrieved on January 8th, 2025, from <https://ierm.univie.ac.at/>
- Universität Wien (2024). Univ.-Prof. Dr. Karl Stöger, Abteilung Medizinrecht. retrieved on January 8th, 2025, from <https://staatsrecht.univie.ac.at/team/stoeger-karl/>
- Valera, L., & Bellver, V. (2023). Contemporary bioethical and legal perspectives on cognitive enhancement. In *The Routledge Handbook of the Ethics of Human Enhancement* (pp. 407-418). Routledge.
- van Slobbe, M. (2022). Freedom of thinking and neurotechnology: ensuring free thought in the age of brain-computer interfaces.
- Vasquez, P. C. (2024). Convergencia internacional y caminos propios: regulación de la inteligencia artificial en América Latina. *Actualidad jurídica iberoamericana*, (21), 468-493.
- Vöneky, S., & Schmidt, T. (2024). Regulating AI in non-military applications: lessons learned. In *Research Handbook on Warfare and Artificial Intelligence* (pp. 352-369). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Webster, H. S., & Sankary, L. R. (2023). Re-Routing Along the Path to Enshrine Global Neurorights. *AJOB neuroscience*, 14(4), 375-377.
- Winickoff, D. (2021, August). Neurotechnology at the OECD: The role of the private sector in governance. In *Annales des Mines-Réalités Industrielles* (No. 3, pp. 7-11). Cairn/Softwin.
- Wu, Z., & Cheng, L. (2024). *The EU Artificial Intelligence Act: Regulating Subliminal AI Systems*: by Rostam J. Neuwirth, London, Routledge, 2023, xiii+ 129 pp., £ 48.99 (cloth).
- Yoo, S. H., Choi, K., Nam, S., Yoon, E. K., Sohn, J. W., Oh, B. M., ... & Choi, M. Y. (2023). Development of Korea neuroethics guidelines. *Journal of Korean Medical Science*, 38(25).
- Zeinhofer, C. (2009). Der Anwendungsbereich des Gewebesicherheitsgesetzes. In Kopetzki (Ed.), *Gewebesicherheitsrecht* (pp. 98-140). Unknown publisher.
- Zúñiga-Fajuri, A., Miranda, L. V., Miralles, D. Z., & Venegas, R. S. (2021). Neurorights in Chile: Between neuroscience and legal science. *Developments in neuroethics and bioethics*, 4, 165-179.

9. Annexes

9.1. Events, Conferences and Memberships

Events:

- 2025, March 28th. *Global Neurotech Summit*. H*Quotient and Imperial College Neurotech Society. Online.
- 2025, April 7th. *CDR Event*. Önormen/ Austrian Standards KPMG Austria. KPMG Innsbruck.
- 2025, April 29. *Innovating in Healthcare and Medical Technologies*. LYEONS NeuroTech. Online.
- 2025, May 19th-23rd. *Neuroscience Week 2025 Hybrid Event*. University of York, Europe Campus, CITY College. Online and In-Person.
- 2025, September 10th. *Exploiting Attacker Cognitive Biases*. Cognitive Security Institute. Online.
- 2025, September 16th. *Cybersecurity - IT-Sicherheit für Medizinprodukte*. TÜV Süd Austria. Online.
- 2025, September 22nd. *Forum Roundtable: Regulatory Update für Medizinprodukte und IVD*. En.co.tec Schmid KG. Online.
- 2025, September 25th-26th. *2025 Brain Days*. Global Brain Coalition, European Brain Council and United Nations General Assembly. Online.
- 2025, September 30th. *Cyber Security Management*. TÜV Austria Academie. Online.

Memberships and Subscriptions:

- The Centre for Neurotechnology and Law. Membership. <https://www.neurotechlaw.com/>
- International Neuroethics Society Membership. <https://neuroethicssociety.org/membership/>
- ISACA Membership <https://www.isaca.org/membership>
- Neurosecurity - Where Infosec Meets Brain-Machine Interface Course. BSidesLV [Link](#)
- NeurotechEU Online Campus <https://nteucampus.org/>
- Cognitive Security Institute <https://www.cognitivesecurity.institute/join>

9.2. Supplementary Terminology

#	Important Vocabulary	Definition
1	Active vs Passive BCIs	“...A passive BCI merely interprets brain signals to give insight into an individual's cognitive state. For example, it may detect a user's emotional state during a consumer research study or training program. An active BCI requires users to actively modulate their brain signals to interact with an external device. For example, a user may imagine moving their arm, causing a robotic arm to move similarly.” (Emotiv, 2025)
2	Cognitive Liberty	The right of individuals to control their own mental processes, including “the right to alter one's mental states with the help of <u>neurotools</u> as well as to refuse to do so” (Bublitz 2013, p. 234)
3	Brainjacking	“unauthorized control of an electronic brain implant” (Pycroft, 2016, p.1)
4	Brain Data	“Data that are recorded directly or indirectly from an individual's brain, such as with brain imaging, intracranial recordings, or a brain computer interface.” (UNESCO, 2021, p.78)
5	Structural vs. Functional Brain Scans	“...Structural, such as MRI scans, deals with, as the name suggests, the structure of the brain... They are used by researchers to understand brain anatomy. Functional brain scans are used to indirectly measure brain functions, such as neural activity.” (Emotiv, 2025)
6	Cognitive vs Mental Health	“Cognitive health as a general umbrella can refer to brain health. Mental health is one subset of brain health which patients and doctors should closely monitor to care for their well-being. Cognitive and mental health are closely related within the study and care of mental health.” (Emotiv, 2025)
7	Cognitive Science vs Neuroscience	“Cognitive science is the scientific study of thought, learning, and the human mind. Neuroscience is the scientific study of the nervous system.” (Emotiv, 2025)
8	Behavioral vs. Cognitive Neuroscience	“Cognitive refers to thoughts. Behavioral refers to actions. Cognitive Neuroscience is the study of the biological basis of cognition.” (Emotiv, 2025)

9.3. Hacking the Mind: A Step-by-Step Guide to Building a BCI

Hacking the Mind: A Step-by-Step Guide to Building a BCI³¹⁹

What would you need?

1	PiEEG-16	\$390	Link
2	ThinkPulse™ Active Electrode Add-on Kits	\$435,95	Link
3	Raspberry Pi 4 Model B, High Case	\$18	Link
4	Raspberry Pi 4 Computer Model B 8GB Single Board	\$82,21	Link
5	3D Printing PLA Filament	\$13,99	Link
6	Power Distributor	\$7,90	Link
7	Other cables and materials	~\$65	

For approximately \$1014 (3D Printer not included), a Linux or Python online course and/or the help of Chat GPT, you can create your own NT.

Instructions available in the following link: <https://mindgardenai.com/blog/2024-09-11-lets-build-a-bci/>

³¹⁹ Mind Garden AI, 2025.

9.4. Future Educational Modules in this Area

Legal Neurotechnology Curriculum*

Module	Key Topics Covered
Module 1: Foundational Concepts in Neurotechnology and Law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to Neurotechnology • Principles of Neurolaw • Neuroethics and Neurorights
Module 2: Neurotechnology in the Courtroom and Legal Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criminal Responsibility and the Brain • Criminal Law and Civil law systems.
Module 3: Regulation and Policy of Neurotechnology (EU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Law, focused on EU Regulations: GDPR, MDR, AIA, GPSR, DMA, DSA, RED, CRA and NIS2. • Other Digital Legislations worldwide, as FDA (USA), LGPD (Brazil), etc.

Neurotech Legal Cybersecurity Curriculum*

Module	Key Topics Covered
Module 1: The Cybersecurity of the Brain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to Cybersecurity, Brain Data Security and Neurosecurity • Ethical AI and Technology Principles • Threats and Vulnerabilities for Neurotechnologies • Ethical Hacking and Defence Mechanisms • Neuro "Security-by-Design" principles.
Module 2: Legal and Regulatory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Overview of the Digital Law, specially on EU Regulations: GDPR, MDR, AIA, GPSR, DMA, DSA, RED, CRA and NIS2. • General Overview of other Digital Legislations worldwide, as FDA (USA), LGPD (Brazil), etc.
Module 3: Governance and Future of Neuro-Cybersecurity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cybercrime and Novel Neuro-attacks • Cybersecurity Governance and Risk Management Frameworks, like NIST, ISACA, ISO, etc. • Final Project

Neurotechnology Cybersecurity Curriculum

Module	Key Topics Covered
Current Methods (Source: Ruiz- Vanoye)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Anonymization • Blockchain protection uses • NT Access Control • Data Encryption • NT Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) • Plus, all Hardware, Software, Network and Cloud Cybersecurity methods.*
Future-Focused Methods (Source: Ruiz- Vanoye)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brain Firewalls • Advanced Encryption for Brain Data • Neuro-Consent Interfaces • Cognitive Liberty Guardians, autonomous AI Systems • Electromagnetic Shields • Integrated Security Implants, with self-deactivation capabilities
Other Considerations*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post-quantum security measures • Proactive prevention to future technologies and vulnerabilities

* Author's recommendations

9.5. Recommended Related ISO Standards³²⁰

Recommended ISO Standards for Neurotechnology

ISO/IEC	Recommended ISOs for NTs	General Description
27001:2022	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Information security management systems — Requirements	World's best-known standard for information security management systems (ISMS). It defines requirements an ISMS must meet, with guidance for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving an information security management system.
24741:2024	Information technology — Biometrics — Overview and application	This document describes the history and purpose of biometrics, the various biometric technologies in general use today (for example, fingerprint recognition, face recognition and iris recognition) and the architecture of the systems and the system processes that allow automated recognition using those technologies. It makes references to other ISO/IEC Standards as the 18584, 19784, 19792, 19794, 20027, 22604, 24708, 24709, 24713, 24745, 29109, 29164, 29196, 29794, 30106, 30107, 30137 and 39794, also biometrics-related.
11073-40102:2022	Health informatics — Device interoperability Part 40102: Foundational — Cybersecurity — Capabilities for mitigation	Within the context of secure plug-and-play interoperability, cybersecurity is the process and capability of preventing unauthorized access or modification, misuse, denial of use, or the unauthorized use of information that is stored on, accessed from, or transferred to and from a PHD/PoCD.
TR 27599:2025	Information technology — Brain-computer interfaces — Use cases	This document provides a collection of representative use cases of brain-computer interface (BCI) applications in a variety of domains: proposed medical and health, industrial controls, smart environment, etc.
ISO 15223	Medical devices — Symbols to be used with information to be supplied by the manufacturer — Part 1: General requirements	Specifies the symbols manufacturers must use on labels, packaging, and accompanying documentation for medical devices. The symbols are designed to convey essential information about the product's safe and effective use, regardless of language. This includes symbols for a product's sterile status, manufacturer, expiration date, and more.
ISO 16142	Medical devices — Recognized essential principles of safety and performance of medical devices	Provides a framework of essential principles that a medical device must meet to be considered safe and to perform as intended. It serves as a guide for manufacturers to ensure their products are designed and produced in a way that minimizes risk and maintains clinical effectiveness. This standard is often used by regulatory bodies to assess conformity and is foundational to many national medical device regulations.
ISO 81001	Health informatics — Safety, effectiveness and security of health software and health IT systems	A standard that provides a framework for managing safety and security risks throughout the lifecycle of health applications and devices.
ISO 14971	Medical devices — Application of risk management to medical devices	The international standard for risk management for medical devices. It outlines the process manufacturers must follow to identify, evaluate, and control risks associated with their devices.
ISO 24971	Medical devices — Guidance on the application of ISO 14971	A technical report that provides guidance on the application of the ISO 14971 standard. It clarifies the concepts and provides examples for implementing the medical device risk management process.
ISO/IEC 13485	Medical devices — Quality management systems — Requirements for regulatory purposes	The international standard for Quality Management Systems (QMS) for medical devices. It specifies requirements for organizations involved in the lifecycle of a medical device to ensure consistent product safety and quality.
ISO/IEC 27034	Information technology — Security techniques — Application security	A standard for application security. It provides a framework for integrating security into the entire lifecycle of software applications, from design and development to deployment and maintenance.
ISO/IEC 29147	Information technology — Security techniques — Vulnerability disclosure	A standard on vulnerability disclosure. It outlines a structured process for vendors to receive, assess, and act on reports of security vulnerabilities in their products or services.
ISO/IEC 30111	Information technology — Security techniques — Vulnerability handling processes	A standard on vulnerability handling processes. It provides guidance for vendors on how to handle vulnerability information, including communication, coordination, and remediation.
ISO 20924	IoT-Reference Architecture	A published international standard that provides a vocabulary and definition of Internet of Things (IoT) and digital twin. It serves as a foundational terminology for other IoT-related standards.
ISO 29341	Standard für Universal Plug and Play	A series of standards related to UPnP (Universal Plug and Play) Device Architecture. It defines an architecture for pervasive peer-to-peer network connectivity of devices, allowing for seamless and automatic discovery in networks.
CD 8663	Information technology — Brain-computer interfaces — Vocabulary	A Committee Draft for an ISO standard. Not yet released
CD TS 27571	Information technology — Brain-computer interfaces — BCI data format for non-invasive brain information collection	A Committee Draft Technical Specification. Not yet released
CD 27572	Information technology — Brain-computer interfaces — Reference architecture	A Committee Draft on Reference architecture. Not yet released
Other regional or national certifications		

Source: Collected from ISO Standards page, Gemini recommendations and associations between them.

³²⁰ ISO, 2025.

9.6. Cultural Bonus

Die Gedanken sind frei – Thoughts are free ³²¹

Author: Unknown (around 1780, some say they can be found since the 13th century)

Music: August Heinrich Hoffmann von Fallersleben and Ernst Heinrich Leopold Richter (1842)

Lyrics in German:

Die Gedanken sind frei,
wer kann sie erraten,
sie fliegen vorbei,
wie nächtliche Schatten.
Kein Mensch kann sie wissen,
kein Jäger erschießen.
Es bleibet dabei:
Die Gedanken sind frei.

Und sperrt man mich ein
im finsternen Kerker,
das alles sind rein
vergebliche Werke,
denn meine Gedanken
zerreißen die Schranken
und Mauern entzwei:
die Gedanken sind frei.

Ich denke, was ich will,
und was mich beglückt,
doch alles in der Still,
und wie es sich schicket.
Mein Wunsch und Begehren
kann niemand verwehren,
es bleibet dabei:
Die Gedanken sind frei.

Drum will ich auf immer
den Sorgen entsagen
und will mich auch nimmer
mit Grillen mehr plagen.
Mann kann ja im Herzen
stets lachen und scherzen
und denken dabei:
Die Gedanken sind frei.

Lyrics in English:

Thoughts are free, who can guess them? They fly by like night shadows.
No one can know them, no hunter can shoot them.
It remains this: Thoughts are free.

I think what I want, and what makes me happy,
but all in silence, and as is fitting.
No one can deny my wishes and desires, it remains this: thoughts are free.

And if they lock me up in a dark dungeon, all these are purely futile efforts,
for my thoughts tear down the barriers and walls: thoughts are free.

Therefore, I will forever renounce worries and will never torment myself with whims again.
One can always laugh and joke in one's heart and think at the same time:
Thoughts are free.

³²¹ Hoffmann von Fallersleben.